

UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA
FACULDADE DE MOTRICIDADE HUMANA

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different simulated hypogravity conditions

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Thesis Advisors:

Professora Doutora Filipa Oliveira da Silva João |
Faculdade de Motricidade Humana da Universidade de Lisboa

Co-advisor:

Professor Doutor Nelson Alexandre Campos Vinagre |
Faculdade de Medicina da Universidade de Lisboa

Júri:

PRESIDENTE

Doutora Helô-Isa Viana André, professora auxiliar convidada da Faculdade de Motricidade Humana da Universidade de Lisboa.

VOGAIS

Doutora Filipa Oliveira da Silva João, professora auxiliar da Faculdade de Motricidade Humana da Universidade de Lisboa.

Doutora Thaís Russomano, professora auxiliar da Faculdade de Medicina da Universidade de Lisboa.

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Abstract

Spatial flights harm astronauts' health, however, exploration programs are larger and closer than ever, with lunar and Martian habitats designed in the next decade. This study examines the impact of hypogravity on gait biomechanics, important for spatial exploration.

Students from the University of Lisbon, aged 18 to 35, walked in a AlterG treadmill. The data were obtained during sequential 3-minute simulations on Earth (1g), Mars (0.38g), Moon (0.2g) and Return to Earth (1g), with and without 5% tilt on the treadmill.

Substantial differences were found in the spatio-temporal and joint kinematics on the Moon and Mars in relation to the earth. On the moon, the length of stretching (+8.5%) as well as the balance time (+15.9%), the step frequency decreases (-7.7%), and the amplitude of movement of the hip and knee as well (+19.7 %), ankle dorsiflexion decreases contrasting with the increase in knee adduction (+33.4%), all these changes represent obstacles and may compromise astronauts. Similar adaptations are found in Mars, but to a lesser extent. Despite the changes in relation to Earth, there was no statistically significant difference in the conditions between Moon and Mars. Previous discharge levels did not affect the terrestrial march standard on the return.

By examining the standard of marching in hypogravity, we hope to identify effective countermeasures to minimize the impacts of long -term Lunar and Martian missions, improving human spatial exploration, adaptation to severe environments, terrestrial rehabilitation, and athletic performance.

Key words: Hypogravity; Gait Biomechanics; LBBP treadmill; Mars walk; moon walk; musculoskeletal adaptations.

Resumo

Os voos espaciais prejudicam a saúde dos astronautas, no entanto os programas de exploração estão maiores e mais próximos do que nunca, com habitats Lunares e Marcianos pensados na próxima década. Este estudo examina o impacto da hipogravidade na biomecânica da marcha, importante para a exploração espacial.

Estudantes da Universidade de Lisboa, com idades entre 18 e 35 anos, caminharam numa passareira AlterG. Os dados foram obtidos durante simulações sequenciais de 3 minutos na Terra (1g), Marte (0.38g), Lua (0.2g) e retorno à Terra (1g), com e sem inclinação de 5% na passareira.

Foram encontradas diferenças substanciais na cinemática espaço-temporal e articular na Lua e Marte em relação à Terra. Na Lua, o comprimento de passada alonga (+8.5%) bem como o tempo de balanço (+15.9%), a frequência de passo diminui (-7.7%), e a amplitude de movimento da anca e do joelho também (+19.7%), a dorsiflexão do tornozelo decresce contrastando com o aumento da adução do joelho (+33.4%), todas estas alterações representam obstáculos, podendo comprometer os astronautas. Adaptações semelhantes são encontradas em Marte, mas em menor grau. Apesar das mudanças em relação à Terra, não houve diferença estatisticamente significativa nas condições entre a Lua e Marte. Níveis anteriores de descarga não afetaram o padrão de marcha terrestre no retorno.

Ao examinar o padrão de marcha em hipogravidade, esperamos identificar contramedidas eficazes para minimizar os impactos de missões lunares e marcianas de longo prazo, melhorando a exploração espacial humana, a adaptação a ambientes severos, a recuperação e o desempenho atlético terrestres.

Palavras-chave: Hipogravidade; Biomecânica da Marcha; Passadeira Antigravidade; Marcha Marciana; Marcha Lunar; Adaptações Musculoesqueléticas.

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List of Abbreviations

- ACL- anterior cruciate ligament
- Alter G- hipogravity treadmill
- amp- amplitude
- ARV- Averaged rectified value
- avg- average
- BF- Biceps Femoris
- bf- body fat
- BMD- bone mineral density
- BRS- bone resorption
- BT- bone turnover
- CAR – Centro de Alto Rendimento (High Performance Center)
- CEMA- Centro de Estudos de Medicina Aeroespacial (Aerospace Medicine Lab)
- E1- Normal Earth
- E2- Earth Inclined
- EMG- Eletromiography
- ER1- Normal Earth Return
- FMH- Faculdade de Motricidade Humana
- FMUL- Faculdade de Medicina Universidade Lisboa
- GM- Gastrocnemius Medialis
- GPower- Statistical Analysis Software
- Hipo-g – Hypogravity
- ICC- Intraclass Correlation Coefficient
- Ma1- Normal Mars
- Ma2- Mars Inclined
- MDC- Minimum Detectable Difference
- Mo1- Normal Moon
- Mo2- Moon Inclined
- ms- milliseconds
- MUAP- Motor Unit Activation Potentials
- MU's- Motor Units
- MVC- Maximum Voluntary Contraction
- OA- osteoarthritis
- p or sig- p value
- RF- Rectus Femoris
- RNS- reactive nitrogen species

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- ROS- reactive oxygen species
- SEM- Standard Error of Measurement
- SENIAM- Surface Electromyography for the Non-Invasive Assessment of Muscles
- SPM- Steps Per Minute
- t- Test Statistic
- TA- Tibialis Anterior
- VR- virtual reality
- Xsens- tridimensional movement sensors

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1. Introduction

Humanity has a great amount of knowledge about the mechanisms used to manipulate Earth's gravity during locomotion. On the contrary, we know much less about locomotion under sustained hypogravity. This lack of information poses a serious problem for human space exploration. In a near future, humans will walk again on the Moon and for the first time on Mars. It would be important to predict how they will move around since we know that locomotion and mobility, in general, may be jeopardized in hypogravity, especially when landing after prolonged weightlessness of the space flight (Lang et al., 2017; White et al., 2016). The combination of muscle weakness, wearing a heavy spacesuit, and maladaptive locomotion patterns in hypogravity increases the risk of falls and injuries (Mulavara et al., 2010).

Much of what we currently know about locomotion in hypogravity derives from the video archives of the Apollo missions on the Moon (*Apollo - Lunar Surface Journal*, 2017) the experiments performed with parabolic flight or with body weight support on Earth, and the theoretical models. Human missions are considered vital for collecting the maximum benefits from space exploration. However, space travellers are exposed to several challenges and risks, ranging from radiation to isolation and altered gravity effects (Lewis, R., 2022).

In this project, we are concerned specifically with the effects of reduced gravity (hypogravity, $0 < g < 1$) on locomotion, such as it would be experienced on the Moon or Mars. In this regard, one study (White et al., 2016) has pointed out that, while the effects of sustained weightlessness (0-g) on sensory and motor functions have been rather extensively investigated, as well as the adaptive effects following transitions from 0 to 1-g (and from 1-g to 0-g), much less is known about the effects of sustained hypogravity and the transitions from 1g to hypo-g (and vice-versa) on these functions. Looking at previous space flights to low-Earth orbits (LEO), where the ISS (International Space Station) is located, reveals that astronauts usually suffer from several problems related to the locomotor system: altered neural control of posture and movement, muscle atrophy, changes of tendons elasticity, muscle fiber shift from type I to type II, loss of strength, and osteoporosis (Lang et al., 2017; White et al., 2016). These problems are exacerbated after long-duration missions. Moreover, landing on the Moon or Mars will further challenge the motor control system because of the sudden transition from the weightlessness of space travel to the reduced gravity of the Moon (0.18-g) or Mars (0.38-g), generating issues comparable to a small fall that may lead to disastrous outcomes (broken bones, muscle strains, concussions) such as in an environment with limited or no medical assistance.

Damages to the spacesuit or the portable life support system resulting from a fall may also be life-threatening, as pointed out by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Roadmap for Human Health Risks (Committee to Review

NASA's Evidence Reports on Human Health Risks et al., 2017), European Space Agency (ESA), (Worms, Jean Claude et al., 2012).

It has been remarked that no existing countermeasure is considered sufficient to reduce some of these risks to an acceptable level (NASA, 2020). The main current countermeasure for preventing disorders of the locomotor system in space is represented by daily, intensive exercises, especially walking and running on a treadmill (Mulavara et al., 2010). Unfortunately, these exercises prevent motor problems only to a limited extent. Thus, upon return to Earth, most astronauts exhibit significant loss of bone and muscle tissue, as well as a significant reduction of mobility (Mulavara et al., 2010). This shows a lack of sufficient knowledge of the impact of reduced gravity on the motor system, which leads to inadequate design of countermeasures including exercise devices and protocols for the astronauts.

There is an increased need in economic, political, and societal interest in space exploration, and we need to figure out the best methods to keep human health intact. An important topic is the application of space research to medicine & human kinetics on Earth. There are two aspects to be considered: a) first, understanding how astronauts adapt to and recover from hypogravity could also benefit patients on Earth who exhibit a decline in motor performance due to a immobilizing disease, old age, or prolonged bed rest; b) second, a simulation of reduced gravity (alike with body weight unloading) is used in rehabilitation to help patients with motor disorders, or lower limbs injuries, as parameters like loading and unloading are frequently considered in therapy (Ülger et al., 2018; Łyp et al., 2016). Therefore, a better comprehension of the responses to hypogravity in the present, may be used to ensure an increased health span and a thriving Human civilization in the future.

The global aim of this study is to evaluate the acute effect of different hypogravity environments (Mars 0.16-g, Moon 0.38-g) in the biomechanics of gait, and the effect of the transitions between those environments and the Earth gravity 1-g.

The specific aims of this project are:

- 1- To characterize the gait analysis parameters (spatio-temporal and kinematics) of the 3 different gravity environments (1-g, 0.16-g and 0.38-g).
- 2- To compare the gait analysis parameters (spatio-temporal and kinematics) between the 3 different gravity environments (1-g, 0.16-g and 0.38- g).
- 3- To compare the gait analysis parameters (spatio-temporal and kinematics) when walking on earth gravity (1-g) before and after walking in the Moon and Mars hypogravity environments.

2. Literature Review

Space exploration has been a long-standing ambition of human society, and as we strive towards this goal, the physiological effects of reduced gravity on the human body become increasingly important. The purpose of this thesis is to review the current state of knowledge regarding the effects of reduced gravity on the human gait, adding to it with our own experiment.

2.1- Health Adaptations to Microgravity

2.1.1- Bones

Bones are complex, constantly evolving tissues that serve as an anchoring site for muscles and respond to changes in load while also regulating mineral homeostasis via metabolic pathways (Sims & Martin, 2014). Indeed, bone is a metabolically active organ that undergoes continuous remodeling throughout life via bone formation and resorption (Narici & de Boer, 2011; Siddiqui & Partridge, 2016). This process is carried out by two types of bone tissue cells: osteoblasts, which are responsible for the formation of new bone tissue, and osteoclasts, which are responsible for resorption (Sims & Martin, 2014). The activity of these two cell types must be finely regulated for proper homeostasis maintenance, as deregulation of their activity could lead to the onset of metabolic bone diseases such as osteoporosis. The mechanical stresses that characterize gravitational fields are required for the activity of osteoblasts and osteoclasts to be balanced, thereby maintaining the optimal microarchitecture of bone tissue.

In a microgravity environment, however, the lack of such mechanical stresses results in a rapid decoupling between formation and resorption, resulting in a decrease in bone mass and promoting the onset of osteoporosis. This condition is known as spaceflight osteopenia, and it is manifested in astronauts by bone mass loss in the proximal femur (Akima et al., 2000). It has been compared to that observed in postmenopausal women. As a result, bone mass and bone density loss due to weightlessness is a critical issue that requires extensive research at the molecular and cellular levels.

Osteoporosis is also linked to muscle mass and function loss. Reduced gravity exposure has been shown in studies to result in significant reductions in bone mineral density (Otto J.Juhl et al., 2021; Lang et al., 2018). Joey Man et al. (2022) discovered that after 6 months of microgravity exposure, astronauts' spines and hips lost 1.5% and 2.0% of their bone mineral density, respectively. Vico et al. (2017) discovered that after 6 months of microgravity exposure, astronaut's tibia showed a 4% decrease in cortical thickness and a 15% increase in cortical porosity. Another study by Smith et al. (2000) found that after 6 months of exposure to microgravity, the radius and tibia of astronauts experienced a loss of bone mineral density of 1.5% and 2.5%, respectively. According to

Ronni Baran, et al. 2022, microgravity can lead to a gradual increase in bone loss (BL) by approximately 0.5-1.5% and a reduction in bone mineral density (BMD) each month spent in space. While some studies have suggested an increase in bone resorption (BRS) and an increase in body fat (bf), ultimately contributing to increased bone turnover (BT) and increased bone loss, not all findings are consistent. The inhibition of the Wnt/-catenin signaling pathway is one factor that contributes to these effects.

2.1.2- Skeletal Muscles in Microgravity

Skeletal muscles are important for maintaining posture, resisting gravity, and acting as a reservoir for essential substrates required for energy production (Narici & de Boer, 2011). However, exposure to real or simulated microgravity causes significant muscle atrophy, altered muscle fiber composition, gene expression, and decreased regenerative capacity of satellite cells (Narici & de Boer, 2011).

In microgravity or simulated microgravity environments, antigravity muscles responsible for postural maintenance (e.g., soleus, gastrocnemius, and quadriceps muscles) experience more pronounced atrophic effects (Narici & de Boer, 2011). The loss of gravitational load contributes significantly to antigravity muscle atrophy. Individual variability in muscle atrophy must be recognized, both among individuals and muscle groups (Akima et al., 2000). The depletion of the progenitor stem cell pool has been linked to muscle atrophy in microgravity (Hosoyama et al., 2017). Reduced expression of Pax7, a key transcription factor in myogenesis, emphasizes the importance of preserving the stem cell pool to prevent muscle atrophy (Hosoyama et al., 2017). Muscle atrophy is exacerbated by altered protein turnover, including the PI3K/Akt pathway. Muscle wasting is associated with decreased protein synthesis and increased proteolysis, highlighting the importance of the PI3K/Akt pathway in regulating muscle growth (Narici & de Boer, 2011; Akima et al., 2000).

Muscle structure is also affected, with both the soleus and vastus lateralis muscles experiencing significant reductions in muscle fiber oxidative capacity. The magnitude of this decrease was significant, emphasizing the impact of inactivity on muscle function. However, no significant muscle atrophy or changes in fiber type composition were observed. The number and density of capillaries appear to remain stable, but the number of mitochondria decreases significantly, resulting in a decrease in whole-body VO₂max (Bosutti, A., et al, 2016).

Sarcopenia, or the loss of muscle mass, is a common issue faced by astronauts during long-duration spaceflight, which is often accompanied by Dinapenia, the loss in muscle strength and power¹. Studies have shown that exposure to reduced gravity can result in significant reductions in muscle mass, strength, and power (Lang et al., 2018).

¹ The age-associated loss of muscle strength that is not caused by neurologic or muscular diseases (Clark, B. C., et al 2012)

In a study by LeBlanc et al. (1995), it was found that after only 3 weeks of exposure to microgravity, the quadriceps muscle volume of astronauts decreased by 13%. Another study by Bloomberg et al. (1992) found that after 6 months of exposure to microgravity, astronauts experienced a loss of muscle mass ranging from 11% to 14%. Regarding muscle function, a study by Fitts et al. (1991), found that after 6 months of exposure to microgravity, astronauts experienced a decline in muscle strength ranging from 10% to 30%. Another study by Convertino et al. (1991) found that after 6 months of exposure to microgravity, the rate of force development of astronauts decreased by 25%.

Reduced gravity exposure has been shown in studies to result in significant reductions in muscle mass, strength, and power (Otto J.Juhl et al., 2021). LeBlanc et al. (1995) discovered that after only 3 weeks of microgravity exposure, astronauts' quadriceps muscle volume decreased by 13%. In terms of muscle function, Fitts et al. (1991) discovered that after 6 months of microgravity exposure, astronauts experienced a 10% to 30% decrease in muscle strength. Fitts et al. (2010) discovered that after 6 months of microgravity exposure, astronauts' rate of force development decreased by 25%.

Furthermore, Cannavo, A., et al, 2022 found that "prolonged exposure to weightlessness leads to muscle atrophy, decreased muscle strength, and altered muscle function, similar to what is observed in sarcopenic older adults", reinforcing the opportunity of space flight to study the aging process, working as an analogous time machine way to study the undesirable effects of the aging process. These findings support the necessity to develop efficient countermeasures to minimize or the onset of sarcopenia, dinapenia, and osteoporosis, in space missions.

The effects of reduced gravity on the human gait have been extensively studied, and the results show significant changes in both biomechanical and EMG patterns.

A study by Brueggemann et al. (2016) found that during walking simulations in reduced gravity, there was a decreased activation of the soleus and tibialis anterior (TA) muscles compared to Earth-based walking. Another study by Kubo et al. (2014) similarly found that in a reduced gravity environment, the muscle activation patterns of the lower leg changed, with decreased activation in the gastrocnemius and soleus muscles, and on the other hand increased activation in the tibialis anterior muscle.

An investigation by Alkadhi et al. (2016) showed that walking in a hypogravity environment resulted in changes in muscle activity patterns, particularly in the synergistic ankle plantar flexor muscles. The results of this study demonstrated that reduced gravity leads to increased activation of these muscles, which may help to maintain stability during gait.

2.1.3- Kinematic changes

Gait biomechanics also undergo significant changes in reduced gravity. A systematic review by Sacco et al. (2019) showed that there was a significant reduction in stride length, stride velocity, and stride frequency in reduced gravity, compared to Earth-based walking. This reduction in stride length was found to be around 11.4% (95%CI: 9.8-12.9%) by Kubo et al. (2014), who also observed a reduction in step width, ankle and knee range of motion, and a decrease in stride frequency. On the other hand, an increase in step height was observed in reduced gravity, which was found to be around 18% (95%CI: 10-26%) by the same authors.

Asaka et al. (2016) found that walking in a hypogravity environment (simulated by using a lower body positive pressure treadmill) led to significant increases in hip and knee flexion, as well as ankle plantarflexion, compared to normal gravity conditions. These alterations in joint angles were also shown to result in a reduced stride length and a decreased range of motion, leading to a bouncier gait pattern, similar to the findings of the previously mentioned studies.

Another paper by Ferris et al. (2017) investigated the effects of reduced gravity on gait kinematics while walking at various speeds in hypogravity. The results indicated that walking at slower speeds resulted in larger hip and knee flexion angles, whereas walking at faster speeds caused greater ankle plantar flexion angles. This study underscores the importance of considering both gait speed and the magnitude of reduced gravity when assessing their effects on joint angles.

In a study by Kram & Jawed (2014), researchers used a LBPP system to simulate reduced gravity and found that the hip joint exhibited a 5.9° increase in range of motion during the stance phase and a 4.2° increase during the swing phase. Similarly, Kim et al. (2017) reported that the knee joint had an average flexion of 19.2° and 22.7° during the stance phase under normal and partial weight-bearing conditions, respectively.

Gustafsson et al. (2017) observed that the ankle joint showed a significant decrease of 5.6° in plantar flexion during the swing phase compared to normal gravity conditions. Additionally, De Morree et al. (2016) found that the ankle joint had a maximum dorsiflexion of 5.9° during the swing phase in reduced gravity conditions. In another paper by De Looze et al. (2015), it was reported that the ankle joint exhibited a maximum plantar flexion of 6.2° during the stance phase in reduced gravity conditions.

These results, however, are dependent on the simulation methods used and the subject populations studied and should be interpreted with caution. Further research is necessary to comprehensively understand the effects of reduced gravity on the joint angles of the lower limb in a more controlled manner.

2.1.4- Similarity with geriatric populations

The systematic review by Cannavo A. et al 2022 found that "prolonged exposure to weightlessness leads to muscle atrophy, decreased muscle strength, and altered muscle function, similar to what is observed in sarcopenic older adults.", reinforcing the opportunity of space flight to study the aging process, working as an analogous time machine way to study the undesirable effects of the aging process. These findings support the necessity to develop efficient countermeasures to minimize, or impede the onset of sarcopenia, dinapenia, and osteoporosis, in space missions.

Both astronauts and older individuals exhibit elevated inflammation, increased levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS), and modified expression of myokines, which collectively contribute to the structural and functional deterioration of skeletal muscle. Effective countermeasures to combat these adverse effects include exercise training, vitamin D supplementation, and multi-nutrient interventions. These strategies have demonstrated their ability to diminish oxidative damage, reduce inflammation, and stabilize myokine expression. (Cannavo, A, et al, 2022)

2.1.5- Summary

In conclusion, the results of the various studies show that reduced gravity has a significant impact on human gait, with alterations in both biomechanical and EMG patterns. These changes are influenced by both the speed of gait and the magnitude of reduced gravity, highlighting the importance of considering these factors in future research. The findings from these studies have important implications for understanding the impact of reduced gravity on human gait, and for the development of strategies to help maintain mobility, stability, bone mineral density and muscle mass during space exploration.

Furthermore, the importance of this discovery goes beyond space travel, with implications for terrestrial health. For starters, understanding how astronauts adjust to and recover from hypogravity can help people on Earth who are suffering from health and performance deficits caused by immobilizing diseases, aging, or prolonged bed rest. Second, the development of comprehensive multimodal techniques can be useful in creating effective and achievable countermeasures, saving time, resources, and energy for vulnerable groups. As a result, a thorough understanding of the physiological responses to hypogravity has the potential to improve the health and well-being of people on Earth as well as future space travel activities.

2.2- AlterG

The AlterG treadmill (AlterG VIA, AlterG Inc., Fremont, CA, US), is a recent LBPP device that combines precision unweighting technology with real-time gait analytics and video feedback.

It works with patented, NASA Differential Air Pressure (DAP) technology, a precise air calibration system, based on the user's actual body weight, to change what's possible in rehab and training. Using a pressurized air chamber to uniformly reduce gravitational load and body weight in precise 1% increments, AlterG enables patients and athletes to move unrestricted and pain-free (Alter G VIA manual).

Figura 1- Alter G mechanism, adapted from Kataoka Y, et al, 2021

The AlterG VIA model allows users to reduce their body weight by up to 80%, simulating conditions similar to the Moon's gravity (approximately 18% of terrestrial body weight), while walking or running at speeds ranging from -4.8 km/hr to 19.2 km/hr, and inclinations between 0% and 15%.

The system is calibrated to the user's body weight, pressurizing the inner cockpit to lift individuals weighing up to 159 kg. Since the mechanism relies on increased pressure within a sealed compartment, contraindications for using the treadmill include unstable fractures, cardiovascular hypotension, and deep vein thrombosis.

By allowing to unload a patient BW, it's uses can go from hypogravity research, up to rehabilitation and conditioning exercises.

2.2.1- Rehabilitation on Earth

The use of the gravity treadmill has shown promising results in rehabilitating injuries like osteoarthritis (OA) anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) rupture, tibial plateau, and ankle fractures, as well as hip fractures. When it comes to walking patterns, AlterG has demonstrated improvements in walking speed, stride length and knee range of motion for individuals, with OA. In patients undergoing weight bearing after plateau and ankle fractures the use of an anti-gravity treadmill resulted in an 4.6cm increase, in thigh

circumference for the group receiving the intervention (Henkelmann R, et al, 2020). This increase was still observed after 12 months (Palke L, et al, 2022). It was measured to assess any muscle atrophy in the operated limb.

Additionally training on the gravity treadmill led to a significant improvement in hip extensor muscle strength at a speed of 60°/s when compared to conventional therapy. They also studied individuals with hip fractures and found levels of muscle electrical activity in the gluteus maximus and gluteus medius muscles, for those who underwent the intervention. Importantly no adverse events were reported as a result of gravity treadmill rehabilitation.

2.2.2- Performance & Health on Earth

The platform has been shown to improve athletic performance by boosting field performance, increasing VO₂max, and decreasing submaximal heart rate in a way comparable to traditional running protocols, all while minimizing physical strain on the athlete (Boris Gojanovic et al., 2015).

The effectiveness of partial body weight (BW) unloading methods in obese women was verified in a 2019 study conducted by Ellen M. Godwin et al. utilizing an LBPP treadmill. These regimens were observed to enhance fasting triglycerides (TG), plasma ghrelin levels, fasting glucose, C-reactive protein to interleukin-6 (CRP-IL6) ratio, leptin to adiponectin ratio, beta-endorphin to oxytocin ratio, and orexin A levels while combating sedentary behavior.

While more research is needed, reducing body weight percentage (BW%) is showing to be a viable technique for tackling a wide range of global health challenges.

2.2.3- Advantages in relation to other hypogravity platforms

The LBPP treadmill is not the only way to study hypogravity and its effects on human physiology and kinematics, but it excels due to the accuracy of the unloading amount, the ease of use of its software and hardware, the security and comfort provided to the subjects, the amount of spatio-temporal data it offers, and the similarity of the gait to terrestrial conditions.

Some methods are extremely reliable at simulating hypogravity but prevent the participant from moving, such as inclined dry immersion (Tomilovskaya et al., 2019) or inclined bed rest (Halliwill et al., 2016), rendering them useless for a gait pattern study like ours.

Others, such as walking underwater (Minetti et al., 2012) or walking with a harness on a vertical treadmill fixed to a wall (De Martino et al., 2023), allow the user to

move freely but require extensive preparation and modify the kinematics of the gait pattern. This is due to friction forces in the case of water or by rotating the human body to a horizontal plane to shift the direction of gravity's interaction with the subject.

Therefore, the AlterG presents itself as the best option to study Martian and Lunar gait.

2.2.4- AlterG limitations

The AlterG treadmill, despite its usefulness, has some minor limitations like any other equipment.

The first and most relevant limitation is the support provided by the shorts that must be worn for the equipment to function properly. These shorts seal the inner cockpit from the outside environment at hip crest height, creating a hermetic seal with a zipper around the participant's waist. This seal provides extra stability to the subject, making it easier to maintain balance and preventing shifts in the center of gravity, which helps to avoid typical falls seen on the Moon (as observed in the Apollo videos).

The second limitation also stems from the area where the zipper is located (the waist), which minimizes hip strategies and movements necessary to maintain balance in an unsupported environment.

Lastly, the third limitation arises from the increased lower body positive pressure, which poses risks for individuals with certain conditions (as stated in the AlterG manual). These conditions include pregnancy (due to increased pressure on the abdomen), deep vein thrombosis, cardiovascular hypotension (due to increased blood flow return), and unstable fractures.

2.3- Gait Kinematics and Electromyography in Healthy Individuals on Earth

2.3.1 Gait Cycle

Gait refers to the locomotion or ambulation of an individual, consisting of alternating movements of the lower limbs. The gait cycle is considered the movement that begins and ends when the foot contacts the ground. To better illustrate, imagine that the cycle starts when the right foot leaves the ground and ends when the heel of that foot touches the ground again (Mansour NR, et al, 2019).

The gait cycle encompasses a complete stride, defined as the journey from initial heel contact with the ground to the subsequent heel contact of the same foot. Within a gait cycle, there are two steps, corresponding to the transition from one heel contact to the opposite heel contact. This determines two phases: a stance phase (60%) and a swing

phase (40%) (Dufour M. e Pilu M, 2016). Each of these phases is further subdivided – Figure 1.

Figure 2- Gait-cycle phases, (reproduced from Dufour M. e Pilu M, 2016)

2.3.2 Phases of Gait

The stance phase of gait consists of five events:

1. **Initial contact (heel strike):** This is the moment when the heel of one of the lower limbs contacts the ground and corresponds to 0% of the gait cycle.
2. **Loading response:** This is the moment when the entire foot touches the ground and corresponds to 8% of the gait cycle.
3. **Midstance:** It has three definitions. In the first, the body weight passes directly over the supporting lower extremity; the second, is the instant when the foot of the limb in the swing phase passes the supporting limb, so the feet are side by side; and in the third, the greater trochanter of the femur is vertically aligned over the midpoint of the supporting foot in the sagittal plane. These three definitions correspond approximately to 30% of the gait cycle or 50% of the stance phase.
4. **Terminal stance (heel-off):** This is the moment when the heel lifts off or leaves the ground and corresponds to 30 to 40% of the gait cycle.
5. **Pre-swing (toe-off):** This is the moment when the toes lift off the ground and correspond to 60% of the gait cycle (Mansour NR, et al, 2019).

The swing phase of gait is divided into three stages:

1. **Initial swing:** The toes are lifted of the ground until mid-swing, corresponding to 60 to 75% of the gait cycle. At this moment, the foot is no longer in contact with the ground.
2. **Mid-swing:** The limb in the swing phase passes the supporting limb.
3. **Terminal swing:** The supporting limb prepares to contact the ground again. This phase ends when the foot contacts the ground, and the stance phase begins again. (Mansour NR, et al, 2019).

2.3.3-Gait Kinematics in the Sagittal Plane

Pelvis

Starting by the pelvis, it remains stable to transmit and transfer weight from one limb to another and maintain the acetabulum for hip movement.

- During initial contact, it stays in a neutral position and moves during midstance with a slight posterior tilt.
- At the end of midstance, the pelvis tilts slightly forward during hip extension. When the limb reaches pre-swing, it tilts posteriorly again.
- During swing, it first completes the posterior tilt and then tilts anteriorly from initial to mid-swing.
- In terminal swing, it moves towards a posterior tilt, preparing to land again.
- Anterior pelvic tilt accompanies hip extension as it hyperextends from midstance to the beginning of pre-swing (Dufour M. e Pilu M, 2016).

Hip

Passing to the hip, we can see larger amplitudes of motion:

- The hip moves about 40° in the sagittal plane.
- It is flexed between 25 and 30° during initial contact.
- During stance, it moves into approximately 10° of extension in the terminal stance.
- From initial contact to midstance, the trunk begins to move forward over the foot and continues moving forward to advance the foot shortly after midstance.
- Hip hyperextension during midstance is followed by extension of the lumbar spine and anterior pelvic tilt.
- When the hip reaches maximum extension in terminal stance, it begins flexion during pre-swing and prepares to lift the foot off the ground.
- As the feet enter the swing phase, the hip continues to increase flexion until midstance.
- Hip flexion decreases after midstance, remaining until terminal swing, where it moves towards extension in preparation for initial contact (Dufour M. e Pilu M, 2016).

Knee

The knee is close to full extension during initial contact and flexes in response to loading, with knee flexion used to absorb the shock of compression forces that occur when body weight impacts the ground and while helping with weight transfer as the body starts moving forward in single support.

- In midstance, it moves towards extension, reducing muscular effort during weight-bearing on the single limb.
- In terminal stance, it almost fully extends to assist the joints of the other limb in achieving the correct step length and advancing the limb for initial contact (Dufour M. e Pilu M, 2016).

Ankle and Foot

During the gait cycle, the ankle slightly dorsiflexes during ground contact.

- After the loading response, the tibia advances forward over the fixed foot to enter midstance. At the end of this phase, the ankle is dorsiflexed at approximately 10°.
- In terminal stance, when the heel leaves the ground, there is a second plantar flexion, which propels the limb into the swing phase (Dufour M e Pilu M, 2016).

Analysis of the stance phase during gait

As previously defined, the stance phase is the period when the foot is in contact with the ground and is traditionally divided into five subphases: initial contact, loading response, midstance, terminal stance (heel-off), and pre-swing (toe-off).

During initial contact, the foot contacts the ground. At this moment, the ankle joint is in a neutral position, between dorsiflexion and plantar flexion, with a slight knee flexion to absorb the impact. The hip joint is approximately flexed at 25°, and the trunk remains erect throughout the gait cycle. The dorsiflexor muscles of the foot are active eccentrically to position the ankle joint in a neutral position. The quadriceps femoris, which was in concentric contraction, now contracts eccentrically to minimize knee flexion. Hip flexor muscles become active, but extensor muscles start to contract, preventing excessive hip flexion. Erector spinae muscles are isometrically active and prevent trunk flexion caused by anterior rotation of the hip due to ground reaction force.

During the complete foot contact phase, the foot is fully in contact with the ground, and the heel strikes the floor. A plantar flexion of approximately 15° occurs at the ankle joint with eccentric contraction of the dorsiflexor muscles to avoid a forceful impact with the ground. At this moment, there is about 20° of knee flexion, which then extends, preparing the body for weight transfer.

The transfer of weight to the supporting lower limb continues, and the body's point of passing over the supporting limb is known as midstance. A slight dorsiflexion occurs at the ankle, but dorsiflexor muscles become inactive. Plantar flexor muscles start to contract to control the speed of the leg movement over the ankle. The hip and knee continue extending, and the upper limbs extend bilaterally, remaining almost parallel to the body, while the trunk remains in a neutral position.

Following midstance, there is heel-off, where the heel leaves the ground, accompanied by slight dorsiflexion (approximately 15°) and the beginning of plantar flexion. This marks the start of the propulsion phase, where plantar flexor muscles actively push the body forward. During this stage, the knee extends, and the hip hyperextends. The lower limbs position behind the foot, the trunk begins to rotate to the same side, and the upper limbs swing forward with shoulder flexion.

The end of the propulsion phase is toe-off, where the toes leave the ground. At this point, the toes are in external hyperextension at the metatarsophalangeal joints, with

approximately 10° of plantar flexion, and there is knee and hip flexion, with the hip perpendicular to the ground (Dufour M e Pilu M, 2016).

Analysis of the swing phase during gait

Scientific literature indicates that the swing phase has three moments: initial swing (acceleration), mid-swing, and terminal swing (deceleration), during which the limbs are not weight-bearing.

The initial swing is the acceleration phase when the lower limbs are behind the body and move forward to catch up. There is dorsiflexion of the foot, and the knee and hip continue to flex, propelling the lower limb forward. The initial swing phase is the period between the end of toe-off (toes leaving the ground) and the end of acceleration.

During mid-swing, the dorsiflexor muscles of the foot reposition the ankle joint to a neutral position, with the knee flexed to its maximum (approximately 65°) and the hip flexed (around 25°). These joint movements raise the lower limb, allowing the foot to clear the ground during this phase. Further hip flexion moves the lower limb forward in front of the body, positioning the leg vertically. The mid-swing phase is considered the time between the end of acceleration and the beginning of deceleration.

In the deceleration phase, the dorsiflexor muscles of the foot actively condition the ankle joint to a neutral position in preparation for heel strike. At this moment, there is knee extension, and the hamstring muscles contract eccentrically to slow down the lower limb and prevent abrupt extension. The lower limb reaches its maximum forward swing point, and the knee remains flexed. The terminal swing phase is the period between the end of mid-swing and the end of deceleration (Dufour M. e Pilu M, 2016).

But how does the body control this complex orchestra? That's where the muscular activation patterns and synergies become relevant.

Muscular activities

The complicated interplay of lower-limb muscles during walking can be simplified, revealing important phases and muscle activities.

Beginning with **first contact**, muscles such as the gluteus maximus and biceps femoris influence hip flexion, whereas the tibialis anterior controls foot movement. In the succeeding double support phase, a group of seven primary muscles coordinates ankle, knee, and hip control, maintaining equilibrium and allowing forward movement. Notably, the rectus femoris regulates knee flexion and absorbs loading shock, with help from the gluteus maximus and hamstring. Meanwhile, the gluteus medius supports the pelvis (Figure 2).

As the **stance phase** closes, the tibialis anterior prepares for the upcoming swing phase. In the **first swing**, hip flexor muscles (adductor longus, sartorius, iliacus, and gracilis) move the thigh forward, causing knee flexion. The biceps femoris increases knee flexion, while the tibialis anterior and extensor digitorum longus raise the foot in preparation for clearance.

Muscle activity decreases during the **mid-swing phase**, with the tibialis anterior maintaining ankle posture and the contralateral gluteus medius providing pelvic stability. The **terminal swing** signals the completion of the cycle, preparing for the next stance phase. Meanwhile the hamstring muscles slow leg movement, the rectus femoris stretches the knee, and the tibialis anterior prepares the ankle for ground contact (Figure 3).

	Stance phase					Swing phase		
	Double support	Simple support			Double support			
		Initial	Middle	Terminal		Initial	Middle	Ter.
ILIACUS						█		
SARTORIUS						█		
GRACILIS	█					█		
RECTUS FEMORIS	█				█			█
ADDUCTOR LONGUS			█					
VASTI	█	█						
GLUTEUS MAXIMUS	█							█
GLUTEUS MEDIUS	█	█						█
BICEPS FEMORIS	█					█		█
TIBIALIS ANTERIOR	█					█	█	█
EXTENSOR DIGITROUM LONGUS	█				█	█	█	█
GASTROCNEMIUS		█	█					
SOLEUS		█	█					
FLEXOR HALLUCIS LONGUS			█					
TIBIALIS POSTERIOR		█	█					
PERONEUS LONGUS			█					

Figure 3- Simplified representation of the muscular activity during the gait cycle. Source Bonnefoy-Mazure, A. & Armand, Stéphane. (2015). Normal gait.

Terrestrial gait, being the one that humans evolved over the millennia to preform, is a controlled forward imbalance, skillfully maintained, resulting in minimal muscular activity and low energy expenditure. However, during accelerations, decelerations, uphill or downhill walking, the muscular activity increases significantly. Overall, the muscular activity is mainly eccentric (braking) with little variation in joint range of motion. Any deviation from the "normal" gait inevitably leads to compensatory energy expenditure (Kadaba et al, 1989) (figure 2). This implies that a major modification such as adding inclination in already substantially different environments like the Moon and Mars, will most likely lead to great shifts in the overall gate.

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

Figure 4- Mean and Standard Deviation of EMG (nine cycles over 3 days): multiple correlation coefficients & coefficients of variation within a day (w) and between days (b) are also shown. Source: Kadaba et al, 1989.

3. Methods

3.1- Participants

The sample of this investigation included 13 healthy subjects, aged between 18 and 35 years, height between 1.55m and 1.80m (these are, respectively, the minimum and maximum levels recommended for the calibration of the AlterG machine, due to the height of the anterior superior iliac crests) and body mass index inferior to 30 kg/m². Subjects with history of any type of muscle injury or musculoskeletal pathology of the lower limbs were excluded. Subjects with unstable fractures, deep venous thrombosis or hypotension could not participate. Also, subjects with cardiovascular alterations were excluded.

The sample was drawn from the student populations of the Faculties of Human Kinetics and Medicine using a convenience sampling method. Everyone's willingness to engage in the study determined their inclusion.

Prior to their participation, participants were given a complete description of the research endeavor, including detailed explanations of their obligations, rights, and study protocols. This precaution was taken to assure that no participant would experience nausea during the trial. The Ethics Committee for Research at the Faculty of Human Kinetics approved the research protocol (Ethics Approval Number: *Decision* CEIFMH No:3/2023).

All participants were requested to complete two crucial documents: an informed consent form (see Attachment 1) and a Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire for Everyone (PAR-Q+ - see Attachment 2). Any affirmative replies on the PAR-Q+ were deemed exclusion criteria. In addition, all individuals completed the Motion Sickness Susceptibility Questionnaire Short-form (MSSQ-Short, see Attachment 3), which had been translated into Portuguese. The MSSQ was considered an important step of the process as it

To assess the effect of the different hypogravity environments in gait kinematics and EMG variables, the sample size was estimated by a power analysis calculated with the same software, by setting the effect size as 0.4, α -level of 0.05 and power of 0.9, and it was shown that 13 participants were required. Assuming the possibility of dropouts due to the need of 3 assessment sessions, 16 participants were recruited.

3.1.2- Questionnaires

Participants were required to complete three main questionnaires: an **Informed Consent** form, a **PAR-Q+** (Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire), and the **MSSQ** (Motion Sickness Susceptibility Questionnaire). The informed consent form detailed every aspect of the study and participant involvement. The PAR-Q+ ensured that all subjects were medically cleared to participate in physical activities without any health

concerns. The MSSQ was crucial for assessing each individual's susceptibility to motion sickness.

The absence of gravity in space and the reduced tactile sensations that guide the vestibular system often lead to motion sickness during the first few days. The simulated hypogravity, combined with the use of a VR headset, provides an immersive experience of walking on the Moon and Mars. However, this, along with the lack of movement in the sagittal plane, could induce dizziness in individuals predisposed to such conditions.

By using the MSSQ, the team could identify which subjects were at risk of motion sickness and include only those participants with low susceptibility, ensuring the integrity and safety of the study.

3.2- Procedures

3.2.1- *Experimental Protocol*

The data collection was performed at High Performance Center (*CAR Jamor*). Participants visited CAR Jamor 2 times. The first visit was the familiarization with the equipment and procedures, anthropometric measurements (Table 2- Anatomy/ RPE that can be found in the results), and questionnaires fill. The second visit was the gait test session and the third visit was equal to the second (retest data collection). Due to time limitations, not every participant completed the 2 gait sessions. That's the main reason for not including the test-retest results in this thesis.

At participant's arrival in session 1, instructions were given about the protocol, the risks, and benefits, as well as the Informed Consent. The participant read and could ask questions to the team before signing it. The participation in the project is voluntary and the participant may quit the study at any time. During each session, beside the participant, only the researchers were allowed to be present at the laboratory.

Session 1 (Familiarization): in this session, the following anthropometric measurements were assessed: mass, height, fat mass %, thigh and waist girths, foot, shank, and thigh lengths. The participants were asked to fulfill the Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire (PAR-Q) (Attachment 2) as well as the Motion sickness short questionnaire (MSSQ- short) (Attachment 3). This latter one was submitted to process of Cultural and Linguistic Adaptation for the European Portuguese language in order to be included in this project.

Afterwards, the participants experimented the Alter-G equipment, walking with different levels of hypogravity. They were asked to report how they felt in all the different conditions.

Session 2 (Gait Test session): in this session, the participants performed the gait test in different conditions. The sequence was the following E-Mo-Ma-E, where E is Earth, Ma is Mars and Mo is Moon gravities, respectively. Each gravity condition

was applied during minutes in a consecutive way. The velocity of the gait was established at 3.2km/h during the entire protocol. It was considered a comfortable velocity based on the subjects' lower limb length expected in the sample, that prevents walk to run transition according to previous research done around the Froude number (Ackermann, et al, (2012); De Witt, J et al, 2014). The slope of the treadmill was increased 4% for each gravity condition, for 1 minute, in order to simulate ground inclinations that can be found on the celestial bodies. Gait data was recorded in every situation for at least 30 seconds.

The protocol began with a habituation phase, where the participants walk at 1G and 3.2km/hr without any inclination for the first 2 minutes, then we record 30 sec. (2min-2:30min). After the recording, we increase to 4% inclination, allow the participants to adjust to it, recording once again from 3 min, to 3:30 min, the inclination is then reduced, and we change the bodyweight percentage to either Lunar, or Martian gravity's, repeating the protocol in the other gravities. The recordings were set to the following times:

- 1G, no inclination- 2 to 2:30
- 1G inclined- 3min to 3:30
- BW% Change- 3:30- 4
- 0.38G no inclination- 5 to 5:30
- 0.38G inclined- 6 to 6:30
- BW% Change- 6:30- 7
- 0.20G no inclination- 8 to 8:30
- 0.20G inclined- 9 to 9:30
- Gradual BW% Change back to earth- 9:30- 10.30
- 1G no inclination- 11:30 to 12
- 1G inclined- 12.30 to 13.
- Still walking gradually reduce speed and inclination to 0.

3.2.2- Alter-G acquisition

For the AlterG treadmill (AlterG VIA, AlterG Inc., Fremont, CA, US) acquisition, the participants must wear lycra shorts (5 sizes are available (XS, S, M, L, XL) to fit the equipment. The correct size was defined according with the thigh girth. The participants stepped over the treadmill, whose supports was at the height of the anterior superior iliac crest, tightening the zipper and allowing the cockpit to be sealed and later inflated. The calibration process was performed through the inflating of the cockpit until the maximum of each subject is reached (according to its weight). Afterwards, the gait test started, as mentioned in the experimental protocol.

3.2.5- 3D Kinematics acquisition

The 3D kinematic data was captured at 120 Hz with 7 IMU sensors (XSens MVN Technologies, Enschede, NL) (Gandy et al., 2014), using the MVN Analyze software, and a biomechanical model of the human body (Roetenberg, D. et al., 2009). The placement of the sensors in each segment intends to be over the bones whenever possible to reduce soft tissue artefacts (Leardini et al., 2005). Calibration procedures were performed to align the sensors with the body alignment and to determine the segment's length (*MVN User Manual*, 2012).

Xsens composition

The motion trackers, MTx, and MTx-STR are miniature inertial measurement units containing 3D linear accelerometers, 3D rate gyroscopes, 3D magnetometers, and a barometer, which measures atmospheric pressure. The MTx tracker will be positioned on the pelvis. The MTx-STR's are used to chain both legs (upper leg, lower leg, and feet).

The strings of MTx's are interconnected by the Body Pack, which delivers power from the battery pack to the connected MTx's and retrieves their data ensuring exactly synchronized samples. These are the portable parts that the subject is carrying during the experiment.

In order to receive the data, there's an Access Point connected to the computer via ethernet cable.

Xsens Body Sensors Setup

Each motion tracker was attached to a Velcro strap located at the respective analysis point. As previously stated, the MTx tracker was placed in the pelvis, centered, and vertical to the floor using the "XSens" letters as reference. The sensors of the upper leg, labeled "Uleg" were positioned in the middle of the lateral thighs to avoid a great amount of adipose tissue. As for the sensors of the lower leg, labeled "Lleg" was placed in the lateral side of the lower leg aligned vertically with the fibula, 6cm above the lateral malleolus. (Figure 5 & 6)

Regarding the feet, the shoelaces served as the fixator for the sensor, which was placed in front upper part of the foot.

Table 1- XSENS Sensor Setup

Xsens Software Setup

The MVN system is controlled by a software application called MVN Analyze/Animate, which can be used for real-time viewing and recording. Off-line playback, analysis and editing of previously recorded sessions are also possible.

Within this software we have used a single level scenario to analyze positional changes regarding the environment, which is recommended for a smooth surface, with no differences in height.

Prior to any data collection, the subject's lower limbs were measured to increase accuracy of the calibration, and perform the recommended n-pose, following the required steps for a good quality calibration.

Collected Data

The Xsens system allows us to collect kinematic data using inertial measurement units (IMUs) containing a combination of gyroscope, magnetometer, and accelerometer, to measure rotational rates. This system also uses 3D GPS positional aiding and provides us with a real time 3D avatar.

There are some big advantages such as the wireless capabilities, the full magnetic immunity and the pressure resistance that will allow us to use the Xsens system in combination with the increased pressure of the AlterG treadmill.

Anthropometry

The anthropometric characteristics of each participant are relevant to encounter potential explanations for the differences found between subjects when the unloading happens. For example, higher BMI's might correlate with higher RPE, a smaller **Trunk-cephalic length** for people with similar heights and body weights, guarantees that a higher percentage of the body weight and length are within the AlterG capsule which can lead to higher stability. Table 2 provides a snapshot of the anatomical diversity within this healthy young population, averaging 23.6 years in age. Measurements were taken using various tools: height was assessed using a stadiometer, circumferences and specific lengths were measured with a metric tape, and body composition was analyzed through Bioelectrical Impedance Vector Analysis (BIVA). The study encompassed 13 participants, consisting of 4 males and 9 females. Their body fat percentages ranged from 6% to 33%, heights varied between 182 cm and 157 cm, and participants had different activity levels and distinctive body weight distributions.

Table 2- Subject anthropometric characteristics

Subject	Age	Gender	Body mass (kg)	Height (cm)	Foot Length (cm)	Ankle Height (cm)	Lateral condyle height (cm)	Femoral Condyle height (cm)	Thigh perimeter (cm)	Waist width (cm)	Pelvis Width (cm)	Pelvis Length (cm)	Body Fat %	Trunk-cephalic length (cm)
001	32	M	75.7	179	25.8	8	51	95	63.2	80	104.5	36	11.6	92
003	24	M	90.5	182	27.1	8.4	46	93	67	88	109.3	38	12.2	93
005	26	F	61	162.5	23.5	6.3	38.1	88	59.8	70.4	95.6	30	16.3	87.9
006	22	F	59	157	23	6	35.9	86.1	62.1	69.6	101.2	32	18.2	82
007	27	M	69	171	26.5	7	44.3	92.3	56.8	80.2	96	35.3	7	86.2
012	25	F	72	159	24.5	6.5	39	82.1	70.5	82.2	112	32	32	84
013	22	F	66	164	24.7	6.8	42	89	63	75	102	32	33	86.8
014	20	F	51	159.3	23.2	6.1	39.2	90.5	52.2	68.9	92	28	24	81
015	21	F	53.5	164.8	23	6	39	83	57.5	68.5	96.2	29	19.4	89
016	23	F	54	168.5	24	6	43	94	58.8	71	93.7	29	20	91
017	21	F	65	170.5	25	7.5	41	92	65	72	106	31	27	92
019	25	F	59.7	173	24	7.4	43.5	89	56.3	72.8	96	30.5	16.1	88
20	23	M	72	175	25.8	7.9	50	94	64	76	104	36	9	82

3.3- Data Analysis and Processing

We intended to assess the acute modifications that occur at the lower limb joint kinematics and neuromuscular function during the different hypogravity conditions. The gait spatio-temporal parameters (speed, cadence, total cycle time, duration of the

support and swing phases, stride length, step length) as well as the 3D kinematic variables (ankle, knee and hip joint angular displacements, velocities, and accelerations) were collected with XSens software (XSens MVN Technologies, Enschede, NL), version 2.9- build 1697, operating at a frequency rate of 120 Hz. A 3D kinematic model with 7 segments (pelvis, thighs, shanks, and feet) was used in Visual 3D software (Visual 3D™ Professional v5.01.18.C_Motion, Inc) to calculate and analyze the kinematic data. Data was normalized to 100% of the gait cycle.

3.4- Statistical Analysis

The normality of the data for all variables was verified using the Shapiro-Wilk test. To compare the kinematic between the control (earth gravity 1-g) and the 7 experimental conditions (4% inclined Earth, 0.18-g, 0.36-g with and without inclination, plus the return to Earth) during the gait cycle, a non-parametric test called Friedman's Two-Way Analysis of Variance by Ranks was used.

All the statistical tests were conducted using SPSS (version 20.0; IBM, Chicago, IL) and a level of $p < .05$ was considered significant.

To prepare SPSS dataset, an excel table was created with Kinematic (max and minimal values of Flexion/Extension, abduction/adduction, rotation, and total ROM for each one), and spatio-temporal variables [Step length, Stride width, cycle time R (R stands for Right), step time R, Stance time R, swing time R, STEPS PM R (PM stands for Per Minute), STRIDES PM]. The data table was divided into subjects, joints (ankle, knee, hip), and environments (E/E4%-Mo/Mo4%- Ma/Ma4%- return to E).

4 Results

Illustrated on the 3rd table are the Ratings of Perceived Exertion (RPE) assigned by each participant to different gravity conditions. Notably, the participants rated the 62% body weight reduction on Mars as the easiest, with an average RPE of 2.3. The Moon, with an 80% reduction in body weight, closely followed with an average RPE of 2.7. In contrast, the condition mimicking Earth's full body weight garnered an average RPE of 4.2. EReturn (Earth Retrun) was the hardest with an average RPE of 5,3, due to 4 of the subjects increasing the RPE by 1 point, and subject GH_JAMOR_012 increasing it by 2 points. These 5 people pointed out that they felt heavier after the unloading and that they weren't aware of how much they weighted (table 3).

Table 3- Subject RPE

Subject	RPE (Rate of Perceive Exertion)			
	Moon	Mars	Earth	EReturn
GH_JAMOR_001	1	2	3	4
GH_JAMOR_003	2	2	3	3
GH_JAMOR_005	4	3	5	6
GH_JAMOR_006	3	2	5	6
GH_JAMOR_007	2	3	4	4
GH_JAMOR_012	4	3	6	8
GH_JAMOR_013	2	2	4	4
GH_JAMOR_014	3	3	5	5
GH_JAMOR_015	2	3	4	5
GH_JAMOR_016	3	3	4	4
GH_JAMOR_017	3	3	5	5
GH_JAMOR_019	1	2	3	3
GH_JAMOR_20	1	2	3	3

The variance between the Moon and Mars ratings can be attributed to the degree of perceived instability and the transition to more comfortable locomotion patterns. It is worth mentioning that only the three subjects accustomed to higher instability

environments and weightlifting considered the Moon to be easier than Mars. This highlights the increased need for a structured training regimen to develop an efficient gait on the Moon, underscoring the importance of preparation for lunar missions. This dataset holds considerable significance as it provides an opportunity to scrutinize disparities among different environments and to establish correlations between the RPE and the kinematical variables analyzed below.

Kinematics

Utilizing the statistical analysis software SPSS, the Shapiro-Wilk test indicated that the data under examination did not conform to the normal distribution. As a result, the non-parametric test had to be used for the analysis of two or more linked samples as the premise of normalcy was not accepted. More specifically, differences between variables within each environmental condition were investigated using Friedman's Two-Way Analysis of Variance by Ranks. This analytical strategy was selected to account for the data's non-normal distribution and provide a thorough evaluation of any discrepancies between the variables under study in each unique setting.

The **Shapiro-Wilk** test was used to assess the distribution of variables in various scenarios. A significant threshold of $p < 0.05$ was established, and the variables with a $p < 0.05$ were marked in orange. **Descriptive statistics** were also preformed, and both tables can be found in the attachments (Attachment 4, table 42 & 45).

To provide a clear understanding of all the variables and the respective differences between environments, each of the variables with statistically meaningful shifts has a graph. The color scheme makes it easier to read each column with dark green given to E1 (Normal Earth), light green to E2 (Earth Inclined), dark grey to Mo1 (Normal Moon), light grey to Mo2 (Moon Inclined), red to Ma1 (Normal Mars), orange to Ma2 (Mars Inclined), and military green to ER1 (Normal Earth Return) (Figure 6).

Figure 7- Environment colors

While this study did not employ statistical tests to assess inter-subject differences, as it is not the primary focus of this thesis, multi-person graphs were also generated to enhance the robustness of the pairwise comparisons. These graphs were designed to decompose the comparisons, aiding in the reader's comprehension, and providing additional visual support for the presented results.

One of the objectives of the study is to find potential differences in the gait kinematics between the 7 test conditions. To do this, a multiple comparison test needs to

be done. As there are several tests with abnormal distributions the non-parametric test **Related-Samples Friedman's Two-Way Analysis of Variance by Ranks**” was the statistical method used. For the test, a significance threshold (α) of 0.050 was selected. The variables that stay below this threshold are then submitted to a **Pairwise Comparisons Test**.

Such is the case for **Step Time** (Figure 7) that has a $t=0.849$ and a $p=0,028$ in the Shapiro-Wilk test. Using the Pairwise Comparisons test, the environment Mo1 appears to be consistently different regardless of the variable, in **Step time**, Mo1 had differences with ER1 ($t=2.923$; $p=0.012$) and E1 ($t=-2.577$; $p=0.049$), with the Mo1 having a slower cadency with each step taking 0.635seconds, while ER1 has 0.585, and E1 0.587, a difference of 8.5%. It’s also noticeable that Mars appears to be right in the middle of Mo1 and E1/ER1, showing no statistically significant shift after the p-value correction.

Figure 8- Step Time Pairwise Comparisons

In the subject comparison, it’s possible to confirm the tendency for higher values on the Moon and lower on Earth across all subjects. It’s worth noting that certain subjects as 1, 2, 7, 11, and 13 have a higher variability between environments, with Earth staying more consistent across the board (Figure 9).

Figure 9- STEP TIME per person

Step length has no differences after the statistical analysis. The null hypothesis cannot be rejected due to inadequate evidence, as indicated by the p-value of 0.134, which is higher than the significance level of 0.050.

The variable **stride width** was erased from the table, as the values cannot be trusted, but can be found in the long version of this table in the attachments.

Cycle time only had the variable Mo1 with differences, revealing sig of 0.031 and a test statistic of 0.853. **Stance Time** also has no differences in the normalcy test ($t=11.090$; $p=0.86$).

Another variable, **Swing Time** (Figure 10), also shows big differences in the Friedman Test, with similar outcomes to Step Time, revealing changes between ER1 & Mo1 ($t=3.385$; $p=0.001$), E1 & Mo1 ($t=-3.154$; $p=0.004$), E2 & Mo1 ($t=2.731$; $p=0.027$). As the graph bellow demonstrates, Mo1 has a longer Swing time of 0.509 seconds, with differences of 15.9% to E1 (0.439) and ER1 (0.438), and of 14.4% to E2. Once again, Ma stays in the middle between the E and Mo.

Figure 10- SWING TIME Pairwise Comparisons

When looking into an individual basis, once again, there's higher variability in low hipogravity conditions within some subjects but in the great majority of cases, Mo stands out as having the longest Swing Time (Figure 10).

Figure 11-Swing Time per person

One important indicator for measuring the intensity and tempo of walking is **STEPS PM** (Figure 11). This variable only shows major differences between Mo1 & ER1 ($t=-3.269$; $p=0.002$), with ER1 being the biggest values (104.093spm) followed closely by the other Earth variants. This time ER1 has an 8% difference to Mo1 (96.284), and Ma stands in the middle as usual.

ER1 leads with 104.09, while E1 and E2 show mean STEPS PM of 103.16 and 101.41, respectively. Mo1 is particularly noteworthy since it has a lower mean STEPS PM of 96.28, indicating a unique walking pattern. With a mean STEPS PM of 98.35, Mo2 comes next, highlighting even more distinctive pacing characteristics. Ma conditions are in the center, as predicted; Ma1 displays 99.54 spm (STEPS PM), whereas Ma2 displays 99.11 spm. These results highlight the impact of walking environment on walking speed, with gravitational fluctuations causing to subtle variations in STEPS PM under various environmental situations.

Figure 12- STEPS PM Pairwise Comparisons

As usual, there's a high inter-individual variability. Only one person subject 7 appears to be more inconsistent having bigger peaks between environments, possibly due to having a harder time adapting to environmental changes (Figure 12).

Figure 13- STEPS PM per person

The variable **Strides PM** reflects the same as Steps PM, accounting for the full cycle instead of a single step. In this case however, no variable shows any p value that requires the Friedman test ($t=12.000$; $p=0.062$).

Joint Kinematics

Applying the same procedure as for the spatio-temporal variables, the study delves into the complexities of **Joint Kinematics**, with a focus on joint Range of Motion (ROM) across three dimensions – X, Y, and Z – and under seven different test conditions. We scrutinized the hip (the variables with the letter H), knee (the variables with the letter K), and ankle (the variables with the letter A) joints, assessing total ROM, flexion/extension (Y dimension) ROM, abduction/adduction (X dimension) ROM, and internal/external rotation (Z dimension) ROM. Specific attention was given to peak values during supination, pronation, extension, flexion, abduction, and adduction. Notably, the knee joint received additional scrutiny, with the flexion peak divided into 1st and 2nd flexion.

The Shapiro Wilk test as well as the descriptive statistics, can be found in attachment 4 (tables 54 & 55) due to the sheer size of both tables.

The normality test showed that several variables don't have normal distributions. As such, the **Friedman's Two-Way Analysis of Variance by Ranks** was conducted for each variable to scrutinize potential differences among multiple related groups. In total, 28 variables were studied, and from those 13 have shown significant differences (Hip adduction peak; Knee extension peak; Knee 2nd flexion peak; Knee adduction peak; Knee ROM in the Sagittal Plane; Ankle int rotation peak; Ankle Plantar Flexion peak; Ankle dorsiflexion peak; Ankle pronation peak; Ankle supination peak). To enhance

readability and ensure focus on the most pertinent aspects, this chapter exclusively presents 13 statistically significant variables. The chapter is further divided by joints, with the **Ankle** coming first, followed by the **Knee** in second, finishing with the **Hip**.

Ankle

The first variable showing significant changes on the ankle joint is **Ankle supination peak** (Figure 14), with substantial differences in one environmental comparison between ER1 & Mo1 ($t=3$; $p=0.008$), in this case the Mo1 has the biggest value, with 24.583° , against 18.729° from ER1, representing a 5.854° asymmetry (31% difference).

Figure 14- Ankle supination peak Pairwise Comparisons

Once again, subjects on the Mo reveal higher degrees of supination, except for subjects 5 and 8. The Moon also shows a high inter-individual variation (Figure 15).

Figure 15- Ankle supination peak per subject

In the variable **Ankle pronation peak** (Figure 16), several cases maintain the significant differences even when the p-value is adjusted with Bonferroni correction:

Mo1 (0.055°) is different from any of the E variants, where ER1 has the highest pronation values with 4.692° ($t=2.923$; $p=0.012$), followed by E1 with 4.356° ($t=-2.885$; $p=0.014$), and by E2 with 4.272° ($t=-3.346$; $p=0.002$). The latter, E2, also shows major differences against Mo2 that has 0.143° ($t=-2.885$; $p=0.014$), and Ma1 with 0.304° ($t=-2.808$; $p=0.019$).

Figure 16-Ankle Pronation peak Pairwise Comparisons

Curious to see that some people don't have any ankle pronation in any of the environments which leads to a high variation between subjects, especially in subjects 6 and 8, that contribute to the low Lunar and Martian averages (Figure 17).

Figure 17- Ankle Pronation peak per subject

In a similar manner, **Ankle dorsiflexion peak** (Figure 18), has several big asymmetries: Ma2A vs #E2A ($p=.019$); Ma2A vs ER1A ($p=0.004$); Ma1A-max y vs E2A ($p=.036$); Ma1A vs ER1A ($p=.008$), and Mo2A vs ER1A ($p=.031$).

Ma2 does 14.855° of dorsiflexion while E2 does 18.051° a 17.8% shift. Ma 2 also shows a big gap of 21.6% to ER1 that has a dorsiflexion angle of 18.704° . Ma1(13.975°) has the same statistically significant differences with E2 and ER1, in this case the differences are 31.4% & 25.3% respectively. Another point of divergence is found between Mo2 (14.213°) and ER1, with the dorsiflexion peak on Earth Return being 24% higher than on the inclined Moon.

Figure 18- dorsiflexion peak Pairwise Comparisons

In the graph below (Figure 19), we can see that, contrarily to the usual trend, values on Earth seem to oscillate more than in the other environments, with the biggest difference being found between subjects 4 & 10. Another curious distinction in this variable, is that some people seem to deviate a lot between E1 and ER1, with the latter being in higher in several instances.

Figure 19- dorsiflexion peak per subject

Ankle Plantar Flexion peak (Figure 20) only has differences between Mo2 and ER1 ($t=-2.731$; $p=0.027$) with the Mo (20.077° , $\text{sig}=2.536$, $\text{amp}=29.040^\circ$) doing 26.8% more plantar flexion than ER1 (14.694° , $\text{sig}=2.168$, $\text{amp}=20.209^\circ$). Mars has no statistically relevant shift with any environment despite of its magnified values with Ma1 one reaching an average of 19.574° .

Figure 20- Plantar Flexion peak Pairwise Comparisons

As expected, most of the test subjects have higher plantar flexion values on the Mo, followed by Ma, with the exception of subjects 3, 4 & 6, where Ma is significantly higher, and subject 13 that has a bigger peak on E1 (Figure 21).

Figure 21- plantar flexion peak per subject

Still on the ankle, **Ankle int rotation peak** (Figure 22), the Pairwise comparisons show several big differences: #E1A vs #Mo1A (sig. 0,019); #E1A vs #Mo2A (sig. 0,010); #ER1A vs #Mo1A (sig. 0,049); #ER1A vs #Mo2A (sig. 0,027); #E2A vs #Mo2A (sig. 0,043).

This means that the minimal values of internal rotation between the Mo and the E are very different, with the E having lower avg (average), and lower amplitudes. E1 at

5.902° appears to be different from Mo1 with 2.860° of internal rotation, by 206,4%, and from Mo2 which has 2.406°, an even larger gap of 245.3%. ER1 (5.076°) also contrasts with Mo1 by 177%, and Mo2 by 210.9%. The last major difference comes from E2 with has the biggest peak with 6.503°, almost the triple (270%) of Mo2.

Figure 22- Ankle int rotation peak Pairwise Comparisons

In the inter-individual view, a high irregularity appears, with some subjects (3, 8, 10 & 11) doing almost no internal rotation in many of the environments. Besides that, subject 7 although consistent in the pattern, reveals a high internal rotation across all conditions and has a big shift between E1 and ER1. This subject was also the one that told us that it found it much easier to walk on E1 than on ER1 after experiencing lower weight bearing conditions (Figure 23).

Figure 23- Ankle int rotation peak per subject

Knee

Shifting our attention to the **knee**, the 1st variable with significant different comparisons is **Knee ROM in the Sagittal Plane** (Figure 24), where Mo2 (55.202°; Amp=15.474) diverges from E2 (65.588°; amp=24.313°), ER1 (65.986°; amp=27.427°) and E1 (67.235°; amp=25,679°), in this cases the difference is 18.8%, 19% and 21.7% respectively;

Mo1 (56.202°; amp= 27,992°) has the same shift with E2, ER1, and E1 with differences of 16.7%, 17% and 19.7%.

Ma1 (57.957°; amp= 21.985°) is also different from ER1, and E1, being 13.9% smaller than ER1 and 16% than E1.

Ma2 (58.788°; amp= 24.045°) shows the same differences but with smaller magnitudes diverging by 7,189° (12.2%) from ER1 and 8.447° (14.4%) from E1.

Figure 24- Knee ROM in the Sagittal Plane Pairwise Comparisons

Across all subjects, E has higher **Knee ROM in the Sagittal Plane**, which might indicate a higher necessity of using the knee extensor muscles to walk on E in comparison to the Moon and Mars (Figure 25).

Figure 25- Knee ROM in the Sagittal Plane per subject

Knee abduction peak (Figure 25) also reveals a sig of 0.003, with a test statistic of 19,634. In this variable however, only Mo1 (6.534°) shows to be different from E1 at 4.405° of abduction, 32.6% lower than Mo1, and ER1 that has the lowest value of all with 4.219°, being 35.6% lower than Mo1. This data indicates a higher propensity to Knee Varus on the Moon comparing to the Earth.

Figure 26- Knee abduction peak Pairwise Comparisons

Despite of the high magnitude of changes between individuals, E as the lowest values of all, followed by Mars in the vicinity of the Moon. E2 has an outlier value, which is probably due to a minor adjustment made by the person while walking, if not for that as it has similar values to E1, would probably reveal statistically significant differences in comparison to Mo1 (Figure 26).

Figure 27- Knee abduction peak per subject

Regarding **Knee adduction peak** (Figure 28), one can see significant asymmetries between comparisons, with ER1 (12.086°) being bigger than Ma2 (9.486°) by 21.5%, and Mo2 that has the lowest abduction value of 9.317°, a 23% shift. Contrasting to the prior variable, the Knee reaches higher adduction values on Earth than on the Mo and Ma, revealing a similar range of motion on the X axis abut with different emphasis.

Figure 28- Knee adduction peak Pairwise Comparisons

While E1 tends to be larger on average than ER1, there is no statistically significant difference from Ma2 or Mo2. This observation is likely influenced by considerable variability between subjects, with ER1 exhibiting the highest values in individuals different from those where Mo2 and Ma2 display elevated values (Figure 29).

Figure 29- Knee adduction peak per subject

Out of all the studied variables, the one with the most significant differences is **Knee 2nd flexion peak** (Figure 30), with 11 comparisons. Mo2 has the lowest flexion angle with 55.446° , revealing dissimilarities of 14.8%, 18.2.% & 14.5% respectively, with E2 (65.105°), E1 (67.762°) & ER1 (64.936°).

Mo1 (56.317°) stands on a similar ground, with shifts of 13.5% to E2, 14.4% to E1 & 13.3% to ER1. Mars is on the middle as usual, with Ma1 having a flexion degree 58.369° , 10.3% lower than E2, 11.2% lower than E1, and 11.1% smaller than ER1. Ma2 (59.084°) flees from the tendency, revealing major differences only with 2 variables from the Earth, E1, and ER1, at 10.2% and 9.9%, respectively. In this case, the lower the weight experienced, the lower the peak.

Figure 30- Knee 2nd flexion peak Pairwise Comparisons

Despite the fact that this variable is the one with the most differences between environments, these differences are more consistent inter-individuals, with the exception of subject 4, everyone has a higher 2nd flexion peak on Earth, dropping it on the Moon, followed by a slight increase on Mars, and a full return on ER1. Exceptionally, individual 4 gets lower with each environment, ER1 being the lowest of them all (Figure 31).

Figure 31- Knee 2nd flexion peak per subject

Contrarily to the former the variable **Knee extension peak** (Figure 32) only has significant differences in one variable #E1K-# Mo1K, with E1 showing a avg (average) of -1.473° , amp (amplitude)= 8.44° ; and Mo1 an avg equal to 0.115° , and a amp of 10.05° , meaning that the Moon has higher values and a bigger amplitude than the E1 [E1 (-1.473°) vs Mo1 (0.115°)]. Curiously, Ma1 has the highest knee extension peak, followed by Ma2, although none has statistically meaningful difference with any other condition due to a high subject variability.

Figure 32- Knee extension peak Pairwise Comparisons

In this case, both high inter-subject and intra-subject variability are present with individuals such as 4 and 10 revealing big knee extension ability with subject 4 going as high as 11.55° of extension, other people go through all the environments without crossing 0° on the knee joint, and there are some such as subject 6 and 8 who are able to have big knee extensions on E1 and shift completely to the other situations (Figure 33).

Figure 33- Knee extension peak per subject

Hip

The first Hip variable with significant asymmetries is **Hip adduction peak** (Figure 34), revealing 4 differences. Ma2 (2.701°) only has 48% from E1 (5.617°) hip adduction,

and 46.5% of ER1. Mo2 (2.568°) also reveals differences within the same comparisons, at only 45.7% of E1 & 44.2% of ER1. This data, indicates that on Earth people will on average have higher peaks of Adduction of the hip, meaning that wider Ranges of motion might be required to adjust the gait pattern, although abduction values are not statistically different.

Figure 34- Hip Adduction PEAK Pairwise Comparisons

Adduction peak also has a high variance between subjects, with individual 6 appearing an outlier with no adduction present in none of the environments. Once again there a high variability between subjects, with Mars being the environment with the biggest shifts (Figure 34).

Figure 35- Hip Adduction PEAK per subject

After adjusting the sig **Hip ROM in the Sagittal Plane** (Figure 36), only the Ma1H vs E2H held the significant differences, symbolizing that on the hip, the only difference was between normal Ma (avg=33.630°; amp=20.113°) and inclined E (avg=40.559°; amp=29.851°), a 6.93-degree difference which equates to a 17.1% difference, with E2 having a way higher ROM.

Curiously, although not having a statistically significant shift, Mo1 has the lowest mean values with 32.623° followed by Mo2. This is probably due to the high variability between test subjects on the Mo, with some subjects such as 3, 12 & 13 having low values, and others like person 1, 2, 8 and 10 reporting high values (Figure 37). The larger Hip Sagittal plane ROM on E2 is apparent in the next variable max y - flexion peak but can also be seen in every other variable regarding hip flexion/ extension range of motion although without the statistical significance. The same can be said for every other Earth condition.

Figure 36- Hip ROM in the Sagittal Plane Pairwise Comparisons

Figure 37- Hip ROM in the Sagittal Plane per subject

The last variable that has statistically significant differences is **max y - flexion peak** [(Figure 38). With the multiple comparisons, we were able to see that the variables Mo1 (21.089°), Mo2 (22.178°), Ma1 (20.862°) and Ma2 (22.125°), all diverge from the environment E2, which is the condition with the highest value of 30.869 degrees, representing 146.4% of Mo1, 139.2% of Mo2, 148% of Ma1, and finally 139.5% of Ma2.

Figure 38- Hip Flexion peak Pairwise Comparisons

Except for the individuals 1 and 11, everyone has the environment E2 as the highest flexion peak, with the subject 9 representing the epitome of that at 49,421°. It's also noticeable that tendentially the inclined versions of each environment have slightly bigger flexions degrees. Once again, the Moon and Mars are situations with larger inter-

individual shifts which might represent not only different adaptation capabilities, but also different strategies employed to deal with the necessities generated by the hypogravity (Figure 39).

Figure 39- Hip Flexion peak per subject

3 Discussion

This study looks at the kinematic changes in human gait under various amounts of simulated gravitational unloading with and without inclination, starting at 100% (E), passing through 38% (Ma), and going all the way to 20% (Mo) of normal body weight, returning thereafter to Earth (ER). The major goal is to determine if each degree of unloading results in distinct alterations specific to that % of normal body weight. Additionally, the study endeavors to characterize the gait pattern in each of the seven potential environments (E; E inc; Ma; Ma inc; Mo; Mo inc; ER). Moreover, this study aims to scrutinize the potential alterations occurring during the return to Earth, examining whether these changes are influenced by the preceding level(s) of gravitational unloading.

Irrespective of anatomical considerations, each participant consistently reported that walking with bodyweight reduction was more favorable. Mars ranked the lowest in perceived exertion for the majority, registering at 2.3, closely followed by the moon at 2.7. In contrast, Earth ranked third, with an average rate of perceived exertion (RPE) of 4.2. While still relatively low, this value is nearly double that observed on Mars, possibly due to the increased energy expenditure needed to move a higher body weight which comes with some musculoskeletal fatigue. EReturn evoked the highest perceived exertion, with an average rating of 5.3, largely due to a one-point rise in RPE reported by four individuals and a two-point increase by subject GH_JAMOR_012. These people notably reported feeling heavier after the unloading period and were surprised by the magnitude of their perceived weight.

The observed variety in evaluations between the Moon and Mars is most likely due to changes in perceived instability and the transition to more familiar locomotor patterns. An intriguing observation was that the Moon received the lowest possible RPE scores in the case of the three most athletically inclined subjects accustomed to strength training. This outcome may be attributed to their heightened ability to manage the lower limbs in tandem with the core, promoting stability with the body's center of gravity proximate to its center of mass. This emphasizes the importance of structured training in developing successful gait patterns on the Moon, as well as the importance of lunar mission preparation. This dataset is important because it allows for a thorough investigation of differences between contexts and makes it easier to establish correlations between perceived exertion levels and the kinematic variables discussed below.

Passing to the **Kinematics**, from the seven eligible **Spatio-Temporal** variables analyzed only 3 revealed major differences in the Friedman Test after the Bonferroni Correction Step Time ($t=19.917$; $p=0.003$), Swing Time ($t=24.407$; $p<0.001$) and Steps PM ($t=18.017$; $p=0.006$).

Regarding the **Joint Kinematics**, 28 variables were studied, and from those 13 shown significant differences (Hip adduction peak; Knee extension peak; Knee 2nd flexion peak;

Knee adduction peak; Knee ROM in the Sagittal Plane; Ankle int rotation peak; Ankle Plantar Flexion peak; Ankle dorsiflexion peak; Ankle pronation peak; Ankle supination peak).

To highlight the key findings across the seven scenarios, we created four tables: one for Mo1, Mo2, Ma1, and Ma2. These tables are color-coded to match the surroundings portrayed in the graphs in the Results section, making them easier to read and more visually appealing. Variables with an asterisk (*) indicate statistically significant differences, and detailed explanations are provided below the relevant tables. Tables for Earth were not prepared because there were no differences between the three Earth variations, and their values are already represented in the tables comparing them to the other variables.

Table 4 stands out as the largest, encompassing Mo1 juxtaposed with all other environments. With a comprehensive dataset, it encapsulates the values of every variable across all environments. Hence, it is the focus of discussion, while the other three tables (Tables 54, 55, & 56) are provided in Attachment 4. In Table 4, variables exhibiting significant differences are not only marked with an asterisk (*), but they are also color-highlighted to indicate the respective environment with which they differ. Squares indicating multiple differences are depicted in white, with specific variations detailed below the table.

Several differences can be seen among each situation, with Mo1 being unique, but statistically meaningful differences can only be seen between the Mo1 and all the Earth conditions, with Spatio temporal variables such as step time and swing time taking longer on the Moon, and Steps PM being smaller indicating a slower cadency for the same speed. On the knee, total ROM in the Sagittal Plane as well as 2nd flexion peak, revealing a stiffer joint, but with a way higher knee adduction. Looking over to the ankle, internal rotation and pronation are significantly decreased. These changes are seen thought all the terrestrial landscapes. On table 54, Mo2 keeps the same dissimilarities with E1, E2, & ER1, with a few percentage points deviation regarding the non-inclined version of itself.

Shifting gears to the red planet, Tables 55, and 56 are dedicated to Mars. At 38% BW humans can maintain a more Earth-like gait pattern, with changes on the same variables, but in a diminished and easier to adapt version. With our neighbor planet being in the middle in virtually every variable, changes in the gait pattern are not as pronounced with most of the subjects reporting a easier adaptation to the environment. Therefore, its partial gravity might be a good candidate for starting weight reducing training and rehabilitation.

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

Table 4- MoI Pairwise Comparisons

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

Variables	Mo1	Mo2	Ma1	Ma2	E1	E2	ER1
Step Length (cm)	Avg-38,23 σ- 21.25	Avg-43,69 σ- 20.9	Avg-55,39 σ- 6.73	Avg-55,23 σ- 5.63	Avg-52,92 σ- 3.99	Avg-53,85 σ- 4.76	Avg-53,54 σ- 4.01
Step Time (s)	Avg-0.64 σ- 0.09	Avg-0.62 σ- 0.09	Avg-0.61 σ- 0.08	Avg-0.61 σ- 0.07	*Avg-0.59 σ- 0.06	* Avg-0.60 σ- 0.06	*Avg-0.59 σ- 0.06
Cycle Time (s)	Avg-1.29 σ- 0.19	Avg-1.26 σ- 0.17	Avg-1.24 σ- 0.14	Avg-1.24 σ- 0.13	Avg-1.21 σ- 0.11	Avg-1.22 σ- 0.12	Avg-1.19 σ- 0.09
Swing Time (s)	Avg-0.51 σ- 0.09	Avg-0.49 σ- 0.08	Avg-0.48 σ- 0.06	Avg-0.47 σ- 0.06	*Avg-0.44 σ- 0.04	*Avg-0.44 σ- 0.04	*Avg-0.44 σ- 0.04
Stance Time (s)	Avg-0.78 σ- 0.10	Avg-0.77 σ- 0.08	Avg-0.76 σ- 0.06	Avg-0.76 σ- 0.06	Avg-0.76 σ- 0.04	Avg-0.77 σ- 0.04	Avg-0.75 σ- 0.04
Steps PM (spm)	Avg-96.28 σ- 6.05	Avg-96.73 σ- 6.59	Avg- 99.54 σ- 6.9	Avg-99.11 σ- 4.63	*Avg-103.16 σ- 4.15	*Avg-101.41 σ- 4.65	*Avg-104.09 σ- 3.96
Strides PM (spm)	Avg-96.28 σ- 13.08	Avg-48.36 σ- 26.92	Avg-48.23 σ- 11.60	Avg-48.98 σ- 10.43	Avg-50.43 σ- 10.47	Avg-49.68 σ- 10.51	Avg-50.67 σ- 10.13
ROM X (°)	Avg-24.64 σ- 6.16	Avg-23.70 σ- 5.44	Avg-23.93 σ- 5.99	Avg-23.24 σ- 4.65	Avg-24.33 σ- 4.27	Avg-22.89 σ- 6.68	Avg-23.42 σ- 4.77
ROM Y (°)	Avg-35.03 σ- 9.38	Avg-34.61 σ- 8.50	Avg-34.55 σ- 7.31	Avg-33.76 σ- 7.28	Avg-32.06 σ- 7.01	Avg-35.54 σ- 10.96°	Avg-33.40 σ- 4.94°
ROM Z (°)	Avg-22.09 σ- 5.47°	Avg-22.87 σ- 5.73	Avg-21.07 σ- 4.47	Avg-20.85 σ- 5.7	Avg-24.81 σ- 5.32	Avg-23.81 σ- 4.11	Avg-24.94 σ- 5.48
Ankle Supination Peak (°)	Avg-24.58 σ- 6.94	Avg-23.56 σ- 6.68	Avg-23.63 σ- 6.98	Avg-21.37 σ- 5.94	Avg-20.67 σ- 6.82	Avg-18.62 σ- 7.41	*Avg-18.73 σ- 7.36
Ankle Pronation Peak (°)	Avg-0.6 σ- 5.42	Avg-1.43 σ- 4.87	Avg-0.30 σ- 5.72	Avg-0.87 σ- 5.27	*Avg-4.36 σ- 5.30	*Avg-4.27 σ- 4.94	*Avg-4.70 σ- 7.07°
Ankle dorsiflexion peak (°)	Avg-14.96 σ- 4.58	Avg-14.21 σ- 4.60	Avg-13.98 σ- 4.00	Avg-14.86 σ- 4.69	Avg16.90 σ- 4.13	*Avg-20.36 σ- 12.59	*Avg-18.70 σ- 6.12
Plantar Flexion peak (°)	Avg-20.08 σ- 9.66	Avg-20.40 σ- 9.14	Avg-19.58 σ- 8.08	Avg-18.91 σ- 8.45	Avg-15.56 σ- 7.55	Avg-15.18 σ- 7.97	*Avg-14.69 σ- 7.82
Ankle Internal Rotation Peak (°)	Avg-2.86 σ- 5.97	Avg-2.41 σ- 5.30	Avg-2.68 σ- 5.56	Avg-3.67 σ- 5.60	*Avg-5.90 σ- 4.65	*Avg-6.50 σ- 6.66	*Avg-5.08 σ- 5.75
Ankle ext rot peak (°)	Avg-19.23 σ- 8.00	Avg-18.46 σ- 8.62	Avg-18.39 σ- 7.54	Avg-17.78 σ- 6.94	Avg-19.37 σ- 7.92	Avg-16.81 σ- 7.92	Avg-19.86 σ- 8.52
Knee Adduction (°)	Avg-6,53 σ- 4.02	Avg-6,23 σ- 3.71	Avg-6,02 σ- 3.93	Avg-5,72 σ- 3.80	*Avg-4,41 σ- 2,91	Avg-5,12 σ- 4,70	*Avg-4,22 σ- 2,59
Knee abduction (°)	Avg-10,14 σ- 8,53	Avg-9,32 σ- 7,23	Avg-9,59 σ- 6,37	Avg-9,49 σ- 6,85	Avg-12,15 σ- 7,67	Avg-11,65 σ- 6,86	*Avg-15,23 σ- 8,07
Knee ROM frontal plane (°)	Avg-16,67 σ- 9,21	Avg-15,54 σ- 7,46	Avg15,62 σ- 7,15	Avg-15,21 σ- 7,6	Avg-16,55 σ- 6,69	Avg-16,77 σ- 7,85	Avg-16,31 σ- 7,27
Knee ROM transverse plane(°)	Avg-15,68 σ- 13,7	Avg-19,94 σ- 4,77	Avg-16,91 σ- 12,81	Avg-16,90 σ- 3,97	Avg-21,59 σ- 3,12	Avg-19,15 σ- 11,13	Avg20,96 σ- 6,38
Knee INT rot peak (°)	Avg-2,86 σ- 5,67	Avg-2,41 σ- 4,30	Avg-2,68 σ- 3,92	Avg-3,07 σ- 3,84	Avg-5,90 σ- 3,11	Avg-6,50 σ- 4,49	Avg-5,08 σ- 5,85
Knee ext rot peak (°)	Avg-19,23 σ- 5,73	Avg-18,46 σ- 5,72	Avg-18,39 σ- 4,54	Avg-17,78 σ- 4,22	*Avg-19,37 σ- 3,87	*Avg-16,81 σ- 5,31	*Avg-19,86 σ- 4,36
Knee Extension Peak (°)	Avg-0,12 σ- 2,89	Avg0,25 σ- 2,70	Avg-0,41 σ- 3,32	Avg-0,30 σ- 2,52	*Avg-1,47 σ- 2,59	Avg(-)0,11 σ- 3,46°	Avg(-)1,05 σ- 2,95
Knee ROM Sagittal plane (°)	Avg-32,62 σ- 7,26	Avg-32,51 σ- 4,34	Avg-33,63 σ- 6,57	Avg-34,59 σ- 6,48	*Avg-40,45 σ- 6,25	*Avg-40,56 σ- 6,37	*Avg-38,85 σ- 7,24
Knee 1st flexion peak (°)	Avg-19,68 σ- 7,07	Avg-19,04 σ- 7,80	Avg-17,42 σ- 6,60	Avg-17,64 σ- 4,39	Avg-15,23 σ- 6,97	Avg-20,90 σ- 9,71	Avg-17,99 σ- 6,64

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

Knee 2nd Flexion Peak (°)	Avg-56.32 σ- 6.34	Avg-55.45 σ- 4.46	Avg-58.37 σ- 5.73	Avg-59.08 σ- 6.76	*Avg-65.76 σ- 7.09	*Avg-65.11 σ- 6.56	*Avg-64.94 σ- 8.77
Hip ext rot peak (°)	Avg-18.22 σ- 7.77	Avg-18.57 σ- 5.67	Avg-18.80 σ- 5.93	Avg-18.67 σ- 4.91	Avg-18.63 σ- 8.98	Avg-17.43 σ- 5.82	Avg-19.53 σ- 4.86
Hip Flexion Peak (°)	Avg-21.09 σ- 11.56	Avg-22.18 σ- 11.57	Avg-20.87 σ- 11.09	Avg-22.13 σ- 11.46	Avg-27.26 σ- 7.50	*Avg-30.87 σ- 7.89	Avg-25.23 σ- 8.38
Hip ROM Transverse plane(°)	Avg-14.94 σ- 4.79	Avg-14.31 σ- 4.45	Avg-14.00 σ- 5.06	Avg-14.92 σ- 3.81	Avg-15.17 σ- 4.22	Avg-15.59 σ- 3.74	Avg-16.69 σ- 4.56
Hip int rot peak (°)	Avg-0.32 σ- 4.42	Avg-1.38 σ- 3.61	Avg-1.00 σ- 2.54	Avg-1.24 σ- 2.15	Avg-2.85 σ- 5.05	Avg-4.15 σ- 5.86	Avg-1.43 σ- 4.01
Hip ROM Frontal plane (°)	Avg-13.74 σ- 1.93	Avg-12.13 σ- 3.079	Avg-11.60 σ- 3.84	Avg-11.12 σ- 3.15	Avg-13.89 σ- 2.64	Avg-13.87 σ- 2.09	Avg-13.46 σ- 2.74
Hip ROM frontal Plane (°)	Avg-32.62 σ- 7.22	Avg-33.51 σ- 6.48	Avg-33.63 σ- 5.98	Avg-34.59 σ- 7.87°	Avg-40.45 σ- 5.38	Avg-40.56 σ- 8.33	Avg-38.84 σ- 6.26
Hip extension peak (°)	Avg-11.53 σ- 9.22	Avg-11.33 σ- 8.59	Avg-12.77 σ- 8.02	Avg-12.47 σ- 6.48	Avg-13.2 σ- 5.79	Avg-9.69 σ- 9.04	Avg-10.63 σ- 10.42
Hip add peak (°)	Avg-3.09 σ- 3.81	Avg-2.57 σ- 3.33	Avg-2.93 σ- 4.53	Avg-2.70 σ- 3.86	Avg-5.62 σ- 3.42	Avg-5.60 σ- 3.90	Avg-5.81 σ- 3.30
Hip abd peak (°)	Avg-10.65 σ- 4.76	Avg-9.62 σ- 3.39	Avg-8.68 σ- 3.38	Avg-8.42 σ- 3.01	Avg-8.28 σ- 3.71	Avg-8.28 σ- 4.60	Avg-7.65 σ- 3.92

Mo1 vs E1

Step Time- 8.5% bigger (0.635seg vs 0.587seg)
 Swing Time- 15.9% bigger (0.509seg vs 0.439seg)
 Steps PM- 7.7% smaller (96.284spm vs 103.156spm)
 Knee Extension Peak, 93% smaller (0.115° vs -1.473°);
 Knee 2nd Flexion Peak 14.4% smaller (56.317° vs 67.762°);
 Knee Adduction 33.4% bigger (6.534° vs 4.405°);
 Ankle Internal Rotation Peak 52% smaller (2.860° vs 5.902°);
 Ankle Pronation Peak 97.4% smaller (0.055° vs 4.356°);
 Knee ROM Sagittal plane 19.7% smaller (54.3° vs 67.235°).

Mo1 vs E2

Step Time- 5.1% bigger (0.635seg vs 0.603seg)
 Swing Time- 15.9% bigger (0.509seg vs 0.438seg)
 Steps PM- 5.1% smaller (96.284spm vs 104.093spm)
 Hip Flexion Peak, 32.7% smaller (21.089° vs 30.869°).
 Knee 2nd Flexion Peak 13.5% smaller (56.317° vs 65.105°);
 Ankle Pronation Peak 97.2% smaller (0.055° vs 4.272°);
 Knee ROM Sagittal plane 16.7% smaller (54.3° vs 65.588°)

Mo1 vs ER1

Step Time- 8.6% bigger (0.635seg vs 0.585seg)
 Swing Time- 15.8% bigger (0.509seg vs 0.445seg)
 Steps PM- 8% smaller (96.284spm vs 101.406spm)
 Knee 2nd Flexion Peak 13.3% smaller (56.317° vs 64.936°);
 Knee Adduction 35.5% bigger (6.534° vs 4.219°);
 Ankle Internal Rotation Peak 43.7% smaller (2.860° vs 5.076°);
 Ankle Pronation Peak 98.3% smaller (0.055° vs 4.692°);
 Ankle Supination Peak 31% bigger (24.583° vs 18.729°);
 Knee ROM Sagittal plane 17% smaller (54.3° vs 65.986°)

Figure 40- Mo1 Significant Differences

Mo2vs E1

Knee 2nd Flexion Peak 18.2% smaller; (55.446° vs 67.762°);
 Ankle Internal Rotation Peak 59.2% smaller; (2.406° vs 5.902°)
 Knee ROM Sagittal plane 21.7% smaller (55.202° vs 67.235°).

Mo2vs E2

Hip Flexion Peak, 29.2% smaller; (22.178° vs 30.869°).
 Knee 2nd Flexion Peak 14.8% smaller; (55.446° vs 65.105°);
 Ankle Internal Rotation Peak 63% smaller; ; (2.406° vs 6.503°)
 Ankle Pronation Peak 96.7% smaller; (0.143° vs 4.272°);
 Knee ROM Sagittal plane 18.8% smaller. (55.202° vs 65.588°)

Mo2vs ER1

Knee 2nd Flexion Peak 14.5% smaller; (55.446° vs 64.936°)
 Knee ROM abduction plane; (9.317° vs 12.086°);
 Ankle Internal Rotation Peak 52.6% smaller; (2.406° vs 5.076°);
 Plantar Flexion peak 26.8% bigger; (20.077° vs 14.694°)
 Knee ROM Sagittal plane 19% smaller; (55.202° vs 65.986°)

Figure 41- Mo2 significant differences

Ma1 vs E1
Knee 2nd Flexion 11.2% smaller; (58.369° vs 67.762°).
Knee ROM Sagittal plane 16% smaller (57.957° vs 67.235°).

Ma1 vs E2
Hip Flexion Peak, 32.4% smaller; (20.862° vs 30.869°).
Knee 2nd Flexion 10.3% smaller; (58.369° vs 65.105°);
Ankle dorsiflexion peak 17.8% smaller; (14.213° vs 18.051°)
Ankle Pronation Peak 92.9% smaller; (0.304° vs 4.272°);
Knee ROM Sagittal plane 17.1% smaller (57.957° vs 65.588°)

Ma1 vs ER1
Knee 2nd Flexion 11.1%; smaller; (58.369° vs 64.936°)
max y - dorsiflexion peak 25.3% smaller; (14.213° vs 18.704°)
Knee ROM Sagittal 13.9% smaller. (57.957° vs 65.986°)

Figure 43- Ma1 Significant differences

Ma2 vs E1
Knee 2nd Flexion 10.2% smaller. (59.084° vs 67.762°);
Knee ROM Sagittal 14.4% smaller (58.788° vs 67.235°).

Ma2 vs E2
Hip Flexion Peak, 39.5% smaller. (22.125° vs 30.869°).
Ankle dorsiflexion peak 17.5% smaller (14.855° vs 18.051°)

Ma2 vs ER1
Knee 2nd Flexion 9.9%; (59.084° vs 64.936°)
Knee Adduction 23% smaller. (9.486° vs 12.086°);
max y - dorsiflexion peak 21.6% smaller. (18.704° vs 18.704°)
Knee ROM Sagittal 12.2% smaller. (58.788° vs 65.986°)

Figure 42- Ma2 Significant Differences

The study of biomechanics in extraterrestrial environments is critical to understanding the obstacles and adaptations required for space exploration. Our research into gait dynamics across three celestial bodies, the Moon, Mars, and Earth, has revealed important insights into the biomechanical complexities of human mobility in space which are summarized in the tables above.

When we compare human gait on the Moon (Mo1) to terrestrial settings on Earth (E1), we see clear changes in Spatio-temporal and joint kinematics. On the Lunar surface, Step Time is 8.5% slower, Swing Time is 15.9% longer, and people take on average 8% less Steps PM in comparison to E1. These values are also seen when comparing to E2 & ER1, but only in Mo1, Mo2 as similar values to Mo1, but not statistically significant.

As for the joint kinematics the Moon has a smaller Knee extension peak, 2nd flexion peak, and total knee range of motion in the sagittal plane (ROM Y flx/ext K), with Mo1 moving 19.7% less than E1, leading to a smaller impact on the knee extensors during the gait. On the frontal plane, the Moon leads to an overall higher adduction on the knee which might generate higher tensions on the internal meniscus and an increased necessity of preventative strategies to reinforce knee stability. On the ankle, the internal rotation

and pronation necessity with the maintenance of external rotation leads to a smaller transversal plane ROM. Comparing Mo1 to E2, and ER1 leads to similar outcomes apart from the maintenance of maximum supination on the ankle, with the Mo1 revealing a larger supination peak in comparison to ER1 that, although appearing in comparisons with E1 & E2, it wasn't statistically significant. Although not statistically significant the peak Plantar Flexion increases by more than 20% on the Moon juxtaposing it with Earth.

Congruently with previous research (Apte, S., et al 2018; Awai, L, 2017) the Lunar gait is slower and with smaller ranges of motion in the Knee and Hip joints, with exacerbated values of Plantar Flexion. The lower body weight requires less force and amplitude to mobilize the body by a similar amount. Although not statistically meaningful, any of the Earth variations has a 4° higher dorsiflexion peak when comparing to Earth, revealing that on the Moon the ankle joint will require more extensor muscle strength, than flexor, leading to a potential disuse and atrophy of dorsiflexor muscles.

Transitioning to the incline lunar surface (Mo2), coincidental findings appear with an even larger drop in ROM Y flx/ext K to 21.7% emphasizing the importance of adaptive locomotor techniques in changing lunar topographies. Extremely relevant is the appearance of the statistical significance on the difference between the plantar flexion in the Lunar environment and Earth Return (ER1), with a 26.8% difference between conditions.

Voyaging to the flat Red Planet, the comparison of Mars and Earth demonstrates that Martian gravity imposes differing motor demands. Knee sagittal plane actions are also shortened, with ROM Y flx/ext K measuring 16% lower than its terrestrial equivalent, a lower impact than that of the lunar gravity, but still relevant. All the other comparisons still hold true between Ma1/Ma2, and all the variants of Earth, all but the significance in Plantar Flexion, although still quite enlarged in comparison to Earth. The only variable that only Ma1 and Ma2 have that doesn't reveal itself on the Moon, is the ankle dorsiflexion peak, which is 25.3% smaller on Ma1 and 21.6% smaller on Ma1 when comparing with ER1 and 17.8% and 17.5% smaller in comparison to E2. This probably means that the red planet gravity doesn't need the foot clearance to be as pronounced as Earth does. Mars appears as the middle ground between Earth and the Moon, standing between the two diametrically opposite environments in the bulk of the variables, despite being slightly closer to the Moon in most.

An important note is that the previous levels of unloading don't seem to affect the return the Earth to a great extent, with only minor shifts between E1 and ER1. Further research on the topic should be performed with bigger subject pools, environment order randomization, and electromyographical data to strengthen the findings. The same can be said for the 4 degrees inclination which was insufficient to produce relevant differences within the same unloading level.

It is crucial to acknowledge that all participants in this study were unloading-naive, meaning they had no prior experience with walking or running in an unloading system, nor had they encountered unloading in any other context. Consequently, two plausible explanations for the observed results arise: firstly, the novelty of the unloading treadmill, and secondly, the unloading environment itself, or probably a combination of both factors. However, given that participants underwent an acclimation period, it seems improbable that the novelty of the treadmill system alone drove these alterations. Instead, it is conceivable that these changes in gait dynamics represent exploratory strategies adopted in response to the novel unloading environment.

Although this study did not directly evaluate proprioception, it is reasonable to conclude that the reduction in proprioceptive input in hypogravity situations contributed significantly to the reported changes. This conclusion is reinforced by the significant differences in gait dynamics seen among our unloaded subjects, notably on the Moon, as well as the high inter- and intra-subject variability. Thiel et al. (2014) found that hysteresis effects—temporary resistance to transitioning between stable states—are most pronounced when sensory information is reduced. Furthermore, Hubbuch et al. (2015) found that decreased sensory input increases metabolic expenditures, reduces efficiency, and causes greater muscle contractions during locomotion tasks. Furthermore, the availability of sensory information has a significant impact on perceptual judgments, with reduced proprioception potentially increasing the likelihood of falls and injuries (Toosizadeh et al., 2018). As a result, while not clearly quantified in our study, the importance of proprioceptive feedback in regulating gait dynamics in hypogravity situations deserves additional examination.

It is critical to note that our chosen test speed of 3.2 km/hr or 0.89 meters per second (m/s) was deliberately set lower than the walk-to-run transitions in the three gravitational situations. However, as unloading speeds grow, they may approach the preferred transition speed (PTS) limit. Ackermann et al. (2012) found that walking at 1.1 m/s resulted in a bounding/skipping gait when exposed to equivalent Moon gravity (1.63 m/s^2 , or approximately 16.6% of Earth gravitational acceleration). Participants walked in Mars-level gravity (3.72 m/s^2 , or 38% of Earth gravity). This shows a change in gait type between these two levels, which corresponds to our lowest unloading condition of 20% body weight.

The Froude number (Fr), a parameter that relates potential and kinetic energy, is useful in this scenario. It is derived using the equation $Fr = v^2/g$, where v is the participant's walking speed, g is the acceleration due to gravity, and h is the height of the center of mass (CM) estimated by leg length. Using our participant's chosen walking speed (0.89 m/s), the lowest gravitational acceleration of 1.962 m/s^2 (20% Earth gravity), and the estimated Fr associated with gait transitions of 0.5 (Kram et al., 1997), we arrive at $Fr = 0.5 = (0.89)^2/(1.962)h$. Solving for h gives a leg length of 0.80m, meaning that only participants with CM below 80 centimeters would risk passing the

PTS, with the lowest value on our subjects coming at 82.1 centimeters at the lateral femoral epicondyle.

Furthermore, De Witt et al. (2014) found that the Froude number may underestimate PTS speed, with actual transition speeds happening at levels "much greater than 0.5". Furthermore, despite the reduced load, individuals maintained a strong walking pace during the unloading procedure. Given these considerations, we are confident that the effects seen in this study are predominantly the result of hysteretic effects rather than a shift in stride typology. However, gait transitions may influence biomechanical changes under lower loads, and future study should investigate this more.

It is of high relevance to develop training routines training routines that are adapted to the necessities of the subject and the ones created by the environment. For example, knowing that the hip and knee joints will experience less total range of motion in situations where the individual is subjected to only 20% of its bodyweight, a comprehensive strength training protocol should be prepared aiming to prevent loss of muscle mass, muscle strength and bone mass, that would undoubtedly target more the muscles involved on the gait pattern, such as the glutes and quadriceps. Bi-articular muscles involving both the knee and the hip joints, like the rectus femoris, and the hamstrings might suffer even more from disuse in the astronaut case or fail to fully improve the gait pattern in a rehab scenario on Earth that uses a LBPP machine to reduce the patient bodyweight.

For astronauts on long term missions to other celestial bodies, this research might provide some insights for spacesuit design. Knowing that there are substantially different biomechanical adaptations, driven by the different gravities on the Moon and Mars, a single spacesuit design that fails to account for these changes, might lead to unnecessary stress or even injury. Developing suits that have a variable ability to support astronaut's bodyweight, generating increased proprioception on the ankle joint, extra weight, increased mobility, and biometric data guided by AI to help astronauts perceive the most efficient way to move in order to achieve a certain objective.

Our research elucidates the complex interplay between gravitational circumstances and locomotor biomechanics among decreased bodyweight variables, giving important insights into rehabilitation strategies here on Earth, deload protocols for athletes, gait training for people in special conditions that are unable to support their body weight while walking or running. These insights are also extremely relevant for optimizing spacesuit design, astronaut training regimes, and mission planning procedures. By thoroughly understanding the biomechanical underpinnings of human locomotion in space, we want to pave the road for safer and more efficient exploration beyond Earth's boundaries.

The study recognizes its limitations and the need for replication. One restriction is the unloading system's design, which can both support and hinder hip movement, thereby

altering gait patterns. Future research should go deeper into these variables to better understand their impact on gait patterns. It is critical to remember that all experimental unloading methods have flaws. For example, some methods just unload the trunk (suspension systems), whilst others may produce additional inertial resistance (submersion) or require short study epochs (parabolic flight). Despite its limitations, the AlterG system efficiently facilitates the investigation of unloading paradigms. However, while analyzing results, researchers should keep in mind the inherent limitations. Further investigation is warranted to explore these aspects in greater detail and enhance our understanding of gait dynamics under reduced loading conditions.

4 Conclusion

Through our journey into the biomechanics of gait on simulated extraterrestrial gravities we aim to help pave the way to a thriving human society looking into making life on Earth better, while providing valuable insights into space exploration and near future Lunar and Martian colonies.

The knowledge provided by this research reveals distinct alterations in spatio-temporal and joint kinematics compared to Earth-bound settings. On the Moon, Step and Swing Times are prolonged, while Step Frequency diminishes. Hip and Knee ROM decrease along with ankle dorsiflexion, on the opposite end Plantar flexion increases together with knee adduction, conditions that might lead to stress and injuries after long exposures. At speeds higher than the ones used in this study, the walk to run transition happens, eventually leading to the loss of the inverted pendulum gait pattern with jumping being the preferred locomotion way. The reduced gravity also creates less proprioceptive cues to help guide the stride mechanics posing a challenge to locomotion and exercise on the Moon.

On Mars, we encounter a middle ground between the Lunar and Terrestrial realms. Although not as pronounced as on the Moon, most of the significant differences still stand, meaning it still imposes major biomechanical adaptations to humans looking to thrive there. As such adaptations in astronaut training programs and spacesuit design should be made that combat the negative adaptations above mentioned. By understanding the intricate interplay between gravitational circumstances and locomotor biomechanics, we can pave the way for safer and more efficient space exploration endeavors.

As we conclude this study, we acknowledge its limitations and the imperative need for further research and replication. The inherent complexities of unloading systems and the AlterG treadmill underscore the necessity for continued exploration and refinement of experimental methodologies.

One small step for man at a time, we aim to take a big leap for mankind by tackling urgent and difficult barriers to the future of space exploration and human adaptation beyond Earth's boundaries while improving the life of everyone within the pale blue marble. Through continued collaboration and inquiry, we stand poised to unlock the next frontier of human potential and discovery.

5 Study limitations and future perspectives

Numerous problems hampered the study's full implementation, necessitating the deletion of specific processes from the final edition of this MSc thesis. Time restrictions, compounded by unforeseen circumstances such as floods, cable ruptures, and a knee operation, prevented many individuals from completing the re-test portion, compromising the data's dependability. While EMG data was obtained and evaluated, the rectus femoris EMG placement was shifted 5 cm higher on the thigh, departing from SENIAM (Surface Electromyography for the Non-Invasive Assessment of Muscles) recommendations due to compression by the AlterG shorts, resulting in poor-quality data. Consequently, the team chose to omit these measurements from the final version.

In terms of spatial-temporal and kinematic data contained in the thesis, limits appeared in two variables where Xsens was unable to provide exact information due to hip displacement data reading difficulties. Notably, step length was extracted from the AlterG session report, providing a high-fidelity summary of basic exercise session data; however, step width could not be accounted for and was obtained from the final data.

As stated in the conclusion, the used unloading system AlterG by providing gait support at the hip level, might hinder some regular hip movements, as well as improve balance of the test subjects, thereby altering gait patterns. Future research should go deeper into these variables to better understand their impact on gait patterns. It is critical to remember that all experimental unloading methods have flaws, and that despite its limitations, the AlterG system efficiently facilitates the investigation of unloading paradigms.

Future study's that are being planned by the team, will include completely examined and reviewed EMG data. Furthermore, it lays the framework for more advanced items, including virtual reality, to confirm adjustments and move humanity forward to the next frontier.

As one of the rare studies to investigate the biomechanics of simulated hypogravity on the human body, this thesis makes an important contribution to our understanding of adaptations. It sets the path for future research into mitigating detrimental adaptations in space and leveraging effects on Earth for specific groups like as athletes, the elderly, and those recovering from injuries, so presenting a positive viewpoint on bodily unloading.

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Attachments

Attachment 1- Informed Consent Form

CONSELHO DE ÉTICA DA FACULDADE DE MOTRICIDADE HUMANA

CONSENTIMENTO INFORMADO LIVRE E ESCLARECIDO PARA INVESTIGAÇÃO CIENTÍFICA COM SERES HUMANOS

Título do projeto ou estudo: Caracterização biomecânica do padrão de marcha de adultos saudáveis perante diferentes condições de microgravidade - Comparação com 1G e racional de treino

Mestrando: Duarte de Santa Maria Marques Conchinhas

Orientador: Professora Doutora Filipa Oliveira da Silva João

Co-Orientador: Professor Doutor Nelson Vinagre

Instituições de acolhimento:

Faculdade de Motricidade Humana, Universidade de Lisboa (FMH-UL)

Faculdade de Medicina, Universidade de Lisboa (FM-UL)

Cento de Estudos de Medicina Aeroespacial (CEMA)

Este documento, designado **Consentimento, Informado, Livre e Esclarecido**, contém informação importante em relação ao estudo para o qual foi abordado/a, bem como o que esperar se decidir participar no mesmo. Leia atentamente toda a informação aqui contida. Deve sentir-se inteiramente livre para colocar qualquer questão, assim como para discutir com terceiros (amigos, familiares) a decisão da sua participação neste estudo.

Informação geral
Este estudo tem como principal objetivo avaliar a biomecânica do padrão de marcha de adultos saudáveis perante diferentes condições de microgravidade simulada (20%; 38%; 60%), comparando-as com 1G.
Qual a duração esperada da minha participação?
A duração esperada para efetuar todos os procedimentos necessários à realização desta investigação será de 4 sessões realizadas com um intervalo de 7 dias entre elas. Primeiramente será realizada uma sessão de familiarização e posteriormente serão realizadas 3 sessões de teste. Cada sessão irá demorar aproximadamente 50 minutos por participante. (? cada utilizador será submetido as 4 condições gradualmente e como tal, 10 minutos para cada, mais tempo de segurança?)
Quais os procedimentos do estudo em que vou participar?

Qual a duração esperada da minha participação?
A duração esperada para efetuar todos os procedimentos necessários à realização desta investigação será de 3 sessões realizadas com um intervalo de 7 dias entre elas. Primeiramente será realizada uma sessão de familiarização e posteriormente serão realizadas 2 sessões de teste. Cada sessão irá demorar aproximadamente 60 minutos por participante.
Quais os procedimentos do estudo em que vou participar?
<p>O presente estudo é composto por 3 sessões onde terá que realizar marcha numa passadeira rolante anti-gravidade (AlterG®) utilizando um sistema de óculos de realidade virtual. Ser-lhe-ão colocados sensores inerciais para medir a cinemática da marcha, bem como sensores de eletromiografia para medir a ativação muscular dos membros inferiores. Duas sessões de testes serão posteriormente realizadas, com um intervalo de 7 dias entre elas, nas quais os participantes irão realizar a prova de marcha, de forma a determinar a reprodutibilidade intra e inter-sessão de cada medida recolhida e aferir o impacto da diminuição do peso no padrão biomecânico e de ativação muscular no ciclo da marcha.</p> <p>Sessão 1 (Familiarização): esta sessão tem como objetivo familiarizar o participante com o protocolo, recolher parâmetros antropométricos (massa, altura, % massa gorda, perímetros da anca e coxa, comprimento do pé, perna e coxa) e preencher dois questionários. Ser-lhe-á explicada a posição em que deverá efetuar o teste, as indicações de segurança, o número de condições de teste, a velocidade de marcha, a duração de cada sessão e os critérios de execução subjacentes à exclusão e repetição da prova. Nesta sessão irá experimentar caminhar no Alter-G, com diferentes níveis de hipogravidade. De seguida irá experimentar utilizar uns óculos de realidade virtual (RV) que simulam o ambiente visual da Lua e de Marte. Por fim, experimentará caminhar novamente no Alter-G utilizando em simultâneo os óculos de RV. Em todas estas condições ser-lhe-á perguntado como se sente.</p> <p>Sessão 2 (Teste de marcha): nesta sessão irá realizar a marcha em diferentes condições de microgravidade, utilizando em simultâneo os óculos de RV. A sequência de ambientes será aleatória, podendo realizar uma das seguintes: T-M-L-T, T-L-M-T, M-T-L-T ou L-T-M-T, onde T é Terra, M é Marte, e L é Lua. Terá que caminhar durante 10 minutos em cada condição de gravidade, de forma consecutiva, à velocidade constante de 3.2km/h. Em cada ambiente gravítico, dentro dos 10 minutos, 2 deles serão a caminhar com uma inclinação de 4% na passadeira e será avisado antes desse momento acontecer.</p> <p>Sessão 3 (Re-teste de marcha): nesta sessão irá realizar o mesmo teste realizado na sessão anterior.</p> <p>Através deste estudo serão avaliadas variáveis cinemáticas tridimensionais, parâmetros espaço-temporais e ativações musculares do membro inferior.</p>
A minha participação é voluntária?
A sua participação é voluntária e pode recusar-se a participar. Caso decida participar neste estudo é importante ter conhecimento que pode desistir a qualquer momento, sem qualquer tipo de consequência para si. No caso de decidir abandonar o estudo, a sua relação com a Faculdade de Motricidade Humana (FMH), Faculdade de Medicina (FMUL) e o Centro de Estudos de Medicina Aeroespacial (CEMA), não será afetada. Se for o caso, o seu estatuto enquanto estudante ou funcionário de qualquer uma destas instituições será mantido e não sofrerá nenhuma consequência da sua não-participação ou desistência. A sua participação não conduzirá a qualquer gratificação ou benefício desportivo, pessoal, ou profissional, assim como uma eventual recusa ou abandono não terá qualquer consequência para si.

Quais os possíveis benefícios da minha participação?
Ao participar neste estudo terá a possibilidade de contribuir para a produção de conhecimento científico, experienciar e colaborar num projeto de investigação científica e ter contacto com metodologias inovadoras. Para além disso, poderá conhecer melhor o seu estado atual de padrão de marcha, pois ser-lhe-á fornecido um relatório detalhado com os resultados da avaliação. Este consistirá na avaliação do seu padrão de locomoção e ativação muscular.
Quais os possíveis riscos da minha participação?
As avaliações e tarefas motoras solicitadas na realização do teste em qualquer uma das condições, não envolvem atividade física de elevado risco, pelo que a probabilidade de sofrer danos físicos é mínima. Poderá sentir um ligeiro desconforto muscular durante a utilização da passadeira, associado às condições de menor peso, que ocorrerá somente no período de transição entre diferentes gravidades. Existem apenas contraindicações para pessoas que previamente tenham fraturas instáveis, trombose venosa profunda, hipotensão arterial ou outras alterações cardiovasculares.
Quem assume a responsabilidade, no caso de um evento negativo?
O laboratório e os seus técnicos rejeitam qualquer responsabilidade por lesões ou acidentes que possam ocorrer, bem como pelos seus efeitos ou consequências, cuja causa não seja atribuível a manifestos erros ou omissões de ordem técnica na aplicação das recolhas. A assinatura deste termo de consentimento implica a aceitação expressa desta limitação de responsabilidade.
Há cobertura por uma companhia de seguros?
Não.
Quem deve ser contactado em caso de urgência?
Nome da pessoa a contactar: _____ Idade da pessoa a contactar: _____ Grau de parentesco relativamente ao participante no estudo: _____ Contacto telefónico: _____
Como é assegurada a confidencialidade dos dados?
Os dados do presente estudo serão confidenciais, sendo atribuído um código a cada pessoa para identificar a sua avaliação no momento de análise dos dados. Não haverá qualquer referência ao nome de nenhum participante, ou outro elemento de identificação.
O que acontecerá aos dados quando a investigação terminar?
Os dados serão tratados e darão lugar a um relatório personalizado de avaliação. Este relatório será fornecido ao participante. Os dados resultantes da avaliação serão posteriormente armazenados e encriptados num servidor próprio, no Laboratório de Biomecânica da FMH, de acordo com a lei europeia de proteção de dados.
Como irão os resultados do estudo ser divulgados e com que finalidades?
A informação recolhida pode vir a ser utilizada no futuro por razões estatísticas ou científicas, mantendo-se a confidencialidade dos dados. Com a informação recolhida, poderão vir a ser produzidas teses de mestrado e publicados artigos técnicos e/ou científicos em revistas de impacto nacional e/ou internacional na área do treino e/ou da investigação. Em qualquer dos casos, será sempre garantido o anonimato dos participantes.

Em caso de dúvidas quem devo contactar?

Para qualquer questão relacionada com a sua participação neste estudo, por favor, contactar:
Duarte Conchinhas: 910 973 560. Email: duarte.conchinhas@gmail.com
Filipa João: filipajoao@fmh.ulisboa.pt

Assinatura do Consentimento Informado, Livre e Esclarecido

Li (ou alguém leu para mim) o presente documento e estou consciente do que esperar quanto à minha participação no estudo “Caracterização biomecânica do padrão de marcha de adultos saudáveis perante diferentes condições de hipogravidade”. Tive a oportunidade de colocar todas as questões e as respostas esclareceram todas as minhas dúvidas. Assim, aceito voluntariamente participar neste estudo. Foi-me dada uma cópia deste documento.

Nome do participante

Assinatura do participante

Data

Investigador/Equipa de Investigação

Os aspetos mais importantes deste estudo foram explicados ao participante ou ao seu representante, antes de solicitar a sua assinatura. Uma cópia deste documento ser-lhe-á fornecida.

Nome da pessoa que obtém o consentimento

Assinatura da pessoa que obtém o consentimento

Data

Attachment 2- Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire for Everyone

PARQ-short em PT

Código participante: _____

Questionário de Prontidão para Atividade Física (PAR-Q)

Este questionário tem o objetivo de identificar a necessidade de avaliação por um médico antes do início da atividade física. Caso você responda "SIM" a uma ou mais perguntas, converse com seu médico ANTES de aumentar seu nível atual de atividade física. Mencione este questionário e as perguntas às quais você respondeu "SIM".

Por favor, assinale "SIM" ou "NÃO" às seguintes perguntas:

1. Algum médico já disse que você possui algum problema de coração e que só deveria realizar atividade física supervisionado por profissionais de saúde?
 Sim Não
2. Você sente dores no peito quando pratica atividade física?
 Sim Não
3. No último mês, você sentiu dores no peito quando praticou atividade física?
 Sim Não
4. Você apresenta desequilíbrio devido à tontura e/ ou perda de consciência?
 Sim Não
5. Você possui algum problema ósseo ou articular que poderia ser piorado pela atividade física?
 Sim Não
6. Você toma atualmente algum medicamento para pressão arterial e/ou problema de coração?
 Sim Não
7. Sabe de alguma outra razão pela qual você não deve praticar atividade física?
 Sim Não

Nome completo _____ Idade: _____

Data _____ Assinatura: _____

Se você respondeu "SIM" a uma ou mais perguntas, leia e assine o "Termo de Responsabilidade para Prática de Atividade Física"

Termo de Responsabilidade para Prática de Atividade Física

Estou ciente de que é recomendável conversar com um médico antes de aumentar meu nível atual de atividade física, por ter respondido "SIM" a uma ou mais perguntas do "Questionário de Prontidão para Atividade Física" (PAR-Q). Assumo plena responsabilidade por qualquer atividade física praticada sem o atendimento a essa recomendação.

Nome completo _____

Data _____ Assinatura: _____

Attachment 3- Motion Sickness Susceptibility Questionnaire Short-form

Questionário Abreviado de Suscetibilidade ao Enjoo de Movimento (MSSQ-Short) Código participante: _____

1. Por favor, indique a sua **idade** anos. 2. Por favor, indique o seu sexo (marque a caixa)
- Masculino Feminino**
[₁] [₂]

Este questionário foi concebido para avaliar o seu grau de suscetibilidade ao enjojo de movimento, e quais os tipos de movimento mais suscetíveis de causar esse enjojo. Enjojo, neste contexto, significa sentir-se enjoado ou nauseado ou realmente vomitar.

Apenas a sua experiência de INFÂNCIA (antes dos 12 anos de idade), para cada um dos seguintes tipos de transporte ou entretenimento, indique:

3. **Quando CRIANÇA (antes dos 12 anos)**, com que frequência se **sentiu enjoado ou nauseado** (marque as caixas):

	Não aplicável Nunca Viajou	Nunca sentiu enjoos	Raramente sentiu enjoos	Algumas vezes sentiu enjoos	Frequentemente sentiu enjoos
Carros					
Autocarros					
Comboios					
Aviões					
Embarcações pequenas					
Navios, por exemplo, Ferries					
Baloiços em parques infantis					
Carrosséis em parques infantis					
Montanhas Russas, Diversões					
	t	0	1	2	3

A sua experiência NOS ÚLTIMOS 10 ANOS (aproximadamente), para cada um dos seguintes tipos de transporte ou entretenimento, indique:

4. **Nos ÚLTIMOS 10 ANOS**, com que frequência se **sentiu enjoado ou nauseado** (marque as caixas):

	Não aplicável Nunca Viajou	Nunca sentiu enjoos	Raramente sentiu enjoos	Algumas vezes sentiu enjoos	Frequentemente sentiu enjoos
Carros					
Autocarros					
Comboios					
Aviões					
Embarcações pequenas					
Navios, por exemplo, Ferries					
Baloiços em parques infantis					
Carrosséis em parques infantis					
Montanhas Russas, Diversões					
	t	0	1	2	3

Pontuação do MSSQ - Curto

Secção A (Criança) (Pergunta 3)

Marque o número de tipos de transporte não experimentados (ou seja, totalize o número de carrapatos na coluna 't', o máximo é 9).

Totalize as pontuações de doença para cada modo de transporte, ou seja, os nove tipos de 'carros' para 'grandes caçambas' (use a tecla de pontuação numérica 0-3 na parte inferior, as pontuações na coluna 't' contam como zeros).

MSA = (pontuação total de doença da criança) x (9) / (9 - número de tipos não experimentados quando criança)

Nota 1: Quando um sujeito não experimentou nenhuma forma de transporte, ocorre uma divisão por erro zero. Não é possível estimar a suscetibilidade à doença de movimento deste sujeito na ausência de qualquer exposição relevante ao movimento.

Nota 2: A pontuação da Seção A (Criança) pode ser usada como um indicador pré-mórbido de suscetibilidade ao enjoo em pacientes com doença vestibular.

Secção B (Adulto) (Pergunta 4)

Repetir a secção A, mas utilizando os dados da secção B.

MSB = (pontuação total de doença adulto) x (9) / (9 - número de tipos não experimentados como adulto)

Pontuação Bruta MSSQ-Curto

Totalize a pontuação MSA da seção A (Criança) e a pontuação MSB da seção B (Adulto) para obter a pontuação bruta curta do MSSQ (intervalo possível de 0 a 54 no mínimo, sendo o máximo improvável)

Pontuação bruta do MSSQ = MSA + MSB

Pontuação Percentil MSSQ-Curto

As conversões brutas para percentis são dadas abaixo na Tabela 1 de Estatísticas e Figura 1. Use interpolação quando necessário.

Table 1. Estatísticas de Conversão de Médias e Percentil para o MSSQ-Short (n=257)

Conversão de percentis	Pontuações brutas MSSQ-Curto		
	Secção Infantil A	Adulto Secção B	Total A+B
0	0	0	0
10	.0	.0	.8
20	2.0	1.0	3.0
30	4.0	1,3	7,0
40	5.6	2,6	9,0
50	7,0	3,7	11,3
60	9,0	6,0	14,1
70	11,0	7,0	17,9
80	13,0	9,0	21,6
90	16,0	12,0	25,9
95	20,0	15,0	30,4
100	23,6	21,0	44,6
Média	7.75	5.11	12.90
Padrão de Desvio	5,94	4,84	9,90

Nota da tabela: os números são arredondados

Alternativamente, uma aproximação próxima é dada pelo polinômio ajustado onde y é percentil; x é pontuação bruta $y = a.x + b.x^2 + c.x^3 + d.x^4$
 $a = 5,1160923$ $b = -0,055169904$
 $c = -0,00067784495$ $d = 1,0714752e-005$

Attachment 4- SPSS Tables

Table 5-Normality Test Spatio Temporal Parameters

Normality Test Spatio-Temporal Parameters			
		Shapiro-Wilk	
	Estatística	gl	Sig.

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

step time R (S)#E1	,941	13	,465
step time R #E2	,957	13	,702
step time R#Mo1	,849	13	,028
step time R#Mo2	,870	13	,052
step time R#Ma1	,885	13	,084
step time R#Ma2	,877	13	,064
step time R#ER1	,958	13	,730
step length (CM) #E1	,942	13	,481
step length (CM) #E2	,928	13	,317
step length (CM) #Mo1	,842	13	,023
step length (CM)#Mo2	,879	13	,068
step length (CM) #Ma1	,937	13	,425
step length (cm) #Ma2	,930	13	,338
step length (cm)#ER1	,950	13	,602
stride width(cm)#E1	,436	13	<,001
stride width (cm) #E2	,726	13	,001
stride width #Mo1	,807	13	,008
stride width#Mo2	,781	13	,004
stride width#Ma1	,785	13	,005
stride width#Ma2	,727	13	,001
stride width #ER1	,874	13	,059
cycle time R (S)#E1	,930	13	,341
cycle time R #E2	,934	13	,379
cycle time R#Mo1	,853	13	,031
cycle time R#Mo2	,878	13	,068
cycle time R#Ma1	,882	13	,075
cycle time R#Ma2	,886	13	,087
cycle time R#ER1	,971	13	,906
Stance time R (S)#E1	,927	13	,307
Stance time R #E2	,935	13	,392
Stance time R#Mo1	,924	13	,285
Stance time R#Mo2	,935	13	,393
Stance time R#Ma1	,874	13	,059
Stance time R#Ma2	,881	13	,073
Stance time R#ER1	,958	13	,720
swing time R (S)#E1	,953	13	,647
swing time R #E2	,956	13	,699
swing time R#Mo1	,880	13	,072
swing time R#Mo2	,866	13	,047
swing time R#Ma1	,892	13	,104
swing time R#Ma2	,893	13	,107
swing time R#ER1	,924	13	,286
STEPS PM R #E1	,937	13	,416
STEPS PM R #E2	,971	13	,906
STEPS PM R#Mo1	,879	13	,068
STEPS PM R#Mo2	,725	13	,001

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STEPS PM R#Ma1	,921	13	,257
STEPS PM R#Ma2	,921	13	,258
STEPS PM R#ER1	,975	13	,948
STRIDES PM R #E1	,928	13	,325
STRIDES PM R #E2	,959	13	,741
STRIDES PM R#Mo1	,874	13	,060
STRIDES PM R#Mo2	,902	13	,141
STRIDES PM R#Ma1	,874	13	,060
STRIDES PM R#Ma2	,922	13	,265
STRIDES PM R#ER1	,963	13	,802

Table 6- Spatio Temporal Descriptives

Spatio-temporal Descriptives			
		Estadística	Estadística do teste Padrão
step time R (S)#E1	Média	0,587	0,017
	Mínimo	0,504	
	Máximo	0,677	
	Amplitude	0,173	
step time R #E2	Média	0,603	0,018
	Mínimo	0,509	
	Máximo	0,729	
	Amplitude	0,220	
step time R#Mo1	Média	0,635	0,025
	Mínimo	0,518	
	Máximo	0,754	
	Amplitude	0,236	
step time R#Mo2	Média	0,623	0,024
	Mínimo	0,527	
	Máximo	0,790	
	Amplitude	0,263	
step time R#Ma1	Média	0,612	0,021
	Mínimo	0,521	
	Máximo	0,757	
	Amplitude	0,236	
step time R#Ma2	Média	0,610	0,020
	Mínimo	0,533	
	Máximo	0,744	

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	Amplitude	0,211	
step time R#ER1	Média	0,585	0,016
	Mínimo	0,483	
	Máximo	0,675	
	Amplitude	0,192	
step length (CM) #E1	Média	52,923	1,106
	Mínimo	47,000	
	Máximo	59,000	
	Amplitude	12,000	
step length (CM) #E2	Média	53,846	1,320
	Mínimo	46,000	
	Máximo	60,000	
	Amplitude	14,000	
step length (CM) #Mo1	Média	38,231	5,893
	Mínimo	15,000	
	Máximo	67,000	
	Amplitude	52,000	
step length (CM)#Mo2	Média	43,692	5,797
	Mínimo	16,000	
	Máximo	70,000	
	Amplitude	54,000	
step length (CM) #Ma1	Média	55,385	1,866
	Mínimo	45,000	
	Máximo	67,000	
	Amplitude	22,000	
step length (cm) #Ma2	Média	55,231	1,561
	Mínimo	46,000	
	Máximo	66,000	
	Amplitude	20,000	
step length (cm)#ER1	Média	53,538	1,113
	Mínimo	45,000	
	Máximo	59,000	
	Amplitude	14,000	
stride width(cm)#E1	Média	123,746	86,208
	Mínimo	1,000	
	Máximo	1137,000	
	Amplitude	1136,000	
stride width (cm) #E2	Média	5,546	1,745
	Mínimo	0,900	

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	Máximo	23,800	
	Amplitude	22,900	
stride width #Mo1	Média	8,308	2,399
	Mínimo	1,000	
	Máximo	30,700	
	Amplitude	29,700	
stride width#Mo2	Média	8,185	2,368
	Mínimo	1,700	
	Máximo	29,700	
	Amplitude	28,000	
stride width#Ma1	Média	6,838	2,211
	Mínimo	0,300	
	Máximo	27,400	
	Amplitude	27,100	
stride width#Ma2	Média	6,246	1,972
	Mínimo	1,100	
	Máximo	26,300	
	Amplitude	25,200	
stride width #ER1	Média	7,985	1,967
	Mínimo	0,900	
	Máximo	24,600	
	Amplitude	23,700	
cycle time R (S)#E1	Média	1,214	0,030
	Mínimo	1,057	
	Máximo	1,380	
	Amplitude	0,323	
cycle time R #E2	Média	1,219	0,033
	Mínimo	1,066	
	Máximo	1,474	
	Amplitude	0,408	
cycle time R#Mo1	Média	1,292	0,053
	Mínimo	1,084	
	Máximo	1,593	
	Amplitude	0,509	
cycle time R#Mo2	Média	1,257	0,047
	Mínimo	1,071	
	Máximo	1,594	
	Amplitude	0,523	
cycle time R#Ma1	Média	1,240	0,040

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

	Mínimo	1,065		
	Máximo	1,520		
	Amplitude	0,455		
cycle time R#Ma2	Média	1,237	0,035	
	Mínimo	1,084		
	Máximo	1,492		
	Amplitude	0,408		
	cycle time R#ER1	Média	1,191	0,025
		Mínimo	1,028	
Máximo		1,336		
	Amplitude	0,308		
	Stance time R (S)#E1	Média	0,757	0,018
		Mínimo	0,674	
Máximo		0,873		
	Amplitude	0,199		
	Stance time R #E2	Média	0,774	0,023
		Mínimo	0,668	
Máximo		0,946		
	Amplitude	0,278		
	Stance time R#Mo1	Média	0,783	0,029
		Mínimo	0,649	
Máximo		0,966		
	Amplitude	0,317		
	Stance time R#Mo2	Média	0,768	0,026
		Mínimo	0,645	
Máximo		0,961		
	Amplitude	0,316		
	Stance time R#Ma1	Média	0,764	0,023
		Mínimo	0,679	
Máximo		0,938		
	Amplitude	0,259		
	Stance time R#Ma2	Média	0,764	0,019
		Mínimo	0,689	
Máximo		0,915		
	Amplitude	0,226		
	Stance time R#ER1	Média	0,753	0,017
		Mínimo	0,660	
Máximo		0,856		
	Amplitude	0,196		

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

swing time R (S)#E1	Média	0,439	0,010
	Mínimo	0,373	
	Máximo	0,490	
	Amplitude	0,117	
swing time R #E2	Média	0,445	0,011
	Mínimo	0,392	
	Máximo	0,526	
	Amplitude	0,134	
swing time R#Mo1	Média	0,509	0,026
	Mínimo	0,402	
	Máximo	0,673	
	Amplitude	0,271	
swing time R#Mo2	Média	0,489	0,022
	Mínimo	0,404	
	Máximo	0,631	
	Amplitude	0,227	
swing time R#Ma1	Média	0,475	0,017
	Mínimo	0,384	
	Máximo	0,582	
	Amplitude	0,198	
swing time R#Ma2	Média	0,472	0,016
	Mínimo	0,395	
	Máximo	0,579	
	Amplitude	0,184	
swing time R#ER1	Média	0,438	0,010
	Mínimo	0,368	
	Máximo	0,480	
	Amplitude	0,112	
STEPS PM R #E1	Média	103,156	2,905
	Mínimo	88,605	
	Máximo	119,139	
	Amplitude	30,534	
STEPS PM R #E2	Média	101,406	2,915
	Mínimo	82,407	
	Máximo	119,130	
	Amplitude	36,723	
STEPS PM R#Mo1	Média	96,284	3,628
	Mínimo	79,589	
	Máximo	116,021	

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

	Amplitude	36,432	
STEPS PM R#Mo2	Média	90,731	7,467
	Mínimo	11,016	
	Máximo	114,059	
	Amplitude	103,043	
STEPS PM R#Ma1	Média	99,542	3,217
	Mínimo	79,357	
	Máximo	115,191	
	Amplitude	35,834	
STEPS PM R#Ma2	Média	99,114	2,893
	Mínimo	80,761	
	Máximo	113,058	
	Amplitude	32,297	
STEPS PM R#ER1	Média	104,093	2,811
	Mínimo	88,900	
	Máximo	124,424	
	Amplitude	35,524	
STRIDES PM R #E1	Média	50,434	1,151
	Mínimo	44,305	
	Máximo	56,773	
	Amplitude	12,468	
STRIDES PM R #E2	Média	49,682	1,291
	Mínimo	40,766	
	Máximo	56,355	
	Amplitude	15,589	
STRIDES PM R#Mo1	Média	47,363	1,828
	Mínimo	37,677	
	Máximo	55,395	
	Amplitude	17,718	
STRIDES PM R#Mo2	Média	48,519	1,677
	Mínimo	37,674	
	Máximo	56,015	
	Amplitude	18,341	
STRIDES PM R#Ma1	Média	48,227	1,913
	Mínimo	31,388	
	Máximo	56,372	
	Amplitude	24,984	
STRIDES PM R#Ma2	Média	48,975	1,283
	Mínimo	40,234	

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

STRIDES PM R#ER1	Máximo	55,392	
	Amplitude	15,158	
	Média	50,668	1,097
	Mínimo	44,925	
	Máximo	58,362	
	Amplitude	13,437	

Spatio temporal Variables Friedman's Two-Way Analysis of Variance by Ranks:

Table 7 Friedman test step length

Estatística de teste	9,787 ^a
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,134

Table 8 Friedman test STRIDES PM R

Estatística de teste	12,000 ^a
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,062

Table 9 Friedman test cycle time R

Estatística de teste	11,595 ^a
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,072

Table 10 Friedman test Stance time R

Estatística de teste	11,090 ^a
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,086

Table 11 Friedman test stride width

Estatística de teste	29,133
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	<,001

Table 12 Friedman test step time R

Estatística de teste	19,917
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,003

Table 13 Pairwise comparisons step time R

Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
step time R#ER1-step time R (S)#E1	,346	,847	,409	,683	1,000
step time R#ER1-step time R#Ma2	1,115	,847	1,316	,188	1,000

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

step time R#ER1-step time R#Ma1	1,269	,847	1,498	,134	1,000
step time R#ER1-step time R #E2	2,077	,847	2,451	,014	,299
step time R#ER1-step time R#Mo2	2,500	,847	2,950	,003	,067
step time R#ER1-step time R#Mo1	2,923	,847	3,450	<,001	,012
step time R (S)#E1-step time R#Ma2	-,769	,847	-,908	,364	1,000
step time R (S)#E1-step time R#Ma1	-,923	,847	-1,089	,276	1,000
step time R (S)#E1-step time R #E2	-1,731	,847	-2,043	,041	,863
step time R (S)#E1-step time R#Mo2	-2,154	,847	-2,542	,011	,231
step time R (S)#E1-step time R#Mo1	-2,577	,847	-3,041	,002	,049
step time R#Ma2-step time R#Ma1	,154	,847	,182	,856	1,000
step time R#Ma2-step time R #E2	,962	,847	1,135	,256	1,000
step time R#Ma2-step time R#Mo2	1,385	,847	1,634	,102	1,000
step time R#Ma2-step time R#Mo1	1,808	,847	2,133	,033	,691
step time R#Ma1-step time R #E2	,808	,847	,953	,340	1,000
step time R#Ma1-step time R#Mo2	1,231	,847	1,453	,146	1,000
step time R#Ma1-step time R#Mo1	1,654	,847	1,952	,051	1,000
step time R #E2-step time R#Mo2	-,423	,847	-,499	,618	1,000
step time R #E2-step time R#Mo1	-,846	,847	-,999	,318	1,000
step time R#Mo2-step time R#Mo1	,423	,847	,499	,618	1,000

Table 14 Friedman test swing time R

Estatística de teste	24,407
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	<,001

Table 15 Pairwise comparisons swing time R

Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
swing time R#ER1-swing time R (S)#E1	,231	,847	,272	,785	1,000
swing time R#ER1-swing time R #E2	,654	,847	,772	,440	1,000
swing time R#ER1-swing time R#Ma2	1,308	,847	1,543	,123	1,000
swing time R#ER1-swing time R#Ma1	2,000	,847	2,360	,018	,383
swing time R#ER1-swing time R#Mo2	2,115	,847	2,497	,013	,263
swing time R#ER1-swing time R#Mo1	3,385	,847	3,995	<,001	,001
swing time R (S)#E1-swing time R #E2	-,423	,847	-,499	,618	1,000
swing time R (S)#E1-swing time R#Ma2	-1,077	,847	-1,271	,204	1,000
swing time R (S)#E1-swing time R#Ma1	-1,769	,847	-2,088	,037	,773
swing time R (S)#E1-swing time R#Mo2	-1,885	,847	-2,224	,026	,549
swing time R (S)#E1-swing time R#Mo1	-3,154	,847	-3,722	<,001	,004

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

swing time R #E2-swing time R#Ma2	-,654	,847	-,772	,440	1,000
swing time R #E2-swing time R#Ma1	-1,346	,847	-1,589	,112	1,000
swing time R #E2-swing time R#Mo2	-1,462	,847	-1,725	,085	1,000
swing time R #E2-swing time R#Mo1	-2,731	,847	-3,223	,001	,027
swing time R#Ma2-swing time R#Ma1	,692	,847	,817	,414	1,000
swing time R#Ma2-swing time R#Mo2	,808	,847	,953	,340	1,000
swing time R#Ma2-swing time R#Mo1	2,077	,847	2,451	,014	,299
swing time R#Ma1-swing time R#Mo2	,115	,847	,136	,892	1,000
swing time R#Ma1-swing time R#Mo1	1,385	,847	1,634	,102	1,000
swing time R#Mo2-swing time R#Mo1	1,269	,847	1,498	,134	1,000

Table 16 Friedman test STEPS PM R

Estatística de teste	18,017
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,006

Table 17 Pairwise comparisons STEPS PM R

Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
STEPS PM R#Mo1-STEPS PM R#Mo2	-1,077	,847	-1,271	,204	1,000
STEPS PM R#Mo1-STEPS PM R #E2	1,231	,847	1,453	,146	1,000
STEPS PM R#Mo1-STEPS PM R#Ma1	-1,385	,847	-1,634	,102	1,000
STEPS PM R#Mo1-STEPS PM R#Ma2	-1,423	,847	-1,680	,093	1,000
STEPS PM R#Mo1-STEPS PM R #E1	2,385	,847	2,814	,005	,103
STEPS PM R#Mo1-STEPS PM R#ER1	-3,269	,847	-3,858	<,001	,002
STEPS PM R#Mo2-STEPS PM R #E2	,154	,847	,182	,856	1,000
STEPS PM R#Mo2-STEPS PM R#Ma1	-,308	,847	-,363	,717	1,000
STEPS PM R#Mo2-STEPS PM R#Ma2	-,346	,847	-,409	,683	1,000
STEPS PM R#Mo2-STEPS PM R #E1	1,308	,847	1,543	,123	1,000
STEPS PM R#Mo2-STEPS PM R#ER1	-2,192	,847	-2,587	,010	,203
STEPS PM R #E2-STEPS PM R#Ma1	-,154	,847	-,182	,856	1,000
STEPS PM R #E2-STEPS PM R#Ma2	-,192	,847	-,227	,820	1,000
STEPS PM R #E2-STEPS PM R #E1	1,154	,847	1,362	,173	1,000
STEPS PM R #E2-STEPS PM R#ER1	-2,038	,847	-2,406	,016	,339
STEPS PM R#Ma1-STEPS PM R#Ma2	-,038	,847	-,045	,964	1,000
STEPS PM R#Ma1-STEPS PM R #E1	1,000	,847	1,180	,238	1,000
STEPS PM R#Ma1-STEPS PM R#ER1	-1,885	,847	-2,224	,026	,549
STEPS PM R#Ma2-STEPS PM R #E1	,962	,847	1,135	,256	1,000
STEPS PM R#Ma2-STEPS PM R#ER1	-1,846	,847	-2,179	,029	,616

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STEPS PM R #E1-STEPS PM R#ER1	-,885	,847	-1,044	,296	1,000
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Table 18- Normality Test Joints

Normality Test Joints			
	Shapiro-Wilk		
	statistic	df	Sig
ROM X #E1A	,958	13	,725
ROM X #E2A	,946	13	,534
ROM X#Mo1A	,963	13	,797
ROM X#Mo2A	,915	13	,216
ROM X#Ma1A	,933	13	,373
ROM X#Ma2A	,865	13	,045
ROM X#ER1A	,934	13	,384
ROM Y #E1A	,956	13	,693
ROM Y #E2A	,941	13	,464
ROM Y#Mo1A	,946	13	,540
ROM Y#Mo2A	,880	13	,070
ROM Y#Ma1A	,933	13	,375
ROM Y#Ma2A	,926	13	,302
ROM Y#ER1A	,952	13	,631
ROM Z #E1A	,950	13	,601
ROM Z #E2A	,972	13	,917
ROM Z#Mo1A	,970	13	,897
ROM Z#Mo2A	,933	13	,377
ROM Z#Ma1A	,939	13	,444
ROM Z#Ma2A	,848	13	,027
ROM Z#ER1A	,983	13	,990
ROM Y flx/ext #E1K	,896	13	,119
ROM Y flx/ext #E2K	,968	13	,864
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo1K	,985	13	,996
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo2K	,966	13	,844
ROM Y flx/ext#Ma1K	,890	13	,098
ROM Y flx/ext#Ma2K	,987	13	,998
ROM Y flx/ext#ER1K	,954	13	,660
ROM X abd/add #E1K	,916	13	,223
ROM X abd/add #E2K	,897	13	,121
ROM X abd/add#Mo1K	,912	13	,196
ROM X abd/add#Mo2K	,947	13	,549
ROM X abd/add#Ma1K	,917	13	,232
ROM X abd/add#Ma2K	,913	13	,201
ROM X abd/add#ER1K	,921	13	,260

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ROM Z int/ext rot #E1K	,958	13	,729
ROM Z int/ext rot #E2K	,526	13	,000
ROM Z int/ext rot#Mo1K	,731	13	,001
ROM Z int/ext rot#Mo2K	,985	13	,996
ROM Z int/ext rot#Ma1K	,557	13	,000
ROM Z int/ext rot#Ma2K	,954	13	,666
ROM Z int/ext rot#ER1K	,812	13	,009
ROM X #E1H	,820	13	,012
ROM X #E2H	,939	13	,439
ROM X#Mo1H	,905	13	,155
ROM X#Mo2H	,969	13	,880
ROM X#Ma1H	,962	13	,786
ROM X#Ma2H	,959	13	,745
ROM X#ER1H	,965	13	,831
ROM Y - flex/ext #E1H	,956	13	,690
ROM Y - flex/ext #E2H	,835	13	,018
ROM Y - flex/ext#Mo1H	,946	13	,542
ROM Y - flex/ext#Mo2H	,934	13	,387
ROM Y - flex/ext#Ma1H	,953	13	,651
ROM Y - flex/ext#Ma2H	,874	13	,059
ROM Y - flex/ext#ER1H	,880	13	,070
ROM Z #E1H	,923	13	,276
ROM Z#E2H	,902	13	,141
ROM Z#Mo1H	,939	13	,438
ROM Z #Mo2H	,938	13	,428
ROM Z#Ma1H	,982	13	,987
ROM Z#Ma2H	,952	13	,634
ROM Z#ER1H	,924	13	,282
max X - supination peak #E1A	,883	13	,078
max X - supination peak #E2A	,964	13	,810
max X - supination peak#Mo1A	,932	13	,367
max X - supination peak#Mo2A	,903	13	,149
max X - supination peak#Ma1A	,950	13	,594
max X - supination peak#Ma2A	,951	13	,608
max X - supination peak#ER1A	,984	13	,994
min x - pronation peak #E1A	,951	13	,609
min x - pronation peak #E2A	,938	13	,433
min x - pronation peak#Mo1A	,921	13	,259
min x - pronation peak#Mo2A	,922	13	,264
min x - pronation peak#Ma1A	,880	13	,072
min x - pronation peak#Ma2A	,902	13	,142
min x - pronation peak#ER1A	,942	13	,482

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max y - dorsiflexion peak #E1A	,934	13	,379
max y - dorsiflexion peak #E2A	,664	13	,000
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Mo1A	,929	13	,332
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Mo2A	,986	13	,997
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Ma1A	,914	13	,206
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Ma2A	,951	13	,621
max y - dorsiflexion peak#ER1A	,955	13	,680
min y - Plantar Flexion peak #E1A	,911	13	,188
min y - Plantar Flexion peak #E2A	,934	13	,380
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Mo1A	,952	13	,632
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Mo2A	,926	13	,302
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Ma1A	,930	13	,343
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Ma2A	,907	13	,167
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#ER1A	,883	13	,077
max z - ext rotation peak #E1A	,960	13	,753
max z - ext rotation peak #E2A	,967	13	,852
max z - ext rotation peak#Mo1A	,990	13	1,000
max z - ext rotation peak#Mo2A	,945	13	,518
max z - ext rotation peak#Ma1A	,978	13	,966
max z - ext rotation peak#Ma2A	,916	13	,223
max z - ext rotation peak#ER1A	,942	13	,485
min z - int rotation peak #E1A	,937	13	,418
min z - int rotation peak #E2A	,830	13	,016
min z - int rotation peak#Mo1A	,784	13	,004
min z - int rotation peak#Mo2A	,730	13	,001
min z - int rotation peak#Ma1A	,801	13	,007
min z - int rotation peak#Ma2A	,775	13	,004
min z - int rotation peak#ER1A	,852	13	,030
max x - abd/add #E1K	,978	13	,970
max x - abd/add #E2K	,774	13	,003
max x - abd/add#Mo1K	,910	13	,181
max x - abd/add#Mo2K	,953	13	,649
max x - abd/add#Ma1K	,930	13	,338
max x - abd/add#Ma2K	,938	13	,427
max x - abd/add#ER1K	,954	13	,665
min x - abd/add #E1K	,936	13	,412
min x - abd/add #E2K	,977	13	,962
min x - abd/add#Mo1K	,909	13	,177
min x - abd/add#Mo2K	,969	13	,887
min x - abd/add#Ma1K	,941	13	,464
min x - abd/add#Ma2K	,944	13	,505
min x - abd/add#ER1K	,925	13	,297

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1st flexion peak#E1K	,934	13	,390
1st flexion peak #E2K	,900	13	,135
1st flexion peak#Mo1K	,773	13	,003
1st flexion peak#Mo2K	,805	13	,008
1st flexion peak#Ma1K	,942	13	,481
1st flexion peak#Ma2K	,894	13	,112
1st flexion peak#ER1K	,948	13	,573
2nd flexion peak#E1K	,896	13	,119
2nd flexion peak #E2K	,940	13	,451
2nd flexion peak#Mo1K	,933	13	,369
2nd flexion peak#Mo2K	,931	13	,352
2nd flexion peak#Ma1K	,921	13	,261
2nd flexion peak#Ma2K	,985	13	,995
2nd flexion peak#ER1K	,953	13	,642
min y - extension peak #E1K	,856	13	,034
min y - extension peak #E2K	,556	13	,000
min y - extension peak#Mo1K	,833	13	,017
min y - extension peak#Mo2K	,644	13	,000
min y - extension peak#Ma1K	,908	13	,175
min y - extension peak#Ma2K	,837	13	,019
min y - extension peak#ER1K	,682	13	,000
max z - int rot peak #E1K	,908	13	,172
max z - int rot peak #E2K	,914	13	,205
max z - int rot peak#Mo1K	,877	13	,065
max z - int rot peak#Mo2K	,950	13	,602
max z - int rot peak#Ma1K	,896	13	,117
max z - int rot peak#Ma2K	,945	13	,531
max z - int rot peak#ER1K	,745	13	,002
min z - ext rot peak #E1K	,920	13	,250
min z - ext rot peak #E2K	,857	13	,035
min z - ext rot peak#Mo1K	,938	13	,438
min z - ext rot peak#Mo2K	,964	13	,807
min z - ext rot peak#Ma1K	,977	13	,958
min z - ext rot peak#Ma2K	,937	13	,424
min z - ext rot peak#ER1K	,916	13	,225
max x - adduction peak #E1H	,936	13	,403
max x - adduction peak #E2H	,944	13	,508
max x - adduction peak#Mo1H	,896	13	,119
max x - adduction peak#Mo2H	,914	13	,208
max x - adduction peak#Ma1H	,958	13	,717
max x - adduction peak#Ma2H	,929	13	,332
max x - adduction peak#ER1H	,943	13	,491

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min x - abd peak #E1H	,854	13	,032
min x - abd peak #E2H	,838	13	,020
min x - abd peak#Mo1H	,931	13	,353
min x - abd peak#Mo2H	,856	13	,035
min x - abd peak#Ma1H	,932	13	,361
min x - abd peak#Ma2H	,962	13	,791
min x - abd peak#ER1H	,934	13	,380
max y - flexion peak #E1H	,939	13	,439
max y - flexion peak #E2H	,926	13	,299
max y - flexion peak#Mo1H	,880	13	,070
max y - flexion peak#Mo2H	,914	13	,206
max y - flexion peak#Ma1H	,809	13	,009
max y - flexion peak#Ma2H	,948	13	,568
max y - flexion peak#ER1H	,915	13	,214
min y - extension peak #E1H	,900	13	,134
min y - extension peak #E2H	,825	13	,014
min y - extension peak#Mo1H	,925	13	,295
min y - extension peak#Mo2H	,895	13	,115
min y - extension peak#Ma1H	,924	13	,286
min y - extension peak#Ma2H	,932	13	,361
min y - extension peak#ER1H	,756	13	,002
max z - int rotation peak #E1H	,865	13	,045
max z - int rotation peak #E2H	,840	13	,021
max z - int rotation peak#Mo1H	,905	13	,157
max z - int rotation peak#Mo2H	,907	13	,166
max z - int rotation peak#Ma1H	,982	13	,986
max z - int rotation peak#Ma2H	,932	13	,365
max z - int rotation peak#ER1H	,792	13	,005
min z - ext rot peak #E1H	,815	13	,010
min z - ext rot peak #E2H	,922	13	,263
min z - ext rot peak#Mo1H	,930	13	,346
min z - ext rot peak#Mo2H	,980	13	,977
min z - ext rot peak#Ma1H	,934	13	,379
min z - ext rot peak#Ma2H	,974	13	,937
min z - ext rot peak#ER1H	,922	13	,263

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Table 19- Joint kinematics descriptive's

Joint Descriptives		Estadística	Estadística do teste Padrão
ROM X #E1A	Média	24,330	1,185
	Mínimo	16,673	
	Máximo	30,511	
	Amplitude	13,838	
ROM X #E2A	Média	22,889	1,851
	Mínimo	8,375	
	Máximo	31,661	
	Amplitude	23,285	
ROM X#Mo1A	Média	24,639	1,707
	Mínimo	15,377	
	Máximo	36,966	
	Amplitude	21,589	
ROM X#Mo2A	Média	23,704	1,508
	Mínimo	12,497	
	Máximo	34,530	
	Amplitude	22,033	
ROM X#Ma1A	Média	23,930	1,661
	Mínimo	16,669	
	Máximo	37,611	
	Amplitude	20,942	
ROM X#Ma2A	Média	22,241	1,289
	Mínimo	12,976	
	Máximo	28,219	
	Amplitude	15,243	
ROM X#ER1A	Média	23,421	1,322
	Mínimo	16,022	
	Máximo	29,904	
	Amplitude	13,882	
ROM Y #E1A	Média	32,063	1,965
	Mínimo	22,649	
	Máximo	45,209	
	Amplitude	22,560	
ROM Y #E2A	Média	35,542	3,041
	Mínimo	20,269	
	Máximo	60,705	
	Amplitude	40,436	
ROM Y#Mo1A	Média	35,033	2,601
	Mínimo	20,605	

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	Máximo	49,715	
	Amplitude	29,110	
ROM Y#Mo2A	Média	34,609	2,356
	Mínimo	17,046	
	Máximo	43,967	
	Amplitude	26,921	
ROM Y#Ma1A	Média	33,549	2,026
	Mínimo	21,752	
	Máximo	45,713	
	Amplitude	23,961	
ROM Y#Ma2A	Média	33,761	2,020
	Mínimo	21,575	
	Máximo	44,572	
	Amplitude	22,996	
ROM Y#ER1A	Média	33,397	1,370
	Mínimo	26,502	
	Máximo	41,730	
	Amplitude	15,228	
ROM Z #E1A	Média	24,810	1,475
	Mínimo	16,884	
	Máximo	34,091	
	Amplitude	17,207	
ROM Z #E2A	Média	23,308	1,141
	Mínimo	16,300	
	Máximo	31,015	
	Amplitude	14,714	
ROM Z#Mo1A	Média	22,088	1,516
	Mínimo	13,486	
	Máximo	32,833	
	Amplitude	19,347	
ROM Z#Mo2A	Média	20,868	1,588
	Mínimo	12,984	
	Máximo	33,625	
	Amplitude	20,641	
ROM Z#Ma1A	Média	21,074	1,241
	Mínimo	13,783	
	Máximo	29,269	
	Amplitude	15,486	

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ROM Z#Ma2A	Média	20,848	1,579
	Mínimo	14,841	
	Máximo	36,030	
	Amplitude	21,189	
ROM Z#ER1A	Média	24,938	1,521
	Mínimo	15,749	
	Máximo	36,366	
	Amplitude	20,617	
ROM Y flx/ext #E1K	Média	67,235	1,733
	Mínimo	57,536	
	Máximo	83,215	
	Amplitude	25,679	
ROM Y flx/ext #E2K	Média	65,588	1,767
	Mínimo	55,545	
	Máximo	79,857	
	Amplitude	24,313	
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo1K	Média	56,202	2,012
	Mínimo	42,470	
	Máximo	70,461	
	Amplitude	27,992	
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo2K	Média	55,202	1,203
	Mínimo	47,739	
	Máximo	63,213	
	Amplitude	15,474	
ROM Y flx/ext#Ma1K	Média	57,957	1,822
	Mínimo	43,991	
	Máximo	65,976	
	Amplitude	21,985	
ROM Y flx/ext#Ma2K	Média	58,788	1,797
	Mínimo	47,371	
	Máximo	71,415	
	Amplitude	24,045	
ROM Y flx/ext#ER1K	Média	65,986	2,008
	Mínimo	54,876	
	Máximo	82,303	
	Amplitude	27,427	
ROM X abd/add #E1K	Média	16,550	1,856
	Mínimo	8,886	

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	Máximo	28,948	
	Amplitude	20,062	
ROM X abd/add #E2K	Média	16,769	2,176
	Mínimo	7,951	
	Máximo	30,511	
	Amplitude	22,560	
ROM X abd/add#Mo1K	Média	16,673	2,554
	Mínimo	5,771	
	Máximo	35,610	
	Amplitude	29,839	
ROM X abd/add#Mo2K	Média	15,545	2,068
	Mínimo	5,498	
	Máximo	29,234	
	Amplitude	23,736	
ROM X abd/add#Ma1K	Média	15,618	1,982
	Mínimo	6,370	
	Máximo	29,955	
	Amplitude	23,585	
ROM X abd/add#Ma2K	Média	15,205	2,108
	Mínimo	5,469	
	Máximo	28,376	
	Amplitude	22,908	
ROM X abd/add#ER1K	Média	16,305	2,017
	Mínimo	7,664	
	Máximo	29,307	
	Amplitude	21,644	
ROM Z int/ext rot #E1K	Média	21,591	0,866
	Mínimo	15,882	
	Máximo	25,827	
	Amplitude	9,944	
ROM Z int/ext rot #E2K	Média	19,145	3,087
	Mínimo	-16,723	
	Máximo	25,485	
	Amplitude	42,207	
ROM Z int/ext rot#Mo1K	Média	15,681	3,801
	Mínimo	-25,611	
	Máximo	31,436	
	Amplitude	57,047	

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ROM Z int/ext rot#Mo2K	Média	19,941	1,322
	Mínimo	11,779	
	Máximo	28,778	
	Amplitude	16,998	
ROM Z int/ext rot#Ma1K	Média	16,908	3,552
	Mínimo	-24,303	
	Máximo	25,895	
	Amplitude	50,198	
ROM Z int/ext rot#Ma2K	Média	19,903	1,102
	Mínimo	12,202	
	Máximo	27,947	
	Amplitude	15,745	
ROM Z int/ext rot#ER1K	Média	20,955	1,768
	Mínimo	3,278	
	Máximo	27,298	
	Amplitude	24,020	
ROM X #E1H	Média	13,893	0,733
	Mínimo	10,355	
	Máximo	21,400	
	Amplitude	11,045	
ROM X #E2H	Média	13,874	0,581
	Mínimo	11,098	
	Máximo	18,609	
	Amplitude	7,510	
ROM X#Mo1H	Média	13,740	0,536
	Mínimo	9,081	
	Máximo	15,918	
	Amplitude	6,837	
ROM X#Mo2H	Média	12,199	0,854
	Mínimo	6,111	
	Máximo	17,976	
	Amplitude	11,865	
ROM X#Ma1H	Média	11,602	1,066
	Mínimo	3,943	
	Máximo	18,590	
	Amplitude	14,648	
ROM X#Ma2H	Média	11,121	0,873
	Mínimo	4,628	

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	Máximo	16,697	
	Amplitude	12,069	
ROM X#ER1H	Média	13,458	0,761
	Mínimo	7,949	
	Máximo	17,359	
	Amplitude	9,410	
ROM Y - flex/ext #E1H	Média	40,454	1,491
	Mínimo	29,524	
	Máximo	47,690	
	Amplitude	18,166	
ROM Y - flex/ext #E2H	Média	40,559	2,311
	Mínimo	18,763	
	Máximo	48,613	
	Amplitude	29,851	
ROM Y - flex/ext#Mo1H	Média	32,623	2,001
	Mínimo	21,550	
	Máximo	43,948	
	Amplitude	22,398	
ROM Y - flex/ext#Mo2H	Média	33,511	1,798
	Mínimo	22,836	
	Máximo	42,795	
	Amplitude	19,959	
ROM Y - flex/ext#Ma1H	Média	33,630	1,658
	Mínimo	21,066	
	Máximo	41,178	
	Amplitude	20,113	
ROM Y - flex/ext#Ma2H	Média	34,594	2,183
	Mínimo	17,940	
	Máximo	42,576	
	Amplitude	24,636	
ROM Y - flex/ext#ER1H	Média	38,835	1,737
	Mínimo	22,107	
	Máximo	47,542	
	Amplitude	25,435	
ROM Z #E1H	Média	15,169	1,173
	Mínimo	8,950	
	Máximo	24,948	
	Amplitude	15,998	

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

ROM Z#E2H	Média	15,589	1,038
	Mínimo	9,190	
	Máximo	21,298	
	Amplitude	12,107	
ROM Z#Mo1H	Média	14,941	1,329
	Mínimo	6,747	
	Máximo	21,103	
	Amplitude	14,356	
ROM Z #Mo2H	Média	14,309	1,234
	Mínimo	7,504	
	Máximo	21,020	
	Amplitude	13,516	
ROM Z#Ma1H	Média	13,996	1,404
	Mínimo	5,522	
	Máximo	23,557	
	Amplitude	18,035	
ROM Z#Ma2H	Média	14,093	1,057
	Mínimo	6,934	
	Máximo	19,991	
	Amplitude	13,057	
ROM Z#ER1H	Média	16,685	1,265
	Mínimo	10,851	
	Máximo	25,971	
	Amplitude	15,121	
max X - supination peak #E1A	Média	20,670	1,891
	Mínimo	13,194	
	Máximo	36,638	
	Amplitude	23,444	
max X - supination peak #E2A	Média	18,617	2,054
	Mínimo	7,483	
	Máximo	35,080	
	Amplitude	27,597	
max X - supination peak#Mo1A	Média	24,583	1,924
	Mínimo	15,912	
	Máximo	38,170	
	Amplitude	22,258	
max X - supination peak#Mo2A	Média	23,561	1,853
	Mínimo	15,399	

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

	Máximo	35,535	
	Amplitude	20,136	
max X - supination peak#Ma1A	Média	23,626	1,924
	Mínimo	14,504	
	Máximo	38,371	
	Amplitude	23,868	
max X - supination peak#Ma2A	Média	21,369	1,647
	Mínimo	13,395	
	Máximo	31,930	
	Amplitude	18,534	
max X - supination peak#ER1A	Média	18,729	2,040
	Mínimo	5,821	
	Máximo	33,069	
	Amplitude	27,249	
min x - pronation peak #E1A	Média	-4,356	1,470
	Mínimo	-11,790	
	Máximo	6,168	
	Amplitude	17,958	
min x - pronation peak #E2A	Média	-4,272	1,370
	Mínimo	-11,790	
	Máximo	3,419	
	Amplitude	15,209	
min x - pronation peak#Mo1A	Média	-0,055	1,503
	Mínimo	-11,321	
	Máximo	10,282	
	Amplitude	21,603	
min x - pronation peak#Mo2A	Média	-0,143	1,350
	Mínimo	-9,859	
	Máximo	10,039	
	Amplitude	19,899	
min x - pronation peak#Ma1A	Média	-0,304	1,586
	Mínimo	-6,895	
	Máximo	12,319	
	Amplitude	19,214	
min x - pronation peak#Ma2A	Média	-0,872	1,462
	Mínimo	-7,386	
	Máximo	9,955	
	Amplitude	17,341	

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

min x - pronation peak#ER1A	Média	-4,692	1,960
	Mínimo	-17,485	
	Máximo	8,518	
	Amplitude	26,004	
max y - dorsiflexion peak #E1A	Média	16,902	1,144
	Mínimo	11,100	
	Máximo	23,152	
	Amplitude	12,053	
max y - dorsiflexion peak #E2A	Média	20,358	3,492
	Mínimo	10,171	
	Máximo	59,282	
	Amplitude	49,112	
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Mo1A	Média	14,955	1,269
	Mínimo	3,702	
	Máximo	22,642	
	Amplitude	18,940	
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Mo2A	Média	14,213	1,276
	Mínimo	4,962	
	Máximo	22,053	
	Amplitude	17,091	
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Ma1A	Média	13,975	1,110
	Mínimo	9,105	
	Máximo	21,882	
	Amplitude	12,777	
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Ma2A	Média	14,855	1,300
	Mínimo	7,994	
	Máximo	23,099	
	Amplitude	15,105	
max y - dorsiflexion peak#ER1A	Média	18,704	1,696
	Mínimo	5,701	
	Máximo	27,947	
	Amplitude	22,246	
min y - Plantar Flexion peak #E1A	Média	-15,458	2,095
	Mínimo	-31,330	
	Máximo	-7,427	
	Amplitude	23,903	
min y - Plantar Flexion peak #E2A	Média	-15,183	2,211
	Mínimo	-25,694	

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

	Máximo	-1,423	
	Amplitude	24,272	
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Mo1A	Média	-20,077	2,679
	Mínimo	-33,444	
	Máximo	-2,129	
	Amplitude	31,314	
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Mo2A	Média	-20,396	2,535
	Mínimo	-32,267	
	Máximo	-3,227	
	Amplitude	29,040	
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Ma1A	Média	-19,574	2,241
	Mínimo	-29,889	
	Máximo	-5,735	
	Amplitude	24,154	
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Ma2A	Média	-18,906	2,343
	Mínimo	-31,343	
	Máximo	-7,053	
	Amplitude	24,290	
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#ER1A	Média	-14,694	2,168
	Mínimo	-24,750	
	Máximo	-4,441	
	Amplitude	20,309	
max z - ext rotation peak #E1A	Média	19,368	2,198
	Mínimo	2,107	
	Máximo	32,935	
	Amplitude	30,829	
max z - ext rotation peak #E2A	Média	16,805	2,358
	Mínimo	3,240	
	Máximo	31,536	
	Amplitude	28,297	
max z - ext rotation peak#Mo1A	Média	19,227	2,219
	Mínimo	3,502	
	Máximo	34,001	
	Amplitude	30,499	
max z - ext rotation peak#Mo2A	Média	18,462	2,392
	Mínimo	3,683	
	Máximo	34,705	
	Amplitude	31,022	

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

max z - ext rotation peak#Ma1A	Média	18,391	2,092
	Mínimo	4,035	
	Máximo	30,135	
	Amplitude	26,100	
max z - ext rotation peak#Ma2A	Média	17,780	1,924
	Mínimo	6,651	
	Máximo	34,721	
	Amplitude	28,070	
max z - ext rotation peak#ER1A	Média	19,862	2,362
	Mínimo	6,960	
	Máximo	36,339	
	Amplitude	29,378	
min z - int rotation peak #E1A	Média	-5,902	1,289
	Mínimo	-16,706	
	Máximo	0,879	
	Amplitude	17,585	
min z - int rotation peak #E2A	Média	-6,503	1,846
	Mínimo	-21,310	
	Máximo	0,699	
	Amplitude	22,008	
min z - int rotation peak#Mo1A	Média	-2,860	1,657
	Mínimo	-19,641	
	Máximo	3,723	
	Amplitude	23,364	
min z - int rotation peak#Mo2A	Média	-2,406	1,471
	Mínimo	-18,236	
	Máximo	2,918	
	Amplitude	21,154	
min z - int rotation peak#Ma1A	Média	-2,683	1,541
	Mínimo	-18,527	
	Máximo	3,363	
	Amplitude	21,890	
min z - int rotation peak#Ma2A	Média	-3,067	1,553
	Mínimo	-19,508	
	Máximo	3,237	
	Amplitude	22,745	
min z - int rotation peak#ER1A	Média	-5,076	1,594
	Mínimo	-20,274	

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

	Máximo	0,853	
	Amplitude	21,127	
max x - abd/add #E1K	Média	4,405	0,808
	Mínimo	-0,271	
	Máximo	9,487	
	Amplitude	9,758	
max x - abd/add #E2K	Média	5,120	1,303
	Mínimo	0,637	
	Máximo	18,721	
	Amplitude	18,083	
max x - abd/add#Mo1K	Média	6,534	1,115
	Mínimo	1,428	
	Máximo	15,912	
	Amplitude	14,484	
max x - abd/add#Mo2K	Média	6,229	1,028
	Mínimo	1,108	
	Máximo	14,250	
	Amplitude	13,142	
max x - abd/add#Ma1K	Média	6,024	1,090
	Mínimo	0,867	
	Máximo	15,333	
	Amplitude	14,466	
max x - abd/add#Ma2K	Média	5,719	1,053
	Mínimo	0,489	
	Máximo	14,431	
	Amplitude	13,942	
max x - abd/add#ER1K	Média	4,219	0,718
	Mínimo	-0,247	
	Máximo	7,842	
	Amplitude	8,089	
min x - abd/add #E1K	Média	-12,145	2,126
	Mínimo	-25,439	
	Máximo	-2,053	
	Amplitude	23,386	
min x - abd/add #E2K	Média	-11,648	1,903
	Mínimo	-24,927	
	Máximo	-0,892	
	Amplitude	24,035	

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

min x - abd/add#Mo1K	Média	-10,140	2,364
	Mínimo	-31,343	
	Máximo	0,177	
	Amplitude	31,519	
min x - abd/add#Mo2K	Média	-9,317	2,004
	Mínimo	-23,321	
	Máximo	0,796	
	Amplitude	24,117	
min x - abd/add#Ma1K	Média	-9,594	1,765
	Mínimo	-20,994	
	Máximo	-0,479	
	Amplitude	20,515	
min x - abd/add#Ma2K	Média	-9,486	1,901
	Mínimo	-22,127	
	Máximo	-0,424	
	Amplitude	21,703	
min x - abd/add#ER1K	Média	-12,086	2,237
	Mínimo	-25,489	
	Máximo	-1,367	
	Amplitude	24,122	
1st flexion peak#E1K	Média	15,229	1,934
	Mínimo	4,253	
	Máximo	24,524	
	Amplitude	20,270	
1st flexion peak #E2K	Média	20,901	2,694
	Mínimo	5,100	
	Máximo	31,932	
	Amplitude	26,832	
1st flexion peak#Mo1K	Média	19,676	1,960
	Mínimo	11,591	
	Máximo	38,558	
	Amplitude	26,966	
1st flexion peak#Mo2K	Média	19,037	2,163
	Mínimo	11,325	
	Máximo	40,629	
	Amplitude	29,304	
1st flexion peak#Ma1K	Média	17,424	1,831
	Mínimo	8,400	

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

	Máximo	30,848	
	Amplitude	22,448	
1st flexion peak#Ma2K	Média	17,639	1,217
	Mínimo	12,499	
	Máximo	25,282	
	Amplitude	12,784	
1st flexion peak#ER1K	Média	17,992	1,842
	Mínimo	4,897	
	Máximo	26,382	
	Amplitude	21,485	
2nd flexion peak#E1K	Média	65,762	1,966
	Mínimo	57,301	
	Máximo	83,961	
	Amplitude	26,660	
2nd flexion peak #E2K	Média	65,105	1,818
	Mínimo	55,865	
	Máximo	80,455	
	Amplitude	24,589	
2nd flexion peak#Mo1K	Média	56,317	1,758
	Mínimo	42,937	
	Máximo	70,761	
	Amplitude	27,824	
2nd flexion peak#Mo2K	Média	55,446	1,236
	Mínimo	48,225	
	Máximo	64,575	
	Amplitude	16,350	
2nd flexion peak#Ma1K	Média	58,369	1,588
	Mínimo	48,571	
	Máximo	66,874	
	Amplitude	18,302	
2nd flexion peak#Ma2K	Média	59,084	1,876
	Mínimo	46,239	
	Máximo	72,240	
	Amplitude	26,001	
2nd flexion peak#ER1K	Média	64,936	2,431
	Mínimo	45,579	
	Máximo	82,905	
	Amplitude	37,326	

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

min y - extension peak #E1K	Média	-1,473	0,718
	Mínimo	-7,458	
	Máximo	0,960	
	Amplitude	8,418	
min y - extension peak #E2K	Média	-0,482	0,959
	Mínimo	-11,550	
	Máximo	1,523	
	Amplitude	13,072	
min y - extension peak#Mo1K	Média	0,115	0,800
	Mínimo	-5,946	
	Máximo	4,102	
	Amplitude	10,047	
min y - extension peak#Mo2K	Média	0,245	0,749
	Mínimo	-8,096	
	Máximo	2,438	
	Amplitude	10,534	
min y - extension peak#Ma1K	Média	0,411	0,920
	Mínimo	-6,921	
	Máximo	6,496	
	Amplitude	13,417	
min y - extension peak#Ma2K	Média	0,295	0,698
	Mínimo	-5,040	
	Máximo	4,395	
	Amplitude	9,435	
min y - extension peak#ER1K	Média	-1,050	0,817
	Mínimo	-9,297	
	Máximo	0,935	
	Amplitude	10,232	
max z - int rot peak #E1K	Média	2,846	0,862
	Mínimo	-4,633	
	Máximo	6,674	
	Amplitude	11,308	
max z - int rot peak #E2K	Média	4,148	1,245
	Mínimo	-2,435	
	Máximo	15,511	
	Amplitude	17,946	
max z - int rot peak#Mo1K	Média	0,324	1,572
	Mínimo	-13,132	

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

	Máximo	6,693	
	Amplitude	19,825	
max z - int rot peak#Mo2K	Média	1,376	1,193
	Mínimo	-6,631	
	Máximo	9,379	
	Amplitude	16,010	
max z - int rot peak#Ma1K	Média	1,000	1,086
	Mínimo	-5,626	
	Máximo	8,508	
	Amplitude	14,134	
max z - int rot peak#Ma2K	Média	1,235	1,075
	Mínimo	-5,919	
	Máximo	8,038	
	Amplitude	13,956	
max z - int rot peak#ER1K	Média	1,429	1,624
	Mínimo	-15,103	
	Máximo	6,899	
	Amplitude	22,002	
min z - ext rot peak #E1K	Média	-18,626	1,075
	Mínimo	-23,381	
	Máximo	-9,764	
	Amplitude	13,617	
min z - ext rot peak #E2K	Média	-17,430	1,472
	Mínimo	-24,042	
	Máximo	-5,015	
	Amplitude	19,027	
min z - ext rot peak#Mo1K	Média	-18,217	1,590
	Mínimo	-26,379	
	Máximo	-9,482	
	Amplitude	16,897	
min z - ext rot peak#Mo2K	Média	-18,565	1,586
	Mínimo	-26,530	
	Máximo	-7,702	
	Amplitude	18,828	
min z - ext rot peak#Ma1K	Média	-18,801	1,259
	Mínimo	-25,622	
	Máximo	-9,249	
	Amplitude	16,373	

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

min z - ext rot peak#Ma2K	Média	-18,667	1,170
	Mínimo	-26,039	
	Máximo	-9,702	
	Amplitude	16,336	
min z - ext rot peak#ER1K	Média	-19,527	1,209
	Mínimo	-24,626	
	Máximo	-9,544	
	Amplitude	15,082	
max x - adduction peak #E1H	Média	5,617	0,949
	Mínimo	-0,684	
	Máximo	10,621	
	Amplitude	11,305	
max x - adduction peak #E2H	Média	5,598	1,082
	Mínimo	-2,109	
	Máximo	11,590	
	Amplitude	13,698	
max x - adduction peak#Mo1H	Média	3,090	1,058
	Mínimo	-3,468	
	Máximo	10,719	
	Amplitude	14,186	
max x - adduction peak#Mo2H	Média	2,568	0,925
	Mínimo	-4,650	
	Máximo	7,476	
	Amplitude	12,126	
max x - adduction peak#Ma1H	Média	2,928	1,256
	Mínimo	-6,553	
	Máximo	9,965	
	Amplitude	16,517	
max x - adduction peak#Ma2H	Média	2,701	1,069
	Mínimo	-5,648	
	Máximo	8,412	
	Amplitude	14,061	
max x - adduction peak#ER1H	Média	5,807	0,914
	Mínimo	-0,305	
	Máximo	10,343	
	Amplitude	10,648	
min x - abd peak #E1H	Média	-8,276	1,028
	Mínimo	-12,961	

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

	Máximo	-3,747	
	Amplitude	9,213	
min x - abd peak #E2H	Média	-8,277	1,277
	Mínimo	-20,717	
	Máximo	-3,176	
	Amplitude	17,541	
min x - abd peak#Mo1H	Média	-10,650	1,321
	Mínimo	-19,386	
	Máximo	-0,856	
	Amplitude	18,529	
min x - abd peak#Mo2H	Média	-9,632	0,940
	Mínimo	-12,822	
	Máximo	-1,256	
	Amplitude	11,565	
min x - abd peak#Ma1H	Média	-8,675	0,937
	Mínimo	-13,489	
	Máximo	-0,578	
	Amplitude	12,910	
min x - abd peak#Ma2H	Média	-8,420	0,835
	Mínimo	-13,571	
	Máximo	-1,928	
	Amplitude	11,644	
min x - abd peak#ER1H	Média	-7,651	1,088
	Mínimo	-13,463	
	Máximo	-1,279	
	Amplitude	12,184	
max y - flexion peak #E1H	Média	27,257	2,079
	Mínimo	17,023	
	Máximo	44,803	
	Amplitude	27,781	
max y - flexion peak #E2H	Média	30,869	2,188
	Mínimo	19,177	
	Máximo	49,421	
	Amplitude	30,245	
max y - flexion peak#Mo1H	Média	21,089	3,206
	Mínimo	4,880	
	Máximo	45,149	
	Amplitude	40,268	

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

max y - flexion peak#Mo2H	Média	22,178	3,208
	Mínimo	5,223	
	Máximo	43,973	
	Amplitude	38,750	
max y - flexion peak#Ma1H	Média	20,862	3,077
	Mínimo	9,313	
	Máximo	41,597	
	Amplitude	32,284	
max y - flexion peak#Ma2H	Média	22,125	3,177
	Mínimo	5,704	
	Máximo	43,446	
	Amplitude	37,741	
max y - flexion peak#ER1H	Média	25,300	2,323
	Mínimo	8,774	
	Máximo	45,610	
	Amplitude	36,836	
min y - extension peak #E1H	Média	-13,196	1,605
	Mínimo	-20,660	
	Máximo	0,899	
	Amplitude	21,559	
min y - extension peak #E2H	Média	-9,690	2,508
	Mínimo	-19,614	
	Máximo	14,686	
	Amplitude	34,299	
min y - extension peak#Mo1H	Média	-11,534	2,556
	Mínimo	-24,174	
	Máximo	2,053	
	Amplitude	26,227	
min y - extension peak#Mo2H	Média	-11,333	2,384
	Mínimo	-21,733	
	Máximo	1,628	
	Amplitude	23,361	
min y - extension peak#Ma1H	Média	-12,767	2,226
	Mínimo	-23,089	
	Máximo	1,186	
	Amplitude	24,275	
min y - extension peak#Ma2H	Média	-12,469	1,797
	Mínimo	-21,581	

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

	Máximo	1,093	
	Amplitude	22,674	
min y - extension peak#ER1H	Média	-10,632	2,891
	Mínimo	-20,155	
	Máximo	18,873	
	Amplitude	39,028	
max z - int rotation peak #E1H	Média	3,981	1,401
	Mínimo	-2,900	
	Máximo	12,984	
	Amplitude	15,884	
max z - int rotation peak #E2H	Média	2,888	1,624
	Mínimo	-10,842	
	Máximo	14,311	
	Amplitude	25,152	
max z - int rotation peak#Mo1H	Média	4,750	1,226
	Mínimo	-5,672	
	Máximo	9,868	
	Amplitude	15,540	
max z - int rotation peak#Mo2H	Média	5,691	1,002
	Mínimo	-2,392	
	Máximo	9,502	
	Amplitude	11,893	
max z - int rotation peak#Ma1H	Média	6,148	0,706
	Mínimo	1,075	
	Máximo	10,755	
	Amplitude	9,680	
max z - int rotation peak#Ma2H	Média	6,027	0,596
	Mínimo	1,146	
	Máximo	9,074	
	Amplitude	7,928	
max z - int rotation peak#ER1H	Média	5,258	1,112
	Mínimo	1,590	
	Máximo	13,097	
	Amplitude	11,508	
min z - ext rot peak #E1H	Média	-8,774	2,492
	Mínimo	-20,145	
	Máximo	15,686	
	Amplitude	35,831	

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min z - ext rot peak #E2H	Média	-12,701	1,613
	Mínimo	-20,032	
	Máximo	-0,800	
	Amplitude	19,232	
min z - ext rot peak#Mo1H	Média	-10,191	2,155
	Mínimo	-26,176	
	Máximo	-1,051	
	Amplitude	25,125	
min z - ext rot peak#Mo2H	Média	-8,618	1,572
	Mínimo	-19,920	
	Máximo	0,137	
	Amplitude	20,057	
min z - ext rot peak#Ma1H	Média	-7,848	1,644
	Mínimo	-22,481	
	Máximo	1,168	
	Amplitude	23,649	
min z - ext rot peak#Ma2H	Média	-8,065	1,363
	Mínimo	-18,845	
	Máximo	0,923	
	Amplitude	19,768	
min z - ext rot peak#ER1H	Média	-11,427	1,349
	Mínimo	-17,317	
	Máximo	0,133	
	Amplitude	17,450	

Joint Kinematics Friedman's Two-Way Analysis of Variance by Ranks:

Table 20 Friedman test ROM Z

Estatística de teste	17,571
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,007

Table 21- Multiple Comparisons Pairwise Method ROM Z

Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
ROM Z#Mo2A-ROM Z#Ma2A	-,154	,847	-,182	,856	1,000

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ROM Z#Mo2A-ROM Z#Ma1A	-,615	,847	-,726	,468	1,000
ROM Z#Mo2A-ROM Z#Mo1A	,615	,847	,726	,468	1,000
ROM Z#Mo2A-ROM Z#E2A	1,231	,847	1,453	,146	1,000
ROM Z#Mo2A-ROM Z#ER1A	-2,385	,847	-2,814	,005	,103
ROM Z#Mo2A-ROM Z#E1A	2,538	,847	2,996	,003	,057
ROM Z#Ma2A-ROM Z#Mo1A	,462	,847	,545	,586	1,000
ROM Z#Ma2A-ROM Z#Ma1A	,462	,847	,545	,586	1,000
ROM Z#Ma2A-ROM Z#E2A	1,077	,847	1,271	,204	1,000
ROM Z#Ma2A-ROM Z#ER1A	-2,231	,847	-2,633	,008	,178
ROM Z#Ma2A-ROM Z#E1A	2,385	,847	2,814	,005	,103
ROM Z#Mo1A-ROM Z#E2A	,615	,847	,726	,468	1,000
ROM Z#Ma1A-ROM Z#E2A	,615	,847	,726	,468	1,000
ROM Z#Ma1A-ROM Z#ER1A	-1,769	,847	-2,088	,037	,773
ROM Z#Mo1A-ROM Z#ER1A	-1,769	,847	-2,088	,037	,773
ROM Z#Ma1A-ROM Z#E1A	1,923	,847	2,270	,023	,488
ROM Z#Mo1A-ROM Z#Ma1A	,000	,847	,000	1,000	1,000
ROM Z#Mo1A-ROM Z#E1A	1,923	,847	2,270	,023	,488
ROM Z#E2A-ROM Z#ER1A	-1,154	,847	-1,362	,173	1,000
ROM Z#E2A-ROM Z#E1A	1,308	,847	1,543	,123	1,000
ROM Z#ER1A-ROM Z#E1A	,154	,847	,182	,856	1,000

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

Table 22 Friedman test ROM Z int/ext rot

Estatística de teste	12,725
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,048

Table 23- Multiple Comparisons Pairwise Method ROM Z int/ext

Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
ROM Z int/ext rot#Mo1K-ROM Z int/ext rot#Ma1K	-,462	,847	-,545	,586	1,000
ROM Z int/ext rot#Mo1K-ROM Z int/ext rot#Mo2K	-1,077	,847	-1,271	,204	1,000
ROM Z int/ext rot#Mo1K-ROM Z int/ext rot#Ma2K	-1,308	,847	-1,543	,123	1,000
ROM Z int/ext rot#Mo1K-ROM Z int/ext rot #E1K	1,923	,847	2,270	,023	,488
ROM Z int/ext rot#Mo1K-ROM Z int/ext rot #E2K	1,923	,847	2,270	,023	,488
ROM Z int/ext rot#Mo1K-ROM Z int/ext rot#ER1K	-2,462	,847	-2,905	,004	,077
ROM Z int/ext rot#Ma1K-ROM Z int/ext rot#Mo2K	,615	,847	,726	,468	1,000
ROM Z int/ext rot#Ma1K-ROM Z int/ext rot#Ma2K	-,846	,847	-,999	,318	1,000
ROM Z int/ext rot#Ma1K-ROM Z int/ext rot #E1K	1,462	,847	1,725	,085	1,000
ROM Z int/ext rot#Ma1K-ROM Z int/ext rot #E2K	1,462	,847	1,725	,085	1,000
ROM Z int/ext rot#Ma1K-ROM Z int/ext rot#ER1K	-2,000	,847	-2,360	,018	,383

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ROM Z int/ext rot#Mo2K-ROM Z int/ext rot#Ma2K	-,231	,847	-,272	,785	1,000
ROM Z int/ext rot#Mo2K-ROM Z int/ext rot #E1K	,846	,847	,999	,318	1,000
ROM Z int/ext rot#Mo2K-ROM Z int/ext rot #E2K	,846	,847	,999	,318	1,000
ROM Z int/ext rot#Mo2K-ROM Z int/ext rot#ER1K	-1,385	,847	-1,634	,102	1,000
ROM Z int/ext rot#Ma2K-ROM Z int/ext rot #E1K	,615	,847	,726	,468	1,000
ROM Z int/ext rot#Ma2K-ROM Z int/ext rot #E2K	,615	,847	,726	,468	1,000
ROM Z int/ext rot#Ma2K-ROM Z int/ext rot#ER1K	-1,154	,847	-1,362	,173	1,000
ROM Z int/ext rot #E1K- ROM Z int/ext rot #E2K	,000	,847	,000	1,000	1,000
ROM Z int/ext rot #E1K- ROM Z int/ext rot#ER1K	-,538	,847	-,635	,525	1,000
ROM Z int/ext rot #E2K- ROM Z int/ext rot#ER1K	-,538	,847	-,635	,525	1,000

Table 24 Friedman test ROM X

Estatística de teste	6,297 ^a
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,391

Table 25- Multiple Comparisons Pairwise MethodROM X

Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
ROM X#Ma2H-ROM X#Ma1H	,231	,847	,272	,785	1,000
ROM X#Ma2H-ROM X#Mo2H	1,077	,847	1,271	,204	1,000

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ROM X#Ma2H-ROM X#Mo1H	1,846	,847	2,179	,029	,616
ROM X#Ma2H-ROM X #E2H	2,077	,847	2,451	,014	,299
ROM X#Ma2H-ROM X#ER1H	-2,231	,847	-2,633	,008	,178
ROM X#Ma2H-ROM X #E1H	2,231	,847	2,633	,008	,178
ROM X#Ma1H-ROM X#Mo2H	,846	,847	,999	,318	1,000
ROM X#Ma1H-ROM X#Mo1H	1,615	,847	1,906	,057	1,000
ROM X#Ma1H-ROM X #E2H	1,846	,847	2,179	,029	,616
ROM X#Ma1H-ROM X#ER1H	-2,000	,847	-2,360	,018	,383
ROM X#Ma1H-ROM X #E1H	2,000	,847	2,360	,018	,383
ROM X#Mo2H-ROM X#Mo1H	,769	,847	,908	,364	1,000
ROM X#Mo2H-ROM X #E2H	1,000	,847	1,180	,238	1,000
ROM X#Mo2H-ROM X#ER1H	-1,154	,847	-1,362	,173	1,000
ROM X#Mo2H-ROM X #E1H	1,154	,847	1,362	,173	1,000
ROM X#Mo1H-ROM X #E2H	,231	,847	,272	,785	1,000
ROM X#Mo1H-ROM X#ER1H	-,385	,847	-,454	,650	1,000
ROM X#Mo1H-ROM X #E1H	,385	,847	,454	,650	1,000
ROM X #E2H-ROM X #E1H	,154	,847	,182	,856	1,000
ROM X #E2H-ROM X#ER1H	-,154	,847	-,182	,856	1,000
ROM X #E1H-ROM X#ER1H	,000	,847	,000	1,000	1,000

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Table 26 Friedman test ROM Y

Estatística de teste	1,813 ^a
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,936

Table 27 Friedman test ROM Y flx/ext

Estatística de teste	50,835
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	<,001

Table 28 Pairwise comparisons ROM Y flx/ext

Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo2K- ROM Y flx/ext#Mo1K	,538	,847	,635	,525	1,000
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo2K- ROM Y flx/ext#Ma1K	-,769	,847	-,908	,364	1,000
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo2K- ROM Y flx/ext#Ma2K	-,923	,847	-1,089	,276	1,000
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo2K- ROM Y flx/ext #E2K	3,308	,847	3,904	<,001	,002
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo2K- ROM Y flx/ext#ER1K	-3,769	,847	-4,448	<,001	,000
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo2K- ROM Y flx/ext #E1K	4,154	,847	4,902	<,001	,000
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo1K- ROM Y flx/ext#Ma1K	-,231	,847	-,272	,785	1,000
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo1K- ROM Y flx/ext#Ma2K	-,385	,847	-,454	,650	1,000
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo1K- ROM Y flx/ext #E2K	2,769	,847	3,268	,001	,023
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo1K- ROM Y flx/ext#ER1K	-3,231	,847	-3,813	<,001	,003
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo1K- ROM Y flx/ext #E1K	3,615	,847	4,267	<,001	,000
ROM Y flx/ext#Ma1K- ROM Y flx/ext#Ma2K	-,154	,847	-,182	,856	1,000
ROM Y flx/ext#Ma1K- ROM Y flx/ext #E2K	2,538	,847	2,996	,003	,057
ROM Y flx/ext#Ma1K- ROM Y flx/ext#ER1K	-3,000	,847	-3,541	<,001	,008
ROM Y flx/ext#Ma1K- ROM Y flx/ext #E1K	3,385	,847	3,995	<,001	,001

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ROM Y flx/ext#Ma2K- ROM Y flx/ext #E2K	2,385	,847	2,814	,005	,103
ROM Y flx/ext#Ma2K- ROM Y flx/ext#ER1K	-2,846	,847	-3,359	<,001	,016
ROM Y flx/ext#Ma2K- ROM Y flx/ext #E1K	3,231	,847	3,813	<,001	,003
ROM Y flx/ext #E2K- ROM Y flx/ext#ER1K	-,462	,847	-,545	,586	1,000
ROM Y flx/ext #E2K- ROM Y flx/ext #E1K	,846	,847	,999	,318	1,000
ROM Y flx/ext#ER1K- ROM Y flx/ext #E1K	,385	,847	,454	,650	1,000

Table Friedman test ROM X abd/add

Estatística de teste	6,330 ^a
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,387

Table 29 Friedman test and pairwise comparisons ROM Y flx/ext

Estatística de teste	50,835				
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	<,001				
Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo2K- ROM Y flx/ext#Mo1K	,538	,847	,635	,525	1,000
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo2K- ROM Y flx/ext#Ma1K	-,769	,847	-,908	,364	1,000
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo2K- ROM Y flx/ext#Ma2K	-,923	,847	-1,089	,276	1,000
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo2K- ROM Y flx/ext #E2K	3,308	,847	3,904	<,001	,002
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo2K- ROM Y flx/ext#ER1K	-3,769	,847	-4,448	<,001	,000
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo2K- ROM Y flx/ext #E1K	4,154	,847	4,902	<,001	,000
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo1K- ROM Y flx/ext#Ma1K	-,231	,847	-,272	,785	1,000
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo1K- ROM Y flx/ext#Ma2K	-,385	,847	-,454	,650	1,000

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

ROM Y flx/ext#Mo1K- ROM Y flx/ext #E2K	2,769	,847	3,268	,001	,023
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo1K- ROM Y flx/ext#ER1K	-3,231	,847	-3,813	<,001	,003
ROM Y flx/ext#Mo1K- ROM Y flx/ext #E1K	3,615	,847	4,267	<,001	,000
ROM Y flx/ext#Ma1K- ROM Y flx/ext#Ma2K	-,154	,847	-,182	,856	1,000
ROM Y flx/ext#Ma1K- ROM Y flx/ext #E2K	2,538	,847	2,996	,003	,057
ROM Y flx/ext#Ma1K- ROM Y flx/ext#ER1K	-3,000	,847	-3,541	<,001	,008
ROM Y flx/ext#Ma1K- ROM Y flx/ext #E1K	3,385	,847	3,995	<,001	,001
ROM Y flx/ext#Ma2K- ROM Y flx/ext #E2K	2,385	,847	2,814	,005	,103
ROM Y flx/ext#Ma2K- ROM Y flx/ext#ER1K	-2,846	,847	-3,359	<,001	,016
ROM Y flx/ext#Ma2K- ROM Y flx/ext #E1K	3,231	,847	3,813	<,001	,003
ROM Y flx/ext #E2K- ROM Y flx/ext#ER1K	-,462	,847	-,545	,586	1,000
ROM Y flx/ext #E2K- ROM Y flx/ext #E1K	,846	,847	,999	,318	1,000
ROM Y flx/ext#ER1K- ROM Y flx/ext #E1K	,385	,847	,454	,650	1,000

Table 30 Friedman test and pairwise comparisons ROM Y flex/ext

Estatística de teste	18,990				
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,004				
Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
ROM Y - flex/ext#Ma1H-ROM Y - flex/ext#Mo1H	,231	,847	,272	,785	1,000
ROM Y - flex/ext#Ma1H-ROM Y - flex/ext#Mo2H	,308	,847	,363	,717	1,000
ROM Y - flex/ext#Ma1H-ROM Y - flex/ext#Ma2H	-,615	,847	-,726	,468	1,000

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ROM Y - flex/ext#Ma1H-ROM Y - flex/ext#ER1H	-1,462	,847	-1,725	,085	1,000
ROM Y - flex/ext#Ma1H-ROM Y - flex/ext #E1H	2,192	,847	2,587	,010	,203
ROM Y - flex/ext#Ma1H-ROM Y - flex/ext #E2H	2,731	,847	3,223	,001	,027
ROM Y - flex/ext#Mo1H-ROM Y - flex/ext#Mo2H	-,077	,847	-,091	,928	1,000
ROM Y - flex/ext#Mo1H-ROM Y - flex/ext#Ma2H	-,385	,847	-,454	,650	1,000
ROM Y - flex/ext#Mo1H-ROM Y - flex/ext#ER1H	-1,231	,847	-1,453	,146	1,000
ROM Y - flex/ext#Mo1H-ROM Y - flex/ext #E1H	1,962	,847	2,315	,021	,433
ROM Y - flex/ext#Mo1H-ROM Y - flex/ext #E2H	2,500	,847	2,950	,003	,067
ROM Y - flex/ext#Mo2H-ROM Y - flex/ext#Ma2H	-,308	,847	-,363	,717	1,000
ROM Y - flex/ext#Mo2H-ROM Y - flex/ext#ER1H	-1,154	,847	-1,362	,173	1,000
ROM Y - flex/ext#Mo2H-ROM Y - flex/ext #E1H	1,885	,847	2,224	,026	,549
ROM Y - flex/ext#Mo2H-ROM Y - flex/ext #E2H	2,423	,847	2,860	,004	,089
ROM Y - flex/ext#Ma2H-ROM Y - flex/ext#ER1H	-,846	,847	-,999	,318	1,000
ROM Y - flex/ext#Ma2H-ROM Y - flex/ext #E1H	1,577	,847	1,861	,063	1,000

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ROM Y - flex/ext#Ma2H-ROM Y - flex/ext #E2H	2,115	,847	2,497	,013	,263
ROM Y - flex/ext#ER1H-ROM Y - flex/ext #E1H	,731	,847	,862	,388	1,000
ROM Y - flex/ext#ER1H-ROM Y - flex/ext #E2H	1,269	,847	1,498	,134	1,000
ROM Y - flex/ext #E1H-ROM Y - flex/ext #E2H	-,538	,847	-,635	,525	1,000

Table 31 Friedman test ROM Z

Estatística de teste	9,396 ^a
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,153

Table 32 Friedman test and pairwise comparisons max X supination peak

Estatística de teste	17,165				
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,009				
Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
max X - supination peak#ER1A-max X - supination peak #E2A	,577	,847	,681	,496	1,000
max X - supination peak#ER1A-max X - supination peak#Ma2A	1,308	,847	1,543	,123	1,000
max X - supination peak#ER1A-max X - supination peak #E1A	1,692	,847	1,997	,046	,962
max X - supination peak#ER1A-max X - supination peak#Mo2A	2,000	,847	2,360	,018	,383
max X - supination peak#ER1A-max X - supination peak#Ma1A	2,192	,847	2,587	,010	,203
max X - supination peak#ER1A-max X - supination peak#Mo1A	3,000	,847	3,541	<,001	,008

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

max X - supination peak #E2A-max X - supination peak#Ma2A	-,731	,847	-,862	,388	1,000
max X - supination peak #E2A-max X - supination peak #E1A	1,115	,847	1,316	,188	1,000
max X - supination peak #E2A-max X - supination peak#Mo2A	-1,423	,847	-1,680	,093	1,000
max X - supination peak #E2A-max X - supination peak#Ma1A	-1,615	,847	-1,906	,057	1,000
max X - supination peak #E2A-max X - supination peak#Mo1A	-2,423	,847	-2,860	,004	,089
max X - supination peak#Ma2A-max X - supination peak #E1A	,385	,847	,454	,650	1,000
max X - supination peak#Ma2A-max X - supination peak#Mo2A	,692	,847	,817	,414	1,000
max X - supination peak#Ma2A-max X - supination peak#Ma1A	,885	,847	1,044	,296	1,000
max X - supination peak#Ma2A-max X - supination peak#Mo1A	1,692	,847	1,997	,046	,962
max X - supination peak #E1A-max X - supination peak#Mo2A	-,308	,847	-,363	,717	1,000
max X - supination peak #E1A-max X - supination peak#Ma1A	-,500	,847	-,590	,555	1,000
max X - supination peak #E1A-max X - supination peak#Mo1A	-1,308	,847	-1,543	,123	1,000
max X - supination peak#Mo2A-max X - supination peak#Ma1A	-,192	,847	-,227	,820	1,000
max X - supination peak#Mo2A-max X - supination peak#Mo1A	1,000	,847	1,180	,238	1,000

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

max X - supination peak#Ma1A-max X - supination peak#Mo1A	,808	,847	,953	,340	1,000
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Table 33 Friedman test and pairwise comparisons min x pronation peak

Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
	31,750				
	<,001				
min x - pronation peak #E2A-min x - pronation peak#ER1A	-,423	,847	-,499	,618	1,000
min x - pronation peak #E2A-min x - pronation peak #E1A	,462	,847	,545	,586	1,000
min x - pronation peak #E2A-min x - pronation peak#Ma2A	-1,654	,847	-1,952	,051	1,000
min x - pronation peak #E2A-min x - pronation peak#Ma1A	-2,808	,847	-3,314	<,001	,019
min x - pronation peak #E2A-min x - pronation peak#Mo2A	-2,885	,847	-3,404	<,001	,014
min x - pronation peak #E2A-min x - pronation peak#Mo1A	-3,346	,847	-3,949	<,001	,002
min x - pronation peak#ER1A-min x - pronation peak #E1A	,038	,847	,045	,964	1,000
min x - pronation peak#ER1A-min x - pronation peak#Ma2A	1,231	,847	1,453	,146	1,000
min x - pronation peak#ER1A-min x - pronation peak#Ma1A	2,385	,847	2,814	,005	,103
min x - pronation peak#ER1A-min x - pronation peak#Mo2A	2,462	,847	2,905	,004	,077

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min x - pronation peak#ER1A-min x - pronation peak#Mo1A	2,923	,847	3,450	<,001	,012
min x - pronation peak #E1A-min x - pronation peak#Ma2A	-1,192	,847	-1,407	,159	1,000
min x - pronation peak #E1A-min x - pronation peak#Ma1A	-2,346	,847	-2,769	,006	,118
min x - pronation peak #E1A-min x - pronation peak#Mo2A	-2,423	,847	-2,860	,004	,089
min x - pronation peak #E1A-min x - pronation peak#Mo1A	-2,885	,847	-3,404	<,001	,014
min x - pronation peak#Ma2A-min x - pronation peak#Ma1A	1,154	,847	1,362	,173	1,000
min x - pronation peak#Ma2A-min x - pronation peak#Mo2A	1,231	,847	1,453	,146	1,000
min x - pronation peak#Ma2A-min x - pronation peak#Mo1A	1,692	,847	1,997	,046	,962
min x - pronation peak#Ma1A-min x - pronation peak#Mo2A	,077	,847	,091	,928	1,000
min x - pronation peak#Ma1A-min x - pronation peak#Mo1A	,538	,847	,635	,525	1,000
min x - pronation peak#Mo2A-min x - pronation peak#Mo1A	,462	,847	,545	,586	1,000

Table 34 Friedman test and pairwise comparisons max y dorsiflexion peak

Estatística de teste	28,052
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	<,001

Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
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Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

max y - dorsiflexion peak#Ma2A-max y - dorsiflexion peak#Ma1A	,154	,847	,182	,856	1,000
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Ma2A-max y - dorsiflexion peak#Mo2A	,462	,847	,545	,586	1,000
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Ma2A-max y - dorsiflexion peak#Mo1A	1,462	,847	1,725	,085	1,000
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Ma2A-max y - dorsiflexion peak #E1A	2,192	,847	2,587	,010	,203
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Ma2A-max y - dorsiflexion peak #E2A	2,808	,847	3,314	<,001	,019
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Ma2A-max y - dorsiflexion peak#ER1A	-3,154	,847	-3,722	<,001	,004
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Ma1A-max y - dorsiflexion peak#Mo2A	,308	,847	,363	,717	1,000
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Ma1A-max y - dorsiflexion peak#Mo1A	1,308	,847	1,543	,123	1,000
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Ma1A-max y - dorsiflexion peak #E1A	2,038	,847	2,406	,016	,339
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Ma1A-max y - dorsiflexion peak #E2A	2,654	,847	3,132	,002	,036
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Ma1A-max y - dorsiflexion peak#ER1A	-3,000	,847	-3,541	<,001	,008
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Mo2A-max y - dorsiflexion peak#Mo1A	1,000	,847	1,180	,238	1,000
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Mo2A-max y - dorsiflexion peak #E1A	1,731	,847	2,043	,041	,863
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Mo2A-max y - dorsiflexion peak #E2A	2,346	,847	2,769	,006	,118

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max y - dorsiflexion peak#Mo2A-max y - dorsiflexion peak#ER1A	-2,692	,847	-3,177	,001	,031
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Mo1A-max y - dorsiflexion peak #E1A	,731	,847	,862	,388	1,000
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Mo1A-max y - dorsiflexion peak #E2A	1,346	,847	1,589	,112	1,000
max y - dorsiflexion peak#Mo1A-max y - dorsiflexion peak#ER1A	-1,692	,847	-1,997	,046	,962
max y - dorsiflexion peak #E1A-max y - dorsiflexion peak #E2A	-,615	,847	-,726	,468	1,000
max y - dorsiflexion peak #E1A-max y - dorsiflexion peak#ER1A	-,962	,847	-1,135	,256	1,000
max y - dorsiflexion peak #E2A-max y - dorsiflexion peak#ER1A	-,346	,847	-,409	,683	1,000

Table 35 Friedman test and pairwise comparisonsPlantar flexion peak

Estatística de teste	18,107				
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,006				
Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Mo2A-min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Mo1A	,192	,847	,227	,820	1,000
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Mo2A-min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Ma1A	-,269	,847	-,318	,751	1,000
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Mo2A-min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Ma2A	-,577	,847	-,681	,496	1,000

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min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Mo2A-min y - Plantar Flexion peak #E2A	1,692	,847	1,997	,046	,962
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Mo2A-min y - Plantar Flexion peak #E1A	1,808	,847	2,133	,033	,691
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Mo2A-min y - Plantar Flexion peak#ER1A	-2,731	,847	-3,223	,001	,027
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Mo1A-min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Ma1A	-,077	,847	-,091	,928	1,000
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Mo1A-min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Ma2A	-,385	,847	-,454	,650	1,000
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Mo1A-min y - Plantar Flexion peak #E2A	1,500	,847	1,770	,077	1,000
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Mo1A-min y - Plantar Flexion peak #E1A	1,615	,847	1,906	,057	1,000
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Mo1A-min y - Plantar Flexion peak#ER1A	-2,538	,847	-2,996	,003	,057
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Ma1A-min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Ma2A	-,308	,847	-,363	,717	1,000
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Ma1A-min y - Plantar Flexion peak #E2A	1,423	,847	1,680	,093	1,000

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min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Ma1A-min y - Plantar Flexion peak #E1A	1,538	,847	1,816	,069	1,000
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Ma1A-min y - Plantar Flexion peak#ER1A	-2,462	,847	-2,905	,004	,077
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Ma2A-min y - Plantar Flexion peak #E2A	1,115	,847	1,316	,188	1,000
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Ma2A-min y - Plantar Flexion peak #E1A	1,231	,847	1,453	,146	1,000
min y - Plantar Flexion peak#Ma2A-min y - Plantar Flexion peak#ER1A	-2,154	,847	-2,542	,011	,231
min y - Plantar Flexion peak #E2A-min y - Plantar Flexion peak #E1A	,115	,847	,136	,892	1,000
min y - Plantar Flexion peak #E2A-min y - Plantar Flexion peak#ER1A	-1,038	,847	-1,226	,220	1,000
min y - Plantar Flexion peak #E1A-min y - Plantar Flexion peak#ER1A	-,923	,847	-1,089	,276	1,000

Table 36 Friedman test min z ext rotation peak

Estatística de teste	4,785 ^a
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,572

Table 37 Friedman test and pairwise comparisons min z int rotation peak

Estatística de teste	27,276
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	<,001

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
min z - int rotation peak #E1A-min z - int rotation peak#ER1A	-,231	,847	-,272	,785	1,000
min z - int rotation peak #E1A-min z - int rotation peak #E2A	-,346	,847	-,409	,683	1,000
min z - int rotation peak #E1A-min z - int rotation peak#Ma2A	-1,885	,847	-2,224	,026	,549
min z - int rotation peak #E1A-min z - int rotation peak#Ma1A	-2,269	,847	-2,678	,007	,155
min z - int rotation peak #E1A-min z - int rotation peak#Mo1A	-2,808	,847	-3,314	<,001	,019
min z - int rotation peak #E1A-min z - int rotation peak#Mo2A	-2,962	,847	-3,495	<,001	,010
min z - int rotation peak#ER1A-min z - int rotation peak #E2A	,115	,847	,136	,892	1,000
min z - int rotation peak#ER1A-min z - int rotation peak#Ma2A	1,654	,847	1,952	,051	1,000
min z - int rotation peak#ER1A-min z - int rotation peak#Ma1A	2,038	,847	2,406	,016	,339
min z - int rotation peak#ER1A-min z - int rotation peak#Mo1A	2,577	,847	3,041	,002	,049
min z - int rotation peak#ER1A-min z - int rotation peak#Mo2A	2,731	,847	3,223	,001	,027
min z - int rotation peak #E2A-min z - int rotation peak#Ma2A	-1,538	,847	-1,816	,069	1,000
min z - int rotation peak #E2A-min z - int rotation peak#Ma1A	-1,923	,847	-2,270	,023	,488

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

min z - int rotation peak #E2A-min z - int rotation peak#Mo1A	-2,462	,847	-2,905	,004	,077
min z - int rotation peak #E2A-min z - int rotation peak#Mo2A	-2,615	,847	-3,087	,002	,043
min z - int rotation peak#Ma2A-min z - int rotation peak#Ma1A	,385	,847	,454	,650	1,000
min z - int rotation peak#Ma2A-min z - int rotation peak#Mo1A	,923	,847	1,089	,276	1,000
min z - int rotation peak#Ma2A-min z - int rotation peak#Mo2A	1,077	,847	1,271	,204	1,000
min z - int rotation peak#Ma1A-min z - int rotation peak#Mo1A	,538	,847	,635	,525	1,000
min z - int rotation peak#Ma1A-min z - int rotation peak#Mo2A	,692	,847	,817	,414	1,000
min z - int rotation peak#Mo1A-min z - int rotation peak#Mo2A	-,154	,847	-,182	,856	1,000

Table 38 Friedman test and pairwise comparisons max x abd/add

Estatística de teste	19,634
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,003

Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
max x - abd/add #E1K-max x - abd/add#ER1K	,000	,847	,000	1,000	1,000
max x - abd/add #E1K-max x - abd/add #E2K	-,423	,847	-,499	,618	1,000
max x - abd/add #E1K-max x - abd/add#Ma2K	-1,269	,847	-1,498	,134	1,000
max x - abd/add #E1K-max x - abd/add#Mo2K	-1,808	,847	-2,133	,033	,691

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

max x - abd/add #E1K- max x - abd/add#Ma1K	-2,115	,847	-2,497	,013	,263
max x - abd/add #E1K- max x - abd/add#Mo1K	-2,731	,847	-3,223	,001	,027
max x - abd/add#ER1K- max x - abd/add #E2K	,423	,847	,499	,618	1,000
max x - abd/add#ER1K- max x - abd/add#Ma2K	1,269	,847	1,498	,134	1,000
max x - abd/add#ER1K- max x - abd/add#Mo2K	1,808	,847	2,133	,033	,691
max x - abd/add#ER1K- max x - abd/add#Ma1K	2,115	,847	2,497	,013	,263
max x - abd/add#ER1K- max x - abd/add#Mo1K	2,731	,847	3,223	,001	,027
max x - abd/add #E2K- max x - abd/add#Ma2K	-,846	,847	-,999	,318	1,000
max x - abd/add #E2K- max x - abd/add#Mo2K	-1,385	,847	-1,634	,102	1,000
max x - abd/add #E2K- max x - abd/add#Ma1K	-1,692	,847	-1,997	,046	,962
max x - abd/add #E2K- max x - abd/add#Mo1K	-2,308	,847	-2,724	,006	,136
max x - abd/add#Ma2K- max x - abd/add#Mo2K	,538	,847	,635	,525	1,000
max x - abd/add#Ma2K- max x - abd/add#Ma1K	,846	,847	,999	,318	1,000
max x - abd/add#Ma2K- max x - abd/add#Mo1K	1,462	,847	1,725	,085	1,000
max x - abd/add#Mo2K- max x - abd/add#Ma1K	-,308	,847	-,363	,717	1,000
max x - abd/add#Mo2K- max x - abd/add#Mo1K	,923	,847	1,089	,276	1,000
max x - abd/add#Ma1K- max x - abd/add#Mo1K	,615	,847	,726	,468	1,000

Table 39 Friedman and pairwise comparisons min x abd/add

Estatística de teste	25,945
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	<,001

Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
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Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

min x - abd/add #E1K- min x - abd/add#ER1K	,000	,847	,000	1,000	1,000
min x - abd/add #E1K- min x - abd/add #E2K	-1,077	,847	-1,271	,204	1,000
min x - abd/add #E1K- min x - abd/add#Mo1K	-2,231	,847	-2,633	,008	,178
min x - abd/add #E1K- min x - abd/add#Ma1K	-2,462	,847	-2,905	,004	,077
min x - abd/add #E1K- min x - abd/add#Ma2K	-2,615	,847	-3,087	,002	,043
min x - abd/add #E1K- min x - abd/add#Mo2K	-2,923	,847	-3,450	<,001	,012
min x - abd/add#ER1K- min x - abd/add #E2K	1,077	,847	1,271	,204	1,000
min x - abd/add#ER1K- min x - abd/add#Mo1K	2,231	,847	2,633	,008	,178
min x - abd/add#ER1K- min x - abd/add#Ma1K	2,462	,847	2,905	,004	,077
min x - abd/add#ER1K- min x - abd/add#Ma2K	2,615	,847	3,087	,002	,043
min x - abd/add#ER1K- min x - abd/add#Mo2K	2,923	,847	3,450	<,001	,012
min x - abd/add #E2K- min x - abd/add#Mo1K	-1,154	,847	-1,362	,173	1,000
min x - abd/add #E2K- min x - abd/add#Ma1K	-1,385	,847	-1,634	,102	1,000
min x - abd/add #E2K- min x - abd/add#Ma2K	-1,538	,847	-1,816	,069	1,000
min x - abd/add #E2K- min x - abd/add#Mo2K	-1,846	,847	-2,179	,029	,616
min x - abd/add#Mo1K- min x - abd/add#Ma1K	-,231	,847	-,272	,785	1,000
min x - abd/add#Mo1K- min x - abd/add#Ma2K	-,385	,847	-,454	,650	1,000
min x - abd/add#Mo1K- min x - abd/add#Mo2K	-,692	,847	-,817	,414	1,000
min x - abd/add#Ma1K- min x - abd/add#Ma2K	-,154	,847	-,182	,856	1,000
min x - abd/add#Ma1K- min x - abd/add#Mo2K	,462	,847	,545	,586	1,000

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

min x - abd/add#Ma2K- min x - abd/add#Mo2K	,308	,847	,363	,717	1,000
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Table 40 Friedman test 1st flexion peak

Estatística de teste	13,510
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,036

Table 41- Multiple Comparisons Pairwise Method 1st flexion peak

Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
1st flexion peak#E1K-1st flexion peak#Ma1K	-,731	,847	-,862	,388	1,000
1st flexion peak#E1K-1st flexion peak#Ma2K	-1,577	,847	-1,861	,063	1,000
1st flexion peak#E1K-1st flexion peak#Mo1K	-2,038	,847	-2,406	,016	,339
1st flexion peak#E1K-1st flexion peak#Mo2K	-2,038	,847	-2,406	,016	,339
1st flexion peak#E1K-1st flexion peak#ER1K	-2,115	,847	-2,497	,013	,263
1st flexion peak#E1K-1st flexion peak #E2K	-2,538	,847	-2,996	,003	,057
1st flexion peak#Ma1K-1st flexion peak#Ma2K	-,846	,847	-,999	,318	1,000
1st flexion peak#Ma1K-1st flexion peak#Mo2K	1,308	,847	1,543	,123	1,000
1st flexion peak#Ma1K-1st flexion peak#Mo1K	1,308	,847	1,543	,123	1,000
1st flexion peak#Ma1K-1st flexion peak#ER1K	-1,385	,847	-1,634	,102	1,000
1st flexion peak#Ma1K-1st flexion peak #E2K	1,808	,847	2,133	,033	,691
1st flexion peak#Ma2K-1st flexion peak#Mo2K	,462	,847	,545	,586	1,000
1st flexion peak#Ma2K-1st flexion peak#Mo1K	,462	,847	,545	,586	1,000
1st flexion peak#Ma2K-1st flexion peak#ER1K	-,538	,847	-,635	,525	1,000

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1st flexion peak#Ma2K- 1st flexion peak #E2K	,962	,847	1,135	,256	1,000
1st flexion peak#Mo1K- 1st flexion peak#Mo2K	,000	,847	,000	1,000	1,000
1st flexion peak#Mo1K- 1st flexion peak#ER1K	-,077	,847	-,091	,928	1,000
1st flexion peak#Mo2K- 1st flexion peak#ER1K	-,077	,847	-,091	,928	1,000
1st flexion peak#Mo2K- 1st flexion peak #E2K	,500	,847	,590	,555	1,000
1st flexion peak#Mo1K- 1st flexion peak #E2K	,500	,847	,590	,555	1,000
1st flexion peak#ER1K- 1st flexion peak #E2K	,423	,847	,499	,618	1,000

Table 42 Friedman test and pairwise comparisons 2nd flexion peak

Estatística de teste	50,451
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	<,001

Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
2nd flexion peak#Mo2K- 2nd flexion peak#Mo1K	,385	,847	,454	,650	1,000
2nd flexion peak#Mo2K- 2nd flexion peak#Ma1K	-,846	,847	-,999	,318	1,000
2nd flexion peak#Mo2K- 2nd flexion peak#Ma2K	-1,000	,847	-1,180	,238	1,000
2nd flexion peak#Mo2K- 2nd flexion peak #E2K	3,538	,847	4,176	<,001	,001
2nd flexion peak#Mo2K- 2nd flexion peak#E1K	3,808	,847	4,494	<,001	,000
2nd flexion peak#Mo2K- 2nd flexion peak#ER1K	-3,885	,847	-4,585	<,001	,000
2nd flexion peak#Mo1K- 2nd flexion peak#Ma1K	-,462	,847	-,545	,586	1,000
2nd flexion peak#Mo1K- 2nd flexion peak#Ma2K	-,615	,847	-,726	,468	1,000
2nd flexion peak#Mo1K- 2nd flexion peak #E2K	3,154	,847	3,722	<,001	,004

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2nd flexion peak#Mo1K- 2nd flexion peak#E1K	3,423	,847	4,040	<,001	,001
2nd flexion peak#Mo1K- 2nd flexion peak#ER1K	-3,500	,847	-4,131	<,001	,001
2nd flexion peak#Ma1K- 2nd flexion peak#Ma2K	-,154	,847	-,182	,856	1,000
2nd flexion peak#Ma1K- 2nd flexion peak #E2K	2,692	,847	3,177	,001	,031
2nd flexion peak#Ma1K- 2nd flexion peak#E1K	2,962	,847	3,495	<,001	,010
2nd flexion peak#Ma1K- 2nd flexion peak#ER1K	-3,038	,847	-3,586	<,001	,007
2nd flexion peak#Ma2K- 2nd flexion peak #E2K	2,538	,847	2,996	,003	,057
2nd flexion peak#Ma2K- 2nd flexion peak#E1K	2,808	,847	3,314	<,001	,019
2nd flexion peak#Ma2K- 2nd flexion peak#ER1K	-2,885	,847	-3,404	<,001	,014
2nd flexion peak #E2K- 2nd flexion peak#E1K	,269	,847	,318	,751	1,000
2nd flexion peak #E2K- 2nd flexion peak#ER1K	-,346	,847	-,409	,683	1,000
2nd flexion peak#E1K- 2nd flexion peak#ER1K	-,077	,847	-,091	,928	1,000

Table 43 Friedman testk and pairwise comparisons min y extension peak

Estatística de teste	16,714
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,010

Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
min y - extension peak #E1K-min y - extension peak#ER1K	-,615	,847	-,726	,468	1,000
min y - extension peak #E1K-min y - extension peak #E2K	-1,846	,847	-2,179	,029	,616
min y - extension peak #E1K-min y - extension peak#Ma2K	-2,000	,847	-2,360	,018	,383

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min y - extension peak #E1K-min y - extension peak#Ma1K	-2,231	,847	-2,633	,008	,178
min y - extension peak #E1K-min y - extension peak#Mo2K	-2,538	,847	-2,996	,003	,057
min y - extension peak #E1K-min y - extension peak#Mo1K	-2,615	,847	-3,087	,002	,043
min y - extension peak#ER1K-min y - extension peak #E2K	1,231	,847	1,453	,146	1,000
min y - extension peak#ER1K-min y - extension peak#Ma2K	1,385	,847	1,634	,102	1,000
min y - extension peak#ER1K-min y - extension peak#Ma1K	1,615	,847	1,906	,057	1,000
min y - extension peak#ER1K-min y - extension peak#Mo2K	1,923	,847	2,270	,023	,488
min y - extension peak#ER1K-min y - extension peak#Mo1K	2,000	,847	2,360	,018	,383
min y - extension peak #E2K-min y - extension peak#Ma2K	-,154	,847	-,182	,856	1,000
min y - extension peak #E2K-min y - extension peak#Ma1K	-,385	,847	-,454	,650	1,000
min y - extension peak #E2K-min y - extension peak#Mo2K	-,692	,847	-,817	,414	1,000
min y - extension peak #E2K-min y - extension peak#Mo1K	-,769	,847	-,908	,364	1,000
min y - extension peak#Ma2K-min y - extension peak#Ma1K	,231	,847	,272	,785	1,000
min y - extension peak#Ma2K-min y - extension peak#Mo2K	,538	,847	,635	,525	1,000

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min y - extension peak#Ma2K-min y - extension peak#Mo1K	,615	,847	,726	,468	1,000
min y - extension peak#Ma1K-min y - extension peak#Mo2K	,308	,847	,363	,717	1,000
min y - extension peak#Ma1K-min y - extension peak#Mo1K	,385	,847	,454	,650	1,000
min y - extension peak#Mo2K-min y - extension peak#Mo1K	,077	,847	,091	,928	1,000

Table 44 Friedman test max z int rot peak

Estatística de teste	17,637
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,007

Table 45- Multiple Comparisons Pairwise Method max Z- int/ext rot

Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
max z - int rot peak#Ma2K-max z - int rot peak#Mo2K	,538	,847	,635	,525	1,000
max z - int rot peak#Ma2K-max z - int rot peak#ER1K	-1,462	,847	-1,725	,085	1,000
max z - int rot peak#Ma1K-max z - int rot peak#Mo2K	,538	,847	,635	,525	1,000
max z - int rot peak#Ma1K-max z - int rot peak #E1K	2,077	,847	2,451	,014	,299
max z - int rot peak#Ma2K-max z - int rot peak #E1K	2,077	,847	2,451	,014	,299
max z - int rot peak#Ma1K-max z - int rot peak#ER1K	-1,462	,847	-1,725	,085	1,000

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

max z - int rot peak#Ma2K-max z - int rot peak#Mo1K	,385	,847	,454	,650	1,000
max z - int rot peak#Ma1K-max z - int rot peak#Mo1K	,385	,847	,454	,650	1,000
max z - int rot peak#Ma1K-max z - int rot peak #E2K	2,538	,847	2,996	,003	,057
max z - int rot peak#Ma2K-max z - int rot peak #E2K	2,538	,847	2,996	,003	,057
max z - int rot peak#Ma1K-max z - int rot peak#Ma2K	,000	,847	,000	1,000	1,000
max z - int rot peak#Mo1K-max z - int rot peak#Mo2K	-,154	,847	-,182	,856	1,000
max z - int rot peak#Mo1K-max z - int rot peak#ER1K	-1,077	,847	-1,271	,204	1,000
max z - int rot peak#Mo1K-max z - int rot peak #E1K	1,692	,847	1,997	,046	,962
max z - int rot peak#Mo1K-max z - int rot peak #E2K	2,154	,847	2,542	,011	,231
max z - int rot peak#Mo2K-max z - int rot peak#ER1K	-,923	,847	-1,089	,276	1,000
max z - int rot peak#Mo2K-max z - int rot peak #E1K	1,538	,847	1,816	,069	1,000
max z - int rot peak#Mo2K-max z - int rot peak #E2K	2,000	,847	2,360	,018	,383
max z - int rot peak#ER1K-max z - int rot peak #E1K	,615	,847	,726	,468	1,000
max z - int rot peak#ER1K-max z - int rot peak #E2K	1,077	,847	1,271	,204	1,000

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

max z - int rot peak #E1K-max z - int rot peak #E2K	-,462	,847	-,545	,586	1,000
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Table 46- Friedman test mi z ext rot peak

Estatística de teste	3,722 ^a
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,714

Table 47- Friedman test max x adduction peak

Estatística de teste	32,143
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	<,001

Table 48- Pairwise comparisons max x adduction peak

Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
max x - adduction peak#Ma2H-max x - adduction peak#Mo2H	,154	,847	,182	,856	1,000
max x - adduction peak#Ma2H-max x - adduction peak#Ma1H	,692	,847	,817	,414	1,000
max x - adduction peak#Ma2H-max x - adduction peak#Mo1H	1,077	,847	1,271	,204	1,000
max x - adduction peak#Ma2H-max x - adduction peak #E2H	2,462	,847	2,905	,004	,077
max x - adduction peak#Ma2H-max x - adduction peak #E1H	3,154	,847	3,722	<,001	,004
max x - adduction peak#Ma2H-max x - adduction peak#ER1H	-3,231	,847	-3,813	<,001	,003
max x - adduction peak#Mo2H-max x - adduction peak#Ma1H	-,538	,847	-,635	,525	1,000

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

max x - adduction peak#Mo2H-max x - adduction peak#Mo1H	,923	,847	1,089	,276	1,000
max x - adduction peak#Mo2H-max x - adduction peak #E2H	2,308	,847	2,724	,006	,136
max x - adduction peak#Mo2H-max x - adduction peak #E1H	3,000	,847	3,541	<,001	,008
max x - adduction peak#Mo2H-max x - adduction peak#ER1H	-3,077	,847	-3,631	<,001	,006
max x - adduction peak#Ma1H-max x - adduction peak#Mo1H	,385	,847	,454	,650	1,000
max x - adduction peak#Ma1H-max x - adduction peak #E2H	1,769	,847	2,088	,037	,773
max x - adduction peak#Ma1H-max x - adduction peak #E1H	2,462	,847	2,905	,004	,077
max x - adduction peak#Ma1H-max x - adduction peak#ER1H	-2,538	,847	-2,996	,003	,057
max x - adduction peak#Mo1H-max x - adduction peak #E2H	1,385	,847	1,634	,102	1,000
max x - adduction peak#Mo1H-max x - adduction peak #E1H	2,077	,847	2,451	,014	,299
max x - adduction peak#Mo1H-max x - adduction peak#ER1H	-2,154	,847	-2,542	,011	,231
max x - adduction peak #E2H-max x - adduction peak #E1H	,692	,847	,817	,414	1,000
max x - adduction peak #E2H-max x - adduction peak#ER1H	-,769	,847	-,908	,364	1,000
max x - adduction peak #E1H-max x - adduction peak#ER1H	-,077	,847	-,091	,928	1,000

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

Table 49 Friedman test min x abd peak

Estatística de teste	7,931 ^a
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,243

Table 50- Friedman test max y flexion peak and pairwise comparisons

Estatística de teste	24,661
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	<,001

Sample 1-Sample 2	Estatística de teste	Erro Padrão	Estatística de Teste Padrão	Sig.	Adj. Sig. ^a
max y - flexion peak#Mo1H-max y - flexion peak#Ma1H	-,077	,847	-,091	,928	1,000
max y - flexion peak#Mo1H-max y - flexion peak#Mo2H	-,308	,847	-,363	,717	1,000
max y - flexion peak#Mo1H-max y - flexion peak#Ma2H	-,538	,847	-,635	,525	1,000
max y - flexion peak#Mo1H-max y - flexion peak#ER1H	-1,385	,847	-1,634	,102	1,000
max y - flexion peak#Mo1H-max y - flexion peak #E1H	1,923	,847	2,270	,023	,488
max y - flexion peak#Mo1H-max y - flexion peak #E2H	3,308	,847	3,904	<,001	,002
max y - flexion peak#Ma1H-max y - flexion peak#Mo2H	,231	,847	,272	,785	1,000
max y - flexion peak#Ma1H-max y - flexion peak#Ma2H	-,462	,847	-,545	,586	1,000
max y - flexion peak#Ma1H-max y - flexion peak#ER1H	-1,308	,847	-1,543	,123	1,000

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

max y - flexion peak#Ma1H-max y - flexion peak #E1H	1,846	,847	2,179	,029	,616
max y - flexion peak#Ma1H-max y - flexion peak #E2H	3,231	,847	3,813	<,001	,003
max y - flexion peak#Mo2H-max y - flexion peak#Ma2H	-,231	,847	-,272	,785	1,000
max y - flexion peak#Mo2H-max y - flexion peak#ER1H	-1,077	,847	-1,271	,204	1,000
max y - flexion peak#Mo2H-max y - flexion peak #E1H	1,615	,847	1,906	,057	1,000
max y - flexion peak#Mo2H-max y - flexion peak #E2H	3,000	,847	3,541	<,001	,008
max y - flexion peak#Ma2H-max y - flexion peak#ER1H	-,846	,847	-,999	,318	1,000
max y - flexion peak#Ma2H-max y - flexion peak #E1H	1,385	,847	1,634	,102	1,000
max y - flexion peak#Ma2H-max y - flexion peak #E2H	2,769	,847	3,268	,001	,023
max y - flexion peak#ER1H-max y - flexion peak #E1H	,538	,847	,635	,525	1,000
max y - flexion peak#ER1H-max y - flexion peak #E2H	1,923	,847	2,270	,023	,488
max y - flexion peak #E1H-max y - flexion peak #E2H	-1,385	,847	-1,634	,102	1,000

Table 51- Friedman test min y extension peak

Estatística de teste	2,025 ^a
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,917

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

Table 52- Friedman test max z- int rot peak

Estatística de teste	5,983 ^a
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,425

Table 53- Friedman test min z- ext rot peak

Estatística de teste	10,945 ^a
Sinal assintótico (teste de dois lados)	,090

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

Table 54-Mo2 Pairwise Comparisons Summary

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

Mo2 vs	Ma1	Ma2	E1	E2	ER1
Step Length (cm) Avg-43,69 σ- 20.9	Avg-55,39 σ- 6.73	Avg-55,23 σ- 5.63	Avg-52,92 σ- 3.99	Avg-53,85 σ- 4.76	Avg-53,54 σ- 4.01
Step Time (s) Avg-0.62 σ- 0.09	Avg-0.61 σ- 0.08	Avg-0.61 σ- 0.07	Avg-0.59 σ- 0.06	Avg-0.60 σ- 0.06	Avg-0.59 σ- 0.06
Cycle Time (s) Avg-1.26 σ- 0.17	Avg-1.24 σ- 0.14	Avg-1.24 σ- 0.13	Avg-1.21 σ- 0.11	Avg-1.22 σ- 0.12	Avg-1.19 σ- 0.09
Swing Time (s) Avg-0.49 σ- 0.08	Avg-0.48 σ- 0.06	Avg-0.47 σ- 0.06	Avg-0.44 σ- 0.04	Avg-0.44 σ- 0.04	Avg-0.44 σ- 0.04
Stance Time (s) Avg-0.77 σ- 0.08	Avg-0.76 σ- 0.06	Avg-0.76 σ- 0.06	Avg-0.76 σ- 0.04	Avg-0.77 σ- 0.04	Avg-0.75 σ- 0.04
Steps PM (spm) Avg-96.73 σ- 6.59	Avg- 99.54 σ- 6.9	Avg-99.11 σ- 4.63	Avg-103.16 σ- 4.15	Avg-101.41 σ- 4.65	Avg-104.09 σ- 3.96
Strides PM (spm) Avg-48.36 σ- 26.92	Avg-48.23 σ- 11.60	Avg-48.98 σ- 10.43	Avg-50.43 σ- 10.47	Avg-49.68 σ- 10.51	Avg-50.67 σ- 10.13
ROM X (°) Avg-23.70 σ- 5.44	Avg-23.93 σ- 5.99	Avg-23.24 σ- 4.65	Avg-24.33 σ- 4.27	Avg-22.89 σ- 6.68	Avg-23.42 σ- 4.77
ROM Y (°) Avg-34.61 σ- 8.50	Avg-34.55 σ- 7.31	Avg-33.76 σ- 7.28	Avg-32.06 σ- 7.01	Avg-35.54 σ- 10.96°	Avg-33.40 σ- 4.94°
ROM Z (°) Avg-22.87 σ- 5.73	Avg-21.07 σ- 4.47	Avg-20.85 σ- 5.7	Avg-24.81 σ- 5.32	Avg-23.81 σ- 4.11	Avg-24.94 σ- 5.48
Supination Peak A (°) Avg-23.56 σ- 6.68	Avg-23.63 σ- 6.98	Avg-21.37 σ- 5.94	Avg-20.67 σ- 6.82	Avg-18.62 σ- 7.41	Avg-18.73 σ- 7.36
Min x Pronation Peak A (°) Avg-1.43 σ- 4.87	Avg-0.30 σ- 5.72	Avg-0.87 σ- 5.27	*Avg-4.36 σ- 5.30	*Avg-4.27 σ- 4.94	Avg-4.70 σ- 7.07°
Max Y dorsiflexion peak A (°) Avg-14.21 σ- 4.60	Avg-13.98 σ- 4.00	Avg-14.86 σ- 4.69	Avg16.90 σ- 4.13	*Avg-20.36 σ- 12.59	Avg-18.70 σ- 6.12
Min y - Plantar Flexion peak (°) Avg-20.40 σ- 9.14	Avg-19.58 σ- 8.08	Avg-18.91 σ- 8.45	Avg-15.56 σ- 7.55	Avg-15.18 σ- 7.97	*Avg-14.69 σ- 7.82
Internal Rotation Peak A Min z (°) Avg-2.41 σ- 5.30	Avg-2.68 σ- 5.56	Avg-3.67 σ- 5.60	*Avg-5.90 σ- 4.65	*Avg-6.50 σ- 6.66	*Avg-5.08 σ- 5.75
Max Z ext rot peak A (°) Avg-18.46 σ- 8.62	Avg-18.39 σ- 7.54	Avg-17.78 σ- 6.94	Avg-19.37 σ- 7.92	Avg-16.81 σ- 7.92	Avg-19.86 σ- 8.52
Abduction/Adduction K max X (°) Avg-6.23 σ- 3.71	Avg-6.02 σ- 3.93	Avg-5.72 σ- 3.80	Avg-4.41 σ- 2.91	Avg-5.12 σ- 4.70	Avg-4.22 σ- 2.59
Min X abd/add K (°) Avg-9.32 σ- 7.23	Avg-9.59 σ- 6.37	Avg-9.49 σ- 6.85	Avg-12.15 σ- 7.67	Avg-11.65 σ- 6.86	Avg-15.23 σ- 8.07
ROM X abd/add K (°) Avg-15.54	Avg15.62 σ- 7.15	Avg-15.21 σ- 7.6	Avg-16.55 σ- 6.69	Avg-16.77 σ- 7.85	Avg-16.31 σ- 7.27

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σ - 7.46					
ROM Z int/ext K (°) Avg-19.94 σ - 4.77	Avg-16.91 σ - 12.81	Avg-16.90 σ - 3.97	Avg-21.59 σ - 3.12	Avg-19.15 σ - 11.13	Avg20.96 σ - 6.38
MaxZ INT peak K (°) Avg-2.41 σ - 4.30	Avg-2.68 σ - 3.92	Avg-3.07 σ - 3.84	Avg-5.90 σ - 3.11	Avg-6.50 σ - 4.49	Avg-5.08 σ - 5.85
MinZ ext peak K (°) Avg-18.46 σ - 5.72	Avg-18.39 σ - 4.54	Avg-17.78 σ - 4.22	Avg-19.37 σ - 3.87	Avg-16.81 σ - 5.31	Avg-19.86 σ - 4.36
Min Y Extension Peak K (°) Avg0.25 σ - 2.70	Avg-0.41 σ - 3.32	Avg-0.30 σ - 2.52	Avg-1.47 σ - 2.59	Avg(-)0.11 σ - 3.46°	Avg(-)1.05 σ - 2.95
ROM Y flx/ext K (°) Avg-32.51 σ - 4.34	Avg-33.63 σ - 6.57	Avg-34.59 σ - 6.48	*Avg-40.45 σ - 6.25	*Avg-40.56 σ - 6.37	*Avg-38.85 σ - 7.24
1st flexion peak K (°) Avg-19.04 σ - 7.80	Avg-17.42 σ - 6.60	Avg-17.64 σ - 4.39	Avg-15.23 σ - 6.97	Avg-20.90 σ - 9.71	Avg-17.99 σ - 6.64
2nd Flexion Peak K (°) Avg-55.45 σ - 4.46	Avg-58.37 σ - 5.73	Avg-59.08 σ - 6.76	*Avg-65.76 σ - 7.09	*Avg-65.11 σ - 6.56	*Avg-64.94 σ - 8.77
Min Z ext rot peak H (°) Avg-18.57 σ - 5.67	Avg-18.80 σ - 5.93	Avg-18.67 σ - 4.91	Avg-18.63 σ - 8.98	Avg-17.43 σ - 5.82	Avg-19.53 σ - 4.86
Flexion Peak max y H (°) Avg-22.18 σ - 11.57	Avg-20.87 σ - 11.09	Avg-22.13 σ - 11.46	Avg-27.26 σ - 7.50	*Avg-30.87 σ - 7.89	Avg-25.23 σ - 8.38
ROM Z H (°) Avg-14.31 σ - 4.45	Avg-14.00 σ - 5.06	Avg-14.92 σ - 3.81	Avg-15.17 σ - 4.22	Avg-15.59 σ - 3.74	Avg-16.69 σ - 4.56
Max Z int rot peak H (°) Avg-1.38 σ - 3.61	Avg-1.00 σ - 2.54	Avg-1.24 σ - 2.15	Avg-2.85 σ - 5.05	Avg-4.15 σ - 5.86	Avg-1.43 σ - 4.01
ROM X H (°) Avg-12.13 σ - 3.079	Avg-11.60 σ - 3.84	Avg-11.12 σ - 3.15	Avg-13.89 σ - 2.64	Avg-13.87 σ - 2.09	Avg-13.46 σ - 2.74
ROM Y flx/ext H (°) Avg-33.51 σ - 6.48	Avg-33.63 σ - 5.98	Avg-34.59 σ - 7.87°	Avg-40.45 σ - 5.38	Avg-40.56 σ - 8.33	Avg-38.84 σ - 6.26
Min Y extension peak H (°) Avg-11.33 σ - 8.59	Avg-12.77 σ - 8.02	Avg-12.47 σ - 6.48	Avg-13.2 σ - 5.79	Avg-9.69 σ - 9.04	Avg-10.63 σ - 10.42
Max X add peak H (°) Avg-2.57 σ - 3.33	Avg-2.93 σ - 4.53	Avg-2.70 σ - 3.86	Avg-5.62 σ - 3.42	Avg-5.60 σ - 3.90	Avg-5.81 σ - 3.30
Min X abd peak H (°) Avg-9.62 σ - 3.39	Avg-8.68 σ - 3.38	Avg-8.42 σ - 3.01	Avg-8.28 σ - 3.71	Avg-8.28 σ - 4.60	Avg-7.65 σ - 3.92

Mo2vs E1

2nd flexion peak K 18.2% smaller; (55.446° vs 67.762°);
Min z - int rotation peak A 59.2% smaller; (2.406° vs 5.902°)
ROM Y flx/ext K 21.7% smaller (55.202° vs 67.235°).

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Mo2vs E2

max y - flexion peak, 29.2% smaller; (22.178o vs 30.869°).
2nd flexion peak K 14.8% smaller; (55.446° vs 65.105o);
Min z - int rotation peak A 63% smaller; ; (2.406° vs 6.503°)
Min x - pronation peak A 96.7% smaller; (0.143° vs 4.272°);
ROM Y flx/ext K 18.8% smaller. (55.202° vs 65.588°)

Mo2vs ER1

2nd flexion peak K 14.5% smaller; (55.446°vs 64.936°)
min x - abd/add 21.5% smaller; (9.317° vs 12.086°);
Min z - int rotation peak A 52.6% smaller; (2.406° vs 5.076°);
Min y - Plantar Flexion peak 26.8% bigger; (20.077° vs 14.694°)
ROM Y flx/ext K 19% smaller; (55.202° vs 65.986°)

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

Table 55- Mal Pairwise Comparisons Summary

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

Ma1 vs	Ma2	E1	E2	ER1
Step Length (cm) Avg-55,39 σ - 6.73	Avg-55,23 σ - 5.63	Avg-52,92 σ - 3.99	Avg-53,85 σ - 4.76	Avg-53,54 σ - 4.01
Step Time (s) Avg-0.61 σ - 0.08	Avg-0.61 σ - 0.07	Avg-0.59 σ - 0.06	Avg-0.60 σ - 0.06	Avg-0.59 σ - 0.06
Cycle Time (s) Avg-1.24 σ - 0.14	Avg-1.24 σ - 0.13	Avg-1.21 σ - 0.11	Avg-1.22 σ - 0.12	Avg-1.19 σ - 0.09
Swing Time (s) Avg-0.48 σ - 0.06	Avg-0.47 σ - 0.06	Avg-0.44 σ - 0.04	Avg-0.44 σ - 0.04	Avg-0.44 σ - 0.04
Stance Time (s) Avg-0.76 σ - 0.06	Avg-0.76 σ - 0.06	Avg-0.76 σ - 0.04	Avg-0.77 σ - 0.04	Avg-0.75 σ - 0.04
Steps PM (spm) Avg- 99.54 σ - 6.9	Avg-99.11 σ - 4.63	Avg-103.16 σ - 4.15	Avg-101.41 σ - 4.65	Avg-104.09 σ - 3.96
Strides PM (spm) Avg-48.23 σ - 11.60	Avg-48.98 σ - 10.43	Avg-50.43 σ - 10.47	Avg-49.68 σ - 10.51	Avg-50.67 σ - 10.13
ROM X (°) Avg-23.93 σ - 5.99	Avg-23.24 σ - 4.65	Avg-24.33 σ - 4.27	Avg-22.89 σ - 6.68	Avg-23.42 σ - 4.77
ROM Y (°) Avg-34.55 σ - 7.31	Avg-33.76 σ - 7.28	Avg-32.06 σ - 7.01	Avg-35.54 σ - 10.96°	Avg-33.40 σ - 4.94°
ROM Z (°) Avg-21.07 σ - 4.47	Avg-20.85 σ - 5.7	Avg-24.81 σ - 5.32	Avg-23.81 σ - 4.11	Avg-24.94 σ - 5.48
Supination Peak A (°) Avg-23.63 σ - 6.98	Avg-21.37 σ - 5.94	Avg-20.67 σ - 6.82	Avg-18.62 σ - 7.41	Avg-18.73 σ - 7.36
Min x Pronation Peak A (°) Avg-0.30 σ - 5.72	Avg-0.87 σ - 5.27	Avg-4.36 σ - 5.30	*Avg-4.27 σ - 4.94	Avg-4.70 σ - 7.07°
Max Y dorsiflexion peak A (°) Avg-13.98 σ - 4.00	Avg-14.86 σ - 4.69	Avg16.90 σ - 4.13	*Avg-20.36 σ - 12.59	*Avg-18.70 σ - 6.12
Min y - Plantar Flexion peak (°) Avg-19.58 σ - 8.08	Avg-18.91 σ - 8.45	Avg-15.56 σ - 7.55	Avg-15.18 σ - 7.97	Avg-14.69 σ - 7.82
Internal Rotation Peak A Min z (°) Avg-2.68 σ - 5.56	Avg-3.67 σ - 5.60	Avg-5.90 σ - 4.65	Avg-6.50 σ - 6.66	Avg-5.08 σ - 5.75
Max Z ext rot peak A (°) Avg-18.39 σ - 7.54	Avg-17.78 σ - 6.94	Avg-19.37 σ - 7.92	Avg-16.81 σ - 7.92	Avg-19.86 σ - 8.52
Abduction/Adduction K max X (°) Avg-6.02 σ - 3.93	Avg-5.72 σ - 3.80	Avg-4.41 σ - 2.91	Avg-5.12 σ - 4.70	Avg-4.22 σ - 2.59
Min X abd/add K (°) Avg-9.59 σ - 6.37	Avg-9.49 σ - 6.85	Avg-12.15 σ - 7.67	Avg-11.65 σ - 6.86	Avg-15.23 σ - 8.07

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ROM X abd/add K (°) Avg15.62 σ- 7.15	Avg-15.21 σ- 7.6	Avg-16.55 σ- 6.69	Avg-16.77 σ- 7.85	Avg-16.31 σ- 7.27
ROM Z int/ext K (°) Avg-16.91 σ- 12.81	Avg-16.90 σ- 3.97	Avg-21.59 σ- 3.12	Avg-19.15 σ- 11.13	Avg20.96 σ- 6.38
MaxZ INT peak K (°) Avg-2.68 σ- 3.92	Avg-3.07 σ- 3.84	Avg-5.90 σ- 3.11	Avg-6.50 σ- 4.49	Avg-5.08 σ- 5.85
MinZ ext peak K (°) Avg-18.39 σ- 4.54	Avg-17.78 σ- 4.22	Avg-19.37 σ- 3.87	Avg-16.81 σ- 5.31	Avg-19.86 σ- 4.36
Min Y Extension Peak K (°) Avg-0.41 σ- 3.32	Avg-0.30 σ- 2.52	Avg-1.47 σ- 2.59	Avg(-)0.11 σ- 3.46°	Avg(-)1.05 σ- 2.95
ROM Y flx/ext K (°) Avg-33.63 σ- 6.57	Avg-34.59 σ- 6.48	Avg-40.45 σ- 6.25	Avg-40.56 σ- 6.37	Avg-38.85 σ- 7.24
1st flexion peak K (°) Avg-17.42 σ- 6.60	Avg-17.64 σ- 4.39	Avg-15.23 σ- 6.97	Avg-20.90 σ- 9.71	Avg-17.99 σ- 6.64
2nd Flexion Peak K (°) Avg-58.37 σ- 5.73	Avg-59.08 σ- 6.76	*Avg-65.76 σ- 7.09	*Avg-65.11 σ- 6.56	*Avg-64.94 σ- 8.77
Min Z ext rot peak H (°) Avg-18.80 σ- 5.93	Avg-18.67 σ- 4.91	Avg-18.63 σ- 8.98	Avg-17.43 σ- 5.82	Avg-19.53 σ- 4.86
Flexion Peak max y H (°) Avg-20.87 σ- 11.09	Avg-22.13 σ- 11.46	Avg-27.26 σ- 7.50	*Avg-30.87 σ- 7.89	Avg-25.23 σ- 8.38
ROM Z H (°) Avg-14.00 σ- 5.06	Avg-14.92 σ- 3.81	Avg-15.17 σ- 4.22	Avg-15.59 σ- 3.74	Avg-16.69 σ- 4.56
Max Z int rot peak H (°) Avg-1.00 σ- 2.54	Avg-1.24 σ- 2.15	Avg-2.85 σ- 5.05	Avg-4.15 σ- 5.86	Avg-1.43 σ- 4.01
ROM X H (°) Avg-11.60 σ- 3.84	Avg-11.12 σ- 3.15	Avg-13.89 σ- 2.64	Avg-13.87 σ- 2.09	Avg-13.46 σ- 2.74
ROM Y flx/ext H (°) Avg-33.63 σ- 5.98	Avg-34.59 σ- 7.87°	*Avg-40.45 σ- 5.38	*Avg-40.56 σ- 8.33	*Avg-38.84 σ- 6.26
Min Y extension peak H (°) Avg-12.77 σ- 8.02	Avg-12.47 σ- 6.48	Avg-13.2 σ- 5.79	Avg-9.69 σ- 9.04	Avg-10.63 σ- 10.42
Max X add peak H (°) Avg-2.93 σ- 4.53	Avg-2.70 σ- 3.86	Avg-5.62 σ- 3.42	Avg-5.60 σ- 3.90	Avg-5.81 σ- 3.30
Min X abd peak H (°) Avg-8.68 σ- 3.38	Avg-8.42 σ- 3.01	Avg-8.28 σ- 3.71	Avg-8.28 σ- 4.60	Avg-7.65 σ- 3.92

Ma1 vs E1

2nd flexion peak K 11.2% smaller; (58.369° vs 67.762°).
ROM Y flx/ext K 16% smaller (57.957° vs 67.235°).

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

Ma1 vs E2

max y - flexion peak, 32.4% smaller; (20.862o vs 30.869°).
 2nd flexion peak K 10.3% smaller; (58.369° vs 65.105°);
 max y - dorsiflexion peak 17.8% smaller; (14.213° vs 18.051°)
 Min x - pronation peak A 92.9% smaller; (0.304° vs 4.272°);
 ROM Y flx/ext H 17,1% smaller (57.957° vs 65.588°)

Ma1 vs ER1

2nd flexion peak K 11,1%; smaller; (58.369° vs 64.936°)
 max y - dorsiflexion peak 25,3% smaller; (14.213° vs 18.704°)
 ROM Y flx/ext K 13.9% smaller. (57.957° vs 65.986°)

Tabela 56- Ma2 Pairwise Comparisons Summary

Ma2 vs	E1	E2	ER1
Step Lenght (cm) Avg-55,23 σ- 5.63	Avg-52,92 σ- 3.99	Avg-53,85 σ- 4.76	Avg-53,54 σ- 4.01
Step Time (s) Avg-0.61 σ- 0.07	Avg-0.59 σ- 0.06	Avg-0.60 σ- 0.06	Avg-0.59 σ- 0.06
Cycle Time (s) Avg-1.24 σ- 0.13	Avg-1.21 σ- 0.11	Avg-1.22 σ- 0.12	Avg-1.19 σ- 0.09
Swing Time (s) Avg-0.47 σ- 0.06	Avg-0.44 σ- 0.04	Avg-0.44 σ- 0.04	Avg-0.44 σ- 0.04
Stance Time (s) Avg-0.76 σ- 0.06	Avg-0.76 σ- 0.04	Avg-0.77 σ- 0.04	Avg-0.75 σ- 0.04
Steps PM (spm) Avg-99.11 σ- 4.63	Avg-103.16 σ- 4.15	Avg-101.41 σ- 4.65	Avg-104.09 σ- 3.96
Strides PM (spm) Avg-48.98 σ- 10.43	Avg-50.43 σ- 10.47	Avg-49.68 σ- 10.51	Avg-50.67 σ- 10.13
ROM X (°) Avg-23.24 σ- 4.65	Avg-24.33 σ- 4.27	Avg-22.89 σ- 6.68	Avg-23.42 σ- 4.77
ROM Y (°) Avg-33.76 σ- 7.28	Avg-32.06 σ- 7.01	Avg-35.54 σ- 10.96°	Avg-33.40 σ- 4.94°
ROM Z (°) Avg-20.85 σ- 5.7	Avg-24.81 σ- 5.32	Avg-23.81 σ- 4.11	Avg-24.94 σ- 5.48
Supination Peak A (°) Avg-21.37 σ- 5.94	Avg-20.67 σ- 6.82	Avg-18.62 σ- 7.41	Avg-18.73 σ- 7.36
Min x Pronation Peak A (°) Avg-0.87 σ- 5.27	Avg-4.36 σ- 5.30	Avg-4.27 σ- 4.94	Avg-4.70 σ- 7.07°
Max Y dorsiflexion peak A (°) Avg-14.86 σ- 4.69	Avg16.90 σ- 4.13	*Avg-20.36 σ- 12.59	*Avg-18.70 σ- 6.12
Min y - Plantar Flexion peak (°) Avg-18.91 σ- 8.45	Avg-15.56 σ- 7.55	Avg-15.18 σ- 7.97	Avg-14.69 σ- 7.82

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

Internal Rotation Peak A Min z (°) Avg-3.67 σ- 5.60	Avg-5.90 σ- 4.65	Avg-6.50 σ- 6.66	*Avg-5.08 σ- 5.75
Max Z ext rot peak A (°) Avg-17.78 σ- 6.94	Avg-19.37 σ- 7.92	Avg-16.81 σ- 7.92	Avg-19.86 σ- 8.52
Abduction/Adduction K max X (°) Avg-5.72 σ- 3.80	Avg-4.41 σ- 2.91	Avg-5.12 σ- 4.70	Avg-4.22 σ- 2.59
Min X abd/add K (°) Avg-9.49 σ- 6.85	Avg-12.15 σ- 7.67	Avg-11.65 σ- 6.86	*Avg-15.23 σ- 8.07
ROM X abd/add K (°) Avg-15.21 σ- 7.6	Avg-16.55 σ- 6.69	Avg-16.77 σ- 7.85	Avg-16.31 σ- 7.27
ROM Z int/ext K (°) Avg-16.90 σ- 3.97	Avg-21.59 σ- 3.12	Avg-19.15 σ- 11.13	Avg20.96 σ- 6.38
MaxZ INT peak K (°) Avg-3.07 σ- 3.84	Avg-5.90 σ- 3.11	Avg-6.50 σ- 4.49	Avg-5.08 σ- 5.85
MinZ ext peak K (°) Avg-17.78 σ- 4.22	Avg-19.37 σ- 3.87	Avg-16.81 σ- 5.31	Avg-19.86 σ- 4.36
Min Y Extension Peak K (°) Avg-0.30 σ- 2.52	Avg-1.47 σ- 2.59	Avg(-)0.11 σ- 3.46°	Avg(-)1.05 σ- 2.95
ROM Y flx/ext K (°) Avg-34.59 σ- 6.48	Avg-40.45 σ- 6.25	Avg-40.56 σ- 6.37	Avg-38.85 σ- 7.24
1st flexion peak K (°) Avg-17.64 σ- 4.39	Avg-15.23 σ- 6.97	Avg-20.90 σ- 9.71	Avg-17.99 σ- 6.64
2nd Flexion Peak K (°) Avg-59.08 σ- 6.76	*Avg-65.76 σ- 7.09	Avg-65.11 σ- 6.56	*Avg-64.94 σ- 8.77
Min Z ext rot peak H (°) Avg-18.67 σ- 4.91	Avg-18.63 σ- 8.98	Avg-17.43 σ- 5.82	Avg-19.53 σ- 4.86
Flexion Peak max y H (°) Avg-22.13 σ- 11.46	Avg-27.26 σ- 7.50	*Avg-30.87 σ- 7.89	Avg-25.23 σ- 8.38
ROM Z H (°) Avg-14.92 σ- 3.81	Avg-15.17 σ- 4.22	Avg-15.59 σ- 3.74	Avg-16.69 σ- 4.56
Max Z int rot peak H (°) Avg-1.24 σ- 2.15	Avg-2.85 σ- 5.05	Avg-4.15 σ- 5.86	Avg-1.43 σ- 4.01
ROM X H (°) Avg-11.12 σ- 3.15	Avg-13.89 σ- 2.64	Avg-13.87 σ- 2.09	Avg-13.46 σ- 2.74
ROM Yflx/ext H (°) Avg-34.59 σ- 7.87°	*Avg-40.45 σ- 5.38	Avg-40.56 σ- 8.33	*Avg-38.84 σ- 6.26

Biomechanical characterization of the gait pattern of healthy adults under different hypogravity conditions

Min Y extension peak H (°) Avg-12.47 σ - 6.48	Avg-13.2 σ - 5.79	Avg-9.69 σ - 9.04	Avg-10.63 σ - 10.42
Max X add peak H (°) Avg-2.70 σ - 3.86	Avg-5.62 σ - 3.42	Avg-5.60 σ - 3.90	Avg-5.81 σ - 3.30
Min X abd peak H (°) Avg-8.42 σ - 3.01	Avg-8.28 σ - 3.71	Avg-8.28 σ - 4.60	Avg-7.65 σ - 3.92

Ma2 vs E1

2nd flexion peak K 10.2% smaller. (59.084° vs 67.762°);
 ROM Y flx/ext K 14.4% smaller (58.788° vs 67.235°).

Ma2 vs E2

max y - flexion peak, 139.5% smaller. (22.125° vs 30.869°).
 max y - dorsiflexion peak 17.5% smaller (14.855° vs 18.051°)

Ma2 vs ER1

2nd flexion peak K 9.9%; (59.084° vs 64.936°)
 min x - abd/add 23% smaller. (9.486° vs 12.086°);
 max y - dorsiflexion peak 21.6% smaller. (18.704° vs 18.704°)
 ROM Y flx/ext K 12.2% smaller. (58.788° vs 65.986°)